

D1.1 Insights from the literature review on behavioural ethics, moral psychology & case-based methodologies and review of real-life case studies of research misconduct

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ABSTRACT

The first part of this deliverable is a **scoping review of the literature** examining 147 articles published in peer review academic journals over the past ten years (2013-2023) on the promotion of research ethics and integrity (REI), and breaches of these standards including research misconduct (RM) and questionable research practices (QRPs). It also identifies current challenges, gaps in knowledge and practice, and opportunities for both further research, and policy and educational interventions to promote REI and mitigate RM and QRPs. Findings on state-of-the-art knowledge in REI research suggest some areas of consensus, including on the greater risks for early career researchers to commit RM and the value of responsible conduct of research (RCR) training, particularly approaches that emphasize ethical problem-solving skills. However, the study also identified a lack of consensus in other areas, including the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers who committed RM. Key findings extracted from the review contribute to the understanding that the environment in which researchers operate and other contextual factors significantly influence RCR, rather than primarily the individual behavior of researchers. As such, these environmental and contextual factors require further research and policy attention.

The second part reports the findings of a **review of real-life cases** on REI, RM and QRPs. This review provides an in-depth qualitative evaluation of 23 cases that have appeared in the news media in the last five years across four partner countries within the BEYOND consortium – Estonia (3 cases), Latvia (5 cases), the Netherlands (9 cases) and the UK (6 cases). It thematically analyses these cases in relation to reporting and whistle-blowing, gender aspects (including discrimination, sexual harassment, and other forms of gender-based violence) and researcher working conditions, and identifies several novel and emerging factors affecting REI. Significant findings from this review include: the increasingly complex gender dimensions of REI in contemporary research; the changing nature of senior researchers' responsibility for RM; the roles of social media and online platforms in uncovering and publicizing RM; and the growing politicization of REI concerns in relation to wider political controversies. The review uses these findings to suggest evidence-based practical interventions to better monitor and prevent RM and QRPs, and offers recommendations for further research based on gaps identified in its analysis.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AI – Academic Integrity
CoI – Conflict of Interest
DFG – German Research Foundation
ENRIO – European Network of Research Integrity Offices
EC – European Commission
ECR – Early Career Researcher
GA – (Horizon Europe) Grant Agreement
GDP – Gross Domestic Product
GRU – (Norwegian) National Commission for the Investigation of Research Misconduct
HESA JACS - Higher Education Statistics Agency (UK) Joint Academic Coding System
HREC – Human Research Ethics Committee
IFA – Instructions for Authors
IRB – Institutional Review Board
LMICs – Low and Middle-Income Countries
LOWI – Netherlands Board on Research Integrity
NGO – Non-Governmental Organisation
PRISMA - Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses
QRP(s) – Questionable Research Practice(s)
RCR – Responsible Conduct of Research
RE – Research Ethics
REI – Research Ethics and Integrity
RFO – Research Funding Organisation
RI – Research Integrity
RIO – Research Integrity Office
RM – Research Misconduct
RMP – Research Misconduct Policy
RPO – Research Performing Organisation
SME – Small to Medium Enterprise esto
STEM – Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (disciplines)
TENK – (Finnish) National Board on Research Integrity
TPB – Theory of Planned Behaviour
UCL – University College London
UKRIO – UK Research Integrity Office
VU – Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
WoS – Web of Science

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents an overview of the current state-of-the-art in approaches within the field of Research Ethics and Integrity (REI) to addressing Research Misconduct (RM) and Questionable Research Practices (QRPs), and identifies emerging patterns and trends in this area, alongside recommendations for monitoring and mitigating RM and QRPs.

Scoping review of the REI literature

The first part of this deliverable contains a scoping review focusing on aspects of REI research relating behavioural and organisational ethics, moral psychology and case-based methodologies to identify the state-of-the-art knowledge in these areas. It also identifies current challenges, gaps in knowledge and practice, and opportunities for both further research and policy and educational interventions to promote REI and mitigate RM and QRPs. The review's methodology uses a systematic approach based on the PRISMA methodology for conducting literature reviews to examine 147 articles published in peer review academic journals over the past ten years (2013-2023) on the promotion of research ethics (RE) and research integrity (RI), and breaches of these standards including research misconduct (RM) and questionable research practices (QRPs).

The review's discussion evaluated in detail nine specific topics within the REI literature, which are listed below:

- Organisational and Behavioural Ethics:
- Moral psychology related to the promotion of REI and breaches of these standards
- Opportunities and challenges in the public and private sectors (including SMEs)
- Personal and institutional responsibilities for the promotion of REI
- Questions related to the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers
- Researchers' mental health and well-being in relation to research misconduct (including those employed in uncertain work conditions)
- Gender dimensions and power relations in the context of research misconduct
- Research on the effectiveness of research ethics and integrity training
- Case-based methodologies

Key findings on state-of-the-art knowledge in REI synthesized from the review include:

- The environment in which researchers operate and other contextual factors significantly influence the responsible conduct of research (RCR), rather than primarily the individual behavior of researchers. As such, these environmental and contextual factors require further research and policy attention.
- A consensus that early-career researchers are at higher risk to commit RM or QRPs.
- A consensus that there is no evidentiary basis that gender differences are a risk factor for engaging in RM, contrary to the hypothesis that men are more likely to commit RM.
- RCR training is valuable, particularly approaches that emphasize ethical problem-solving skills.
- There is a lack of agreement in the literature on effective strategies and approaches for the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers who committed RM.

- Opportunities exist for REI research to improve the rigour and quality of the evidence it gathers, and to incorporate greater context and complexity in its analyses and conclusions.
- REI research and governance must consider how to negotiate the balance between uniformity and diversity in policy interventions, education and the measurement of attitudes towards REI-related issues.

Case study review of real-life cases of RM and QRPs

The second part of the report provides a review of real-life cases on REI, RM and QRPs. It provides a broad comparative overview of the research context and REI landscape in the 13 BEYOND partner countries: Cyprus, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Latvia, the Netherlands, Norway and the UK. It then provides an in-depth qualitative case study analysis of 23 cases across four partner countries in BEYOND: Estonia, Latvia, the Netherlands and the UK, which forms the substantive portion of the review. These countries were selected to allow researchers with fluency in their local languages to obtain detailed case-based evidence that would not otherwise be accessible to non-speakers of these languages. Evidence was obtained for incidents and situations which involved implications of RM that were reported in the mainstream press media in the four countries and could be corroborated by additional sources such as other media reports, the Retraction Watch blog and database, official documents, official press statements, and evidence gathered from social media or professional profiles.

The review focuses specifically on how the gathered cases enhance understanding of factors and trends influencing RM across four thematic areas:

- Reporting and whistleblowing mechanisms
- Gender (including discrimination, sexual harassment, and other forms of gender-based violence)
- Researcher working conditions
- Novel and emerging factors

Key findings identified from the case studies evaluated in this review include:

- Mechanisms for reporting **and protecting whistle-blowers** are often weak and not formal enough to ensure robust action to halt RM, and that in some cases it can be in an institution's interest to not address cases of RM; However, this research also identified counter- examples in which institutions demonstrate best practice in supporting whistle-blowers and investigating their allegations in a serious and considered way
- There has been a shift in **gender-related considerations** within RM and QRP, in which research foci, topics and methods with particular gendered dimensions become the focus of REI concerns, rather than just issues concerning researchers' gender in itself being of concern
- Increasingly, **senior researchers are being held responsible** for the culture and behaviours that occur in the research teams they manage by both institutions and external REI advisory and adjudication bodies
- **Digital technology and social media** are increasingly affecting RM reporting and investigation, both in terms of the temporality of how REI concerns are mediated, and how and why RM allegations are brought forward
- **REI concerns and allegations of RM are increasingly becoming politicized** as part of broader political controversies over matters of scientific concern, including climate change and gender dysphoria treatment, with powerful implications for public trust in science

Based on these findings, the review offers the following recommendations:

- To better monitor cases of RM for transparency, as an evidence base for REI research, and to inform policymaking around REI, European (and global) Research Integrity Offices should **develop reporting mechanisms and repositories based on an interoperable rubric for reporting case studies** that includes criteria that facilitate qualitative depth
- A duty of care exists for hiring institutions to conduct due diligence work to prevent researchers with a history of committing RM continuing to do so elsewhere; Information-sharing and reporting mechanisms could be implemented at the international level to improve these processes
- To better support researchers who have committed RM, and redress unfairness caused by systemic issues in the research sector, further work must be done to develop and implement formal **rehabilitation and reintegration mechanisms** for these researchers;
- **Further empirical research on the relationship between researchers' mental health and wellbeing and RM** should be carried out in order to better support researchers in these areas, and to mitigate the occurrence of RM and QRPs

Part 1 – Insights from the literature review on behavioural ethics, moral psychology & case-based methodologies

1.1. INTRODUCTION

1.1.1. Purpose of the review

This scoping review, carried out as part of the Horizon Europe BEYOND Project (<https://beyondbadapples.eu>), focuses on the state-of-the-art knowledge in research ethics and integrity (REI). It seeks out the most up-to-date research on the reasons why researchers commit research misconduct (RM) and Questionable Research Practices (QRPs) and consolidates these recent developments in the field with challenges, gaps and limitations, and opportunities identified through the review and will have the potential to highlight new pathways for innovative policy and educational interventions to promote REI and mitigate RM. These findings will be useful for researchers in the field of REI, researchers in academic, commercial and third-sector research performing organisations (RPOs), university educators, REI practitioners and policy makers. This report ultimately aims to facilitate interventions that will engage with a more complex socio-systemic perspective to addressing the factors that influence RM and lapses in REI standards, rather than focusing solely on individual researchers' agency as the primary cause of RM or QRPs. Such an approach will help to create more meaningful REI governance and education that extends beyond treating these as compliance exercises, or oversimplifying RM as a problem of individual malfeasance and avoid accepting institutional, communal, and governmental responsibility when RM occurs.

1.1.2. Review Scope

The scope of this review was defined by the Grant Agreement for the BEYOND project, and forms part of Work Package 1 (WP1): Literature Review and Monitoring of Cases. The project evaluates the complex combination of individual and organisational factors that influence REI, rather than framing RM as a problem caused by individual researchers who are 'bad apples' that spread questionable research practices across an institution, discipline or the scientific community (Redman, 2013). To do this, BEYOND examines existing behavioural and related evidence-based approaches, and engages with relevant stakeholders to co-create a more holistic approach to managing RM and promoting REI through four linked conceptual approaches: *EXPLORE*, *ENGAGE*, *GUIDE*, and *EQUIP*. The findings of this review will feed into the public consultation process in BEYOND WP2: Public Consultation and Stakeholder Engagement, and will shape the work of WP5: Best Practices Manual, Guidelines to Supplement SOPs, and Roadmap 2030. The latter entails the development of a new best practice manual and guidelines to supplement existing REI policies, new training materials and tools for REI education, and a 2030 Roadmap for improving REI culture.

1.1.3. Overview of Methodology

The methodology for this review is based on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) methodology (M. J. Page et al., 2021) for conducting systematic literature reviews. Contributors reviewed a combined total of 8,663 records identified through searches in seven academic databases (University of Edinburgh Library, Google Scholar, PubMed, Erasmus University Library, Scopus, Web of Science, EBSCO Academic Search Complete) supplemented by references captured from other publications and Google search, and in some cases identified through 'snowballing' from other sources' bibliographies or Google search. From the sources that were screened, 147 articles were found to meet the inclusion criteria for this review, and form part of the final analysis. PRISMA charts for this activity are provided in Appendix A of this document.

1.1.4. Document Structure

Section 2 details the methodology of the review, along with a description of the process through which the review was conducted. Section 3 of the document provides a detailed empirical discussion of the different aspects of REI research that were investigated in this review. These are as follows:

- Section 3.1. Organisational and Behavioural Ethics
- Section 3.2. Moral psychology related to the promotion of REI and breaches of these standards
- Section 3.3. Opportunities and challenges in the public and private sectors (including SMEs)
- Section 3.4. Personal and institutional responsibilities for the promotion of REI and breaches of these standards
- Section 3.5. Questions related to the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers
- Section 3.6. Researchers' mental health and well-being in relation to research misconduct (including those employed in uncertain work conditions)
- Section 3.7. Gender dimensions and power relations in the context of research misconduct
- Section 3.8. Research on the effectiveness of REI training
- Section 3.9. Case-based methodologies

Each of the sub-sections evaluating the specific aspects listed above are structured in line with the review's scope of identifying state-of-the-art knowledge, challenges, gaps and limitations, and opportunities relating to the specific area of literature to which they pertain. References from sources identified and included as part of the review itself are listed under the '*Bibliography*' sub-heading at the end of each discussion section in which they appear, whereas supplementary sources that are outside the inclusion criteria of the literature review are listed under a separate sub-heading titled '*Additional References.*' Alongside the qualitative analysis component of the discussion, descriptive statistics were collated on the articles reviewed for each topic for methodological approaches, disciplinary purview, theoretical approach, publication year and geographical focus.

Section 4 presents a synthesis and conclusions of the findings of the study. This entailed a quantitative synthesis of the descriptive statistics gathered for each subsection of Section 3. These are represented through graphic visualisations of the synthesized data. Supplementing this is a qualitative discussion that highlights crosscutting themes across the discussion topics examined in Section 3, and distils the most significant findings on state-of-the-art knowledge, challenges, gaps and limitations, and opportunities identified through the review.

1.1.5. Additional References

Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*, n71.

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1.2. METHODOLOGY

1.2.1. Framing

The methodology for this literature review was designed for the purpose of reviewing the literature on behavioural and organisational ethics, and moral psychology related to the promotion of REI and breaches of these standards in order to answer the research question ‘why do researchers engage in RM?’ To achieve this aim, contributors adopted a comprehensive and systematic approach by adopting a scoping review methodology derived from Munn et al. (2018). The purpose of a scoping review is to “determine the scope or coverage of a body of literature on a given topic and give clear indication of the volume of literature and studies available” and their focus, as well as to “examine emerging evidence” in a field (Munn et al., 2018, p. 2). This entails identifying evidence, clarifying key concepts, examining methods used in the field, identifying key characteristics relating to REI and analysing knowledge gaps. The relevant areas of research on REI chosen for each sub-field in Section 3 were listed as areas of particular interest in the BEYOND Grant Agreement (GA) task description pertaining to this review. In some instances source authors used different terminology and/or multiple terms interchangeably, e.g. research misconduct and scientific misconduct (SM). In general, this review will apply the terminology used by the original authors, which leads to more a nuanced but complex lexicon for describing concepts in the REI field.

1.2.2. Selection Process

The process for identifying relevant articles for inclusion in the study was a four-stage process of SEARCH>SCREENING>SELECTION>ANALYSIS & SYNTHESIS based on the PRISMA framework (Page et al., 2021) for conducting and evidencing systematic literature searches. This entailed conducting initial searches based on relevant keywords identified by the contributing researchers in scholarly databases decided by the contributor, including Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science. The results of these searches were then recorded by the respective contributor. APPENDIX A of this report documents the results for these searches and the corresponding PRISMA flowcharts.

From the initial searches, the titles, and abstracts for identified articles were then reviewed and screened for inclusion based on the following criteria:

- Peer-reviewed full-length research articles published in academic journals or conference proceedings (a collective decision was taken by the contributors to include the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews as a valid source)
- Publication within the last ten years (2013-2023)
- Written in the English Language
- Duplicate articles were moved to the most relevant thematic area where appropriate. However, several articles are duplicated in multiple sub-sections of the discussion, as each sub-section addresses significantly different aspects of the duplicated articles’ findings.

1.2.3. Analysis and Descriptive Statistics

The articles included in the final selection for review in each sub-topic from the screening stage were then read in full by the contributors and analysed in accordance with the scoping criteria set out in the GA: *methodologies used, state-of-the art knowledge, challenges, gaps and limitations, and opportunities*. These findings were then recorded in the qualitative discussion found in Section 3. Supplementing the qualitative discussion, descriptive statistics were collated by the contributors for each sub-topic for the following data, which can be found in APPENDIX B:

- Total articles included in each sub-section.

- Methodologies used to evaluate each topic – These were divided into three orders of classification: Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed Methods; Primary or Secondary Data (primary data means that original data collection by the researchers took place, while secondary data collates and synthesizes existing analyses of primary data); Specific methods used (Survey, Case Study, interview/focus group, Literature Review, Documentary Analysis, Stakeholder Engagement/Participatory Design, Other). This allows consideration of whether certain disciplines are dominant in the literature and helps to measure their influence in shaping the academic discourse in a given area. Disciplinary focus was divided into 27 categories, and articles were classified according to the primary disciplinary focus of the article. These categories are based on a combination of the Web of Science (WoS) classification system with the first-order categories of UK Higher Education Statistics Agency Joint Academic Coding System (HESA JACS 3.0) system in order to provide a balanced spectrum across the disciplines and mitigate the bias of the WoS system towards science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) discipline to the exclusion of the social sciences and arts and humanities. In addition, an *ad hoc* category was added for articles focusing on practitioners in professional REI governance and policy roles. Articles that were non-specific to any academic discipline or addressed multiple disciplines were recorded under the ‘multidisciplinary’ category.
- Theoretical Approach – Here articles were classified according to whether they applied a specific theoretical approach, and if so, the number of articles relating to a given approach was recorded. This was designed to both demonstrate whether there is a theoretical orientation towards analysing REI/RM and QRPs full stop, and if so, to identify what the dominant theoretical paradigms are for examining these areas.
- Keywords for included articles – This category highlights the specific search terms relevant to the articles included in the study post-screening.
- Articles by publication year – This provides a year-by-year breakdown of when articles in a given sub-topic were published. This was useful to identify trends in whether a particular topic of study received increased and more recent attention, or conversely had become less popular.
- Geographical focus – Studies were recorded as either non-country specific, multi-country or country specific, denoting the relevant country.

This enabled analysis of whether particular countries or geographical regions were more represented than others, and thus playing a more outsized role in shaping the academic discourse on a particular topic evaluated in this review.

These descriptive statistics for the individual topics examined in Section 3 were then collated, visually represented, and comparatively evaluated in the synthesis in Section 4. To facilitate clarity and to derive more coherent analytical value from the data, some data was reorganized and recombined, including merging two duplicate categories. Most notably, the disciplinary data was aggregated to remove null values that would add noise to the data visualisations, and to demonstrate patterns and trends more prominently.

The synthesis also contains a qualitative summary that highlights common features and cross-cutting themes across the discussion in Section 3. This provides an overview of key trends in state-of-the-art knowledge in REI research over the last ten years, and synthesizes key challenges, research gaps and opportunities in keeping with the unifying criteria guiding the present research exercise.

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1.3. DISCUSSION OF TOPICS

1.3.1. *Organisational and Behavioural Ethics*

1.3.1.1. *Introduction*

This sub-section assesses existing key literature covering organisational and behavioural ethics with a focus on researchers, and students' knowledge, perceptions, and attitudes. Moreover, the reviewed literature provides guidelines for practices surrounding ethical research and mechanisms for compliance with legal, regulatory and institutional policy obligations relating to REI. Articles provide insights on the state of ethics education, the important role of institutional research culture(s), various pressures affecting researchers and the quality of outputs as well as the significant influence the cultural context has on research practice.

Conducting research in an ethical way through all its stages is crucial. A lack of organisational and behavioural ethics can have severe consequences for individuals and institutions involved in RM and QRPs. At its extreme, this is illustrated by the violent suicide of a severely mentally unwell young man in 2015 who participated in an industry-sponsored drug study in the US (Elliott, 2017). The patient was recruited by a psychiatrist involved in the study, who was the head of the University of Minnesota's schizophrenia research programme, whilst also being responsible for overseeing the patient's care under a court-ordered involuntarily commitment to a state psychiatric hospital. The list of misconduct by the university and its faculty related to the incident included coerced recruitment, conflict of interests, inadequate clinical care, inadequate institutional oversight and attempting to evade investigative scrutiny and responsibility (Elliott, 2017).

1.3.1.2. *Methodological Approaches*

This section evaluates the methodological approaches used in the articles reviewed in this study relating to behavioural and organisational ethics. 37 peer reviewed articles were analysed to scope the methodological approaches applied to research this topic. These methodological approaches included both qualitative (n=22), quantitative (n=11) and mixed (n=4) analysis, and the analysis of both primary (n=24) and secondary (n=13) data.

The most prevalent approach overall was quantitative primary survey analysis (n=9) and qualitative secondary literature review (n=7). Quantitative primary surveys were largely used to study attitudes and perceptions towards ethics (Janakiram & Gardens, 2014; Malički et al., 2019; Okonta & Rossouw, 2014; Raj et al., 2022; Rani, 2022; Shamsoddin et al., 2021; Trigotra et al., 2019) in various contexts ranging from medicine (Janakiram & Gardens, 2014; Raj et al., 2022; Rani, 2022; Shamsoddin et al., 2021) to departments in universities (Malički et al., 2019; Okonta & Rossouw, 2014) and publications (Trigotra et al., 2019). Trigotra et al. (2019) used a survey methodology to study post-training improvement in knowledge and attitude regarding publication ethics amongst postgraduate students. Additionally, mixed analysis of surveys was conducted in three (n=3) articles (Handal et al., 2021; Houle et al., 2023; Twist et al., 2018), most notably to study harassment and gender-based discrimination as research misconduct (Houle et al., 2023).

Qualitative literature reviews were used to evaluate studies pertaining to definitions and overviews of relevant concepts. This includes defining cronyism, nepotism and favouritism in the publication industry (Teixeira Da Silva et al., 2019), and definitions of misconduct (Hesselmann et al., 2017) and Research Integrity (RI) in relation to publication ethics (Mishra & Dabas, 2021). Other literature reviews evaluated knowledge around reasons for RM (Hanganu & Ioan, 2019), and mechanisms surrounding Research Ethics (RE), RI and RM in higher education in a pan-African context (Simiyu

et al., 2021). Two studies used literature reviews to study the relationship between attitudes to dishonesty and political climate with a recommendation for a holistic approach to REI and new role models (Bazoukis et al., 2020; Beever, 2021).

Documentary analysis of annual reports from the US Department of Health and Human Services' (HHS) Office of Research Integrity (ORI) during the period 1994–2012 was used to study the interrelationship between research integrity, conflict of interest, and the research environment (Grinnell, 2014). Documentary analysis was also used to review how international RE guidelines have been translated into a local context (Satalkar & Shaw, 2015). Bak (2018) used a qualitative secondary case study methodology to investigate how social and cultural context influence the reasons for and nature of research misconduct and the need to attend to local contexts.

Workshops were used in two studies. Reid et al. (2021) used focus groups, and stakeholder engagement to develop a toolkit to support integrity and ethical action. Sivasubramaniam and colleagues (2021) used workshops to evaluate institutional ethics approval processes, which differs in every institution, but is an imperative process in which proactive thinking is essential to identify ethical issues that might affect the project.

1.3.1.3. State-of-the-Art Knowledge

Overall, several articles formulated **guidelines for practices surrounding research ethics** such as ethical approval processes and clarifications on definitions such as for plagiarism (Hanganu & Ioan, 2019; Houle et al., 2023; Mishra & Dabas, 2021; Sivasubramaniam et al., 2022). Notably, Houle et al. (2023) who investigated unethical research practices in the physics community include harassment and gender-based discrimination in their assessment.

Some articles examined the **overall state of academic publishing**. Lins and Carvalho (2014), for instance, focused on assessing trends in quantity versus quality in Brazilian publications. They identify an increase in quantity of scientific outputs while the quality of scientific outputs had declined (Lins & Carvalho, 2014). An observed increase in retracted articles may be due to the low barriers to publication of flawed articles (Steen et al., 2013). Aspects such as lacking a universal definition of scientific misconduct, an inadequate evaluation of severity of scientific misconduct, and an untransparent decision-making process concerning retractions may play into the quantity of retractions too (Hesselmann et al., 2017).

Various scholars investigated **how knowledgeable researchers and students are concerning REI** requirements as well as concepts (Houle et al., 2023; Janakiram & Gardens, 2014; Raj et al., 2022; Twist et al., 2018). For instance, there can be varying definitions of REI amongst a university community which are often too narrow (Twist et al., 2018). In the Indian context specifically, the extent of knowledge about plagiarism appeared to be low amongst undergraduate medical students (Raj et al., 2022). Furthermore, the knowledge of Indian students on medical ethics appeared to be 'satisfactory' – with progress noticeable as students' progress through university (Rani, 2022). More practically, students may not be equipped to resolve the ethical dilemmas they encounter (Janakiram & Gardens, 2014). Regardless, Hanganu and Ioan (2019) emphasize researchers' responsibilities and professional requirements to acquire the necessary knowledge about good practice in research.

Closely linked to this is the issue of **ethics education**. Aubert Bonn and Pinxten (2019) provide an overview of the emergence of RE as a field of study, including relevant methods and institutional actors. Notably, they highlight the low proportion of scientific articles on RI that report empirical data (Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2019). In general, literature problematizes the lack of appropriate

incorporation of ethics into curricula that would be beneficial to students (Janakiram & Gardens, 2014; Raj et al., 2022; Rani, 2022). For instance, a survey conducted after providing an orientation on ‘Publication Ethics’ revealed a significant post-training improvement in knowledge and attitude regarding publication ethics amongst postgraduate students (Trigotra et al., 2019).

Several articles examined research carried out by **practitioners** in applied fields and contexts, including institutional research ethics practitioners. Capaldi (2021) applied a systems approach to better understand the research ethics system, particularly the application of RE in work carried out by a global non-governmental organisation (NGO) working with vulnerable children. The article reveals a lack of independent and recognized ethical research standards in NGO research with often no external accountability or vetting to either government review committees or institutional review boards (IRBs) (Capaldi, 2021). Handal et al. (2021) specifically investigated the perspectives of IRB practitioners, finding that members of Human Research Ethics Committees (HREC) ethical perspectives’ appear to be aligned with sound principles for ethics reviews. Notably, Beever (2021) discusses the role of ethics centres, whose roles should be re-framed to include working with communities to foster an understanding of ethics.

Several articles highlight the important **role of institutional research culture(s)** (Asai et al., 2016; Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2021; Edwards & Roy, 2017; Elliott, 2017; Houle et al., 2023; Malički et al., 2019; Sivasubramaniam et al., 2022). As part of a survey in Croatia, Malički et al. (2019) identified the prevailing ethical climate at three different schools of a single university. According to these authors, ethical climate measures “shared perceptions of ethically correct behaviours and ways by which ethical issues should be handled within an organisation (Malički et al., 2019, p. 233). Knowing the dominant ethical climates may enhance the understanding of both the interpersonal and group dynamics at a workplace (Malički et al., 2019). Crucially, the institutional culture(s) can contribute to and even incentivize research misconduct (Elliott, 2017). For instance, institutions may cover up RM to protect their interests and to avoid legal liability (Elliott, 2017). On the other hand, the organisational vision and the organisation’s willingness to abide by internationally accepted ethical principles appear key in enabling the establishment as well as sustainability of ethical behaviour amongst researchers (Sivasubramaniam et al., 2022). Stakeholders – such as policy makers, funders, institution leaders, editors/publishers, RI office members, RI community members, laboratory technicians, researchers, research students, and former researchers – have been identified as also playing a role regarding REI and the research climate (Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2021). Aubert Bonn and Pinxten (2021) also found that a circle of blame and mistrust exists between those actor groups.

Structured **mechanisms for compliance** are also key. De Jong et al. (2013) differentiates between two types of monitoring programmes, namely, compliance/auditing and quality improvement, with both having different institutional functions. With a focus on policy and administration, Adesanya (2020) provides a detailed research misconduct policy (RMP) template for higher education institutions in African countries which often do not make an RMP available on their websites. In addition, scholars highlight the importance of Committees on Publication Ethics to promote the highest standards in publication ethics (Mishra & Dabas, 2021) and the significance of editors to identify misconduct such as the misuse of confidential information (Shukla et al., 2017). Moreover, Cragoe (2019) argues that research participants from a particular community being studied should be involved in the process of ethical review and compliance through community consultation.

Multiple **pressures on researchers** that affect the quality of publications and ethical conduct have been identified by scholars, such as financial aspects. Financial **pressures** and varying conflicting financial interests play a central role due to the marketisation of publication and the resulting conflict with RE: A market and profit-oriented publication industry fosters unethical ethicists and publication

ethics (Teixeira Da Silva et al., 2019). This may be particularly the case in an emerging knowledge-based economy (Simiyu et al., 2021). Asai et al. (2016) who focus on Japan, state that there is a conflict between research ethics requirements and institutional expectations of efficiency, progress and growth. Similarly, Edwards and Roy (2017) highlight that quantitative performance metrics and funding competitions have negative implications for RI – pointing again to **institutional pressures**. Financial conflict of interests can also have significantly harmful effects including on the welfare of human research participants (Elliott, 2017). **Conflict of interests** (CoI), more broadly, is a key aspect discussed in literature: Grinnell (2014) argues that research misconduct should be framed in the context of CoI – highlighting the need to develop new approaches to manage the research environment’s structure. Teixeira Da Silva (2019) provides an overview of characteristics of personal and institutional ethics-related cronyism and nepotism in publication. At the **individual level**, assessing deontologist versus consequentialist ethical orientations, Fink et al. (2023) found that researchers with a strong consequentialist ethical orientation are more inclined toward RM – which is influenced by competitive pressures. A review of characteristics influencing academic dishonesty found that the only factor that strongly indicated if a group is at risk of cheating was the male gender (Bazoukis et al., 2020).

One emerging theme in contemporary literature is the significant **influence of the cultural context** on research practice. For instance, translating international ethical standards into locally and culturally appropriate norms and values is challenging, resulting in guidelines that are not fit for purpose – such as in the case of India in biomedicine (Satalkar & Shaw, 2015). In general, ethical solutions require flexibility and creativity due to the dynamic, multidimensional, and complex global research contexts (Reid et al., 2021). This requires considering context (Place), actors involved (People) and the values guiding ethical research (Principles) – rather than simply reviewing the current ethical, legal or methodological regulations (Precedents) (Reid et al., 2021). Scholars discuss how the cultural context shapes RE, including through country case studies (Asai et al., 2016). For instance, Bak (2018) who conducted a comparative analysis of RM in Japan, South Korea, and China states that the social and cultural context influence reasons for and the nature of RM. Moreover, ‘grey area practices’ are most likely to be influenced by local contexts (Bak, 2018). Gangbo et al. (2022) investigated informed consent and research practice in Benin and identified challenges in presenting briefing notes for informed consent to participants due to illiteracy and a lack of plain language used in the document. More insights were provided by scholars who conducted surveys of students’ attitudes to and perceptions of different forms of RM such as in Iranian higher education (Shamsoddin et al., 2021); Indian higher education (Raj et al., 2022); Nigerian higher education (Okonta & Rossouw, 2014); and the wider pan-African context (Simiyu et al., 2021).

1.3.1.4. Challenges

The most significant set of challenges pertaining to behavioural and organisational ethics identified in this review relate to **reconciling REI with institutional and professional pressures**. These include how imperatives for institutional self-preservation and reputational damage mitigation can lead to cover-ups and minimisation of the seriousness of RM that occurs at an institution (Elliott, 2017). Financial pressures to obtain research funding and pay institutional costs are another area that can incentivize RM (Asai et al., 2016; Teixeira Da Silva et al., 2019) and precipitate financial conflicts of interest (FCoIs) (Grinnell, 2014) Several authors have also suggested that the complexity of rules, regulations and policies concerning REI at the institutional level can incentivize researchers to cut corners in REI practices or commit RMs (Reid et al., 2021; Shukla et al., 2017; Sivasubramaniam et al., 2022).

Pressures on researchers to publish is another area where challenges were identified. This is partly due to institutional pressures on researchers to publish at a high volume and in high-ranking journals

to maintain their existing professional posts or progress in their careers (Houle et al., 2023; Simiyu et al., 2021). In some cases, this incentivizes researchers including postgraduate students (Trigotra et al., 2019) to publish fraudulent data (Bak, 2018; Lins & Carvalho, 2014; Mishra & Dabas, 2021), Steen et al. (2013) argued that there is a trend of lower barriers to publication of research, which is leading to an increase in retractions of published articles. Teixeira Da Silva et al. (2019) point to structural factors in the publication industry as contributing to RM including marketisation and nepotism, whilst Edwards and Roy (2017) highlight how an overreliance on publication bibliometrics as measurements of researchers' performance contributes to RM and cheating with data.

Another set of challenges relates to existing research culture(s), and how to foster change in research culture(s) (Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2021; Beever, 2021; Sivasubramaniam et al., 2022). This in part caused by **the diversity of individual ethical orientations** (Fink et al., 2023) and in the **cultural attitudes of researchers that contribute to a research culture** (Malički et al., 2019). One significant contributor to challenges in reshaping research culture(s) is a basic lack of awareness amongst researchers and research students of RE and RI principles, and what actions constitute RM, especially in Low and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs) (Adesanya, 2020; Raj et al., 2022; Rani, 2022; Shamsoddin et al., 2021). Another area of challenge that research and interventions in REI need to attend to relate to differentiating according to contextual relevance and specificities including particular disciplines or professional fields (Capaldi, 2021), or specific cultural and linguistic environments (Bak, 2018; Satalkar & Shaw, 2015), or a tendency to privilege the perceived validity of quantitative research methods at the expense of qualitative methods when evaluating RI standards and compliance (Handal et al., 2021). Janakiram and Gardens (2014) suggested that a challenge for changing research culture(s) is how to account for and **address individuals' decision-making and understandings of ethical choices**. Another challenge is learning how to engage the participation of non-academic stakeholders in REI work as a means to enable change in research culture(s), including the participation of representative bodies or individuals from the communities or population groups being researched, in order to enable ethical research practices and truly informed participation (Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2021; Cragoe, 2019). An aspect of this which requires particular care and attention is how to engage in ethical and inclusive research with marginalized populations such as indigenous groups (Gangbo et al., 2022; Cragoe, 2019), who are disadvantaged by structurally unequal power dynamics.

Several authors identify as a challenge **a lack of standardisation in REI practice**. This includes differences in monitoring due to a lack of universal guidance (De Jong et al., 2013), a lack of a shared framework for acceptable research practice (Handal et al., 2021), and universally accepted standards for what constitutes RM (Hesselmann et al., 2017). One aspect of this is a narrow focus on plagiarism to the exclusion of other forms of RM (Twist et al., 2018), such as data fabrication and falsification. Another challenge in establishing shared concepts and definitions of REI is the accuracy of the terminology used to translate them between languages, and the subtle shifts in meaning that occur when concepts and definitions are translated (Satalkar & Shaw, 2015).

3.1.5. Gaps and Limitations

The most notable area of gaps identified in this literature review relates to **a lack of standardized definitions** (Twist et al., 2018) and **structural mechanisms** for REI and managing RM (Grinnell, 2014; Okonta & Rossouw, 2014). This includes a lack of standardisation of policies and procedures between institutions (Sivasubramaniam et al., 2021). Some countries in LMICs lack policies and institutional mechanisms to tackle RM (Adesanya, 2020), including specific offices to investigate suspected misconduct and policies to deal with scientific dishonesty (Lins & Carvalho, 2014). There is also a general absence of RM policies for academic journals (Hesselmann et al., 2017; Mishra &

Dabas, 2021; Shukla et al., 2017; Simiyu et al., 2021), and a lack of international standards for REI in publications (Satalkar & Shaw, 2015).

The literature shows a **disparity between institutional and Research Funding Organisation (RFO) policies and procedures** for managing REI and researchers' working practices and requirements. Likewise, there is a gap in awareness of the occurrence of RM (Shamsoddin et al., 2021), transparent and accessible records for identified cases of RM (Houle et al., 2023), and gap in documentation and monitoring of REI interventions (Bazoukis et al., 2020; De Jong et al., 2013).

Another area of weakness in REI practice is a **lack of education and training for RE and RI**. This includes training for good publication practices (Trigotra et al., 2019) and to cultivate awareness and prevention of plagiarism (Raj et al., 2022). Education can also be developed in promoting the evaluation and ethical reasoning of bioethical dilemmas in the context of clinical medicine research and training (Janakiram & Gardens, 2014). Alongside this, Rani (2022) identifies a need for an integrative and multidisciplinary approach to ethical training in clinical medicine research and education.

Several authors indicate a **research gap in understanding of factors relating to RM** including incentives for RM (Edwards & Roy, 2017), how contextual factors (Reid et al., 2021) such as ethical climate and culture influence RM (Malički et al., 2019), and reasons for retractions in academic journals (Steen et al., 2013). In addition, there are several other gaps in understanding of how different research environments influence attitudes and behaviours regarding REI. Bak (2018, p. 121) suggests that more attention must be paid to understanding the differences between the ethics of research practices in commercial and applied research contexts versus academic research. Capaldi (2021) draws attention to a gap that exists in understanding the distinctions between the ethical practices of NGO practitioners in contrast to academic researchers. The implications of geographical distinctions are another area that would benefit from further comparative analysis (Beever, 2021), including the extent and nature of attitudes and practices relating to REI in LMICs (Gangbo et al., 2022). Finally, this review indicates that there could be better understanding of how various stakeholders influence attitudes and practices relating to REI. This includes to what extent and how stakeholders influence the formulation of institutional ethical guidance (Sivasubramaniam et al., 2022), and the roles of “non-research actors” as stakeholders, including “policy makers, funders, institution leaders, editors or publishers, research integrity office members, research integrity community members, lab technicians, researchers, research students” (Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2021, p. 2) and communities (Cragoe, 2019).

1.3.1.6. Opportunities

Contemporary literature promotes the **development, review and improvement of guidelines, policies, and relevant definitions** (Adesanya, 2020; Asai et al., 2016; De Jong et al., 2013; Gangbo et al., 2022; Houle et al., 2023; Mishra & Dabas, 2021; Reid et al., 2021; Satalkar & Shaw, 2015; Shamsoddin et al., 2021; Simiyu et al., 2021; Sivasubramaniam et al., 2022; Teixeira Da Silva et al., 2019; Twist et al., 2018). In particular, this includes RMPs for institutions to be made available on their websites (Adesanya, 2020); institutional guidelines considering enablers and barriers of RM (Sivasubramaniam et al., 2022); an ethical decision-making toolkit to guide reiterative reflection (Reid et al., 2021); a code of ethics for ethicists and publishers (Teixeira Da Silva et al., 2019); discipline-specific training material on ethics as well as nuanced metrics to measure quality of publications (Houle et al., 2023); and governmental policies and evaluation methods for research achievements (Asai et al., 2016). Additionally, scholars emphasize the importance of improving institutional communication of key guidelines, definitions and templates (such as consent forms) (Gangbo et al., 2022; Simiyu et al., 2021; Twist et al., 2018).

Multiple articles suggest **reviewing and improving the teaching of ethics** at universities with a focus on deliberation to ensure students and staff are well-equipped to conduct ethical research (Janakiram & Gardens, 2014; Malički et al., 2019; Raj et al., 2022; Rani, 2022; Sivasubramaniam et al., 2021; Trigotra et al., 2019). More specifically, Malički et al. (2019) advise to take ethical climate types into account when developing specific training programmes.

Improvements of mechanisms/governance structures, systems development and strengthening and capacity building at institutions are another clear theme emerging from literature (Adesanya, 2020; Elliott, 2017; Hesselmann et al., 2017; Houle et al., 2023; Lins & Carvalho, 2014; Okonta & Rossouw, 2014; Shukla et al., 2017; Simiyu et al., 2021; Sivasubramaniam et al., 2021; Trigotra et al., 2019). Recommendations include creating institutional mechanisms for the administration of RMPs (Adesanya, 2020), structural mechanisms for stopping FCoIs (Elliott, 2017), building accountability structures (Houle et al., 2023) and emphasizing the responsibilities of research institutions for creating an ethical climate (Okonta & Rossouw, 2014).

The literature also discusses opportunities for **compliance** (Bazoukis et al., 2020; Capaldi, 2021; De Jong et al., 2013; Elliott, 2017; Steen et al., 2013). This includes greater editorial oversight of research quality and powers to retrospectively retract articles (Steen et al., 2013), studying the correlation between RE departments and RE compliance (Bazoukis et al., 2020), and creating RE practices and systems of compliance for NGOs (Capaldi, 2021). According to De Jong et al. (2013) testing for compliance should follow a quality improvement approach.

Fostering and understanding the significance of an ethical and inclusive climate is another theme, as well as institutions' responsibilities in facilitating this (Houle et al., 2023; Malički et al., 2019; Okonta & Rossouw, 2014). Closely linked to this is the need for accountability and awareness raising (Hanganu & Ioan, 2019; Shamsoddin et al., 2021).

Scholars also recommend **looking into incentives/enablers for ethical research conduct** (Edwards & Roy, 2017; Grinnell, 2014; Sivasubramaniam et al., 2022). This includes changing incentive structures (Grinnell, 2014) and conducting further research on incentives for RM (Edwards & Roy, 2017).

Several articles identify **opportunities for the participation of non-academic stakeholders** in REI work (Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2019, 2021; Capaldi, 2021; Cragoe, 2019; Gangbo et al., 2022). Aubert Bonn and Pinxten (2019) call for conducting empirical studies to better understand the role of non-research actors. Furthermore, Aubert Bonn and Pinxten (2021) highlight their role in shaping research climate(s) and the opportunity to create spaces for inter-actor dialogue. Similarly, Cragoe (2019) highlights opportunities for community participation in shaping and RE. Gangbo et al. (2022) advocate for better engagement with marginalized populations as part of the research process.

Finally, **further research needs to be conducted** (Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2019; Bak, 2018; Bazoukis et al., 2020; Fink et al., 2023; Handal et al., 2021) in several areas. Areas of opportunity include comparative studies of researchers' experiences and perceptions of RM (Edwards & Roy, 2017), practitioners' attitudes towards ethics (Handal et al., 2021) and the role of consequentialism and competition concerning publications (Fink et al., 2023).

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1.3.2. Moral psychology related to the promotion of REI and breaches of these standards

1.3.2.1. Introduction: From attitudes to cognition, to emotions and ethical environments

This study has aimed to map moral psychology's contribution to understand the theoretical underpinnings of research misconduct and ways to remedy breaches in research integrity. An overview of these theoretical approaches is visually diagrammed in Figure 1.3.1.

Figure 1.3.1. Theoretical framework for the study of moral psychology and research ethics.

Moral psychology is the study of moral identity development, or how people integrate moral ideals with the development of their own character. Moral psychology differs from moral philosophy in that it studies how we make decisions, rather than exploring what moral decisions we should make. It encompasses the study of moral judgment, moral reasoning, moral character, and many related subjects at the intersection of philosophy and psychology (*Moral Psychology*, 2023).

The most significant findings from this section of the review are:

- Mostly studies focus on students, few on more experienced researchers at later stages of their career.
- There is global interest for this topic, with several studies from Asia, Australia & USA.
- The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) is the most used theoretical framework to address moral psychology in REI research (see Section 3.2.3 below for definition).
- TPB is limited in its focus on individuals' cognition and attitudes.
- More multimodal approaches to building ethical environments might be needed.

1.3.2.2. Methodology

The studies selected for this specific review (23) mostly employed quantitative methodological designs, predominantly online survey. Only two studies used a qualitative design in the form of interviews (Waltzer & Dahl, 2023; Waltzer et al., 2022), and one study used both surveys and interviews in a mixed-methods study design (Khathayut et al., 2022). The sample of the selected studies is mostly represented by students, although some (2) studies include employees in higher education or professionals. Students were enrolled in psychology studies (2), business (2), engineering (1), and the rest included other disciplines.

1.3.2.3. State of the art knowledge

One main theory employed is the **theory of planned behaviour (TPB)**, which posits that intention drives behaviour, with attitudes toward the behaviour and subjective norms influencing behaviour through intention, and perceived behavioural control impacting behaviour both directly and mediated through intention (Arabyat et al., 2022; Farooq & Sultana, 2022; Khathayut et al., 2022; Mirzaei-Alavijeh et al., 2021; Rajah-Kanagasabai & Roberts, 2015; Tindall et al., 2021; Waltzer et al., 2022).

TPB conceptualizes moral behaviour, and as such RE and integrity in research can be understood as an alignment of intentions, attitudes and subjective or institutional norms. Researchers have suggested to develop the theory further (*Extended TPB Models*), in the direction of including a more contextual perspective in the model (Al-Nuaimi & Uzun, 2023; Juan et al., 2022; Uzun & Kilis, 2022).

Most articles in this summary employed classic or extended TPB with additional variables, others employed social-cognitive theory, the five-traits personality model, or ethical theories. A major strength of TBP is that variables can be added to the model to increase its explanatory power (Ajzen, 1985). Rajah-Kanagasabai and Roberts (2015) added *descriptive norms and justifications* and found that the justification and intention model does mediate and explain 40% variance in engagement in RM (two-step mediation). Previous self-reporting and engagement in RM were used as proxies for engagement in further RM. Cronan (2018) expands the TPB with past behaviour and moral obligation and predicts 30% of variance. Attitude, past behaviour, and *modus operandi* were the strongest predictors. These results indicate that implementation of academic integrity (AI) education and awareness programs should occur at an earlier stage as they can influence all the factors found to be significant in the present study, and ultimately reduce AI violation behaviours so that the influence of past behaviour on college AI violations is less consequential. Other proposed measures to influence moral attitudes towards AI include intervention campaigns where role models convey messages about AI that orient it as a defining and desirable value for one's individual or group identity. These role models can also work to integrate AI as a value shared within the group identities of different student or professional organisations. Teachers and lecturers can also be involved to advise and counsel these groups and establish morally formative relationships with students (Cronan et al., 2018).

Curtis et. al. 2018 introduce **self-control** from the theory of general crime as self-control is an overlap between the two theories. Campaigns, introducing of honour codes and reducing opportunities for plagiarism (self-control is mediated by opportunity) are some of measures derived from this study. Fu & Tremayne (2021) explored the relationship between negative emotionality – which the authors define in the study as how an individual “experiences or reacts to negative emotions” in relation to stress, anxiety and depression (Fu & Tremayne, 2021, p. 2) – and positive attitudes toward plagiarism through the mediation of academic self-efficacy and self-control. They found that negative emotionality significantly predicted positive attitudes toward plagiarism over and above age and gender. Male students and younger students were more prone to plagiarize. Further they found that academic self-efficacy and self-control mediated the relationship between positive attitudes toward

plagiarism and negative emotionality. These results imply that further research on how to prevent students' positive attitudes toward plagiarism should include variables such as stress and mental health (Fu & Tremayne, 2021).

Gelfand (2016) proposes that teaching students about findings from moral psychology and **the importance of situational/organisational factors**, and how to reduce their influence, can reduce involvement in RM. Zhang et al. (2018) include in the TPB moral attitude, the subjective norm, penalties and enforcement, to indicate students' intention to cheat. They also constructed the factor of *integrity engagement* to indicate the extent to which students showed educational preparedness to behave with academic honesty (Zhang et al., 2018). Results are discussed for the Chinese context and for gender. Penalty enforcement had little significant effect.

Other researchers employed Bandura's theory of **moral disengagement (inactivity of moral self-regulation)** and **moral foundation** (works at cognitive level) and found that moral integrity played a small role, but moral disengagement was more important with 21,4% prediction value (Ampuni et al., 2020). Unauthorized collaboration, i.e. working together with peers on individual assessment tasks, was the most common form of dishonesty found among the students, implying that the tendency to commit academic dishonesty is more influenced by situational factors that result in moral disengagement, and not by more fundamental factors such as certain personality characteristics (Ampuni et al., 2020).

Uzun and Kilis (2020) incorporate *moral obligation and past behaviour* and using **ICT literacy** as a proxy for perceived behavioral control. Moral attitudes and previous behaviour are strongest predictors (more than cognitions) while literacy was not as strong (copy-paste which many students use does not require tech-savviness). Master apprenticeship is one solution. At the university level, establishing a campus moral code and increasing student awareness could prove useful in founding a moral climate, as educational institutions having honour codes face fewer incidents of plagiarism (McCabe et al., 2002; Uzun & Kilis, 2020).

Other studies explored **the relationship between personality traits and ethical ideology**. Authors created a taxonomy of four moral philosophies/characteristics: situationists, absolutists, subjectivists, and exceptionists, where individuals vary within ethical ideology, namely idealism and relativism. Due to these differences, ethical judgments and decisions can be expected from individuals according to their moral philosophy (Khan et al., 2016). For example, the study showed that individuals with greater openness to experience are low on idealism and high on relativism, whilst agreeableness was high on both the ethical ideology dimensions. Extraversion was significantly associated with a relativist ethical ideology (Khan et al., 2016). The role of negative emotions, gender, and demographics to predict RM are explored in Tindall and Curtis (2020) and Tindall et al. (2021). Gender had a weaker predictive role while negative emotion, and stress was a stronger predictor. However, studies are contradictory as to the role of emotionality, as reduced negative emotions can both lead to increased subjective norms and increased or decreased predisposition to plagiarism (mood congruence). Improving mental health, by for example, practicing mindfulness, can improve academic integrity (Tindall & Curtis, 2020).

TPB has traditionally focused on the role of attitudes, and as such individual socioemotional-cognitive factors to predict behaviour. Miron et al.'s (2021) study investigates the use of AI tutorials in higher education institutions and show inconsistencies across AI education. One implication is that use of tutorials, which was predominant, is not enough. Rather, the acculturation of students to the values associated with academic integrity must be multi-faceted and include clear, accessible policies and procedures, and should consider a developmental, relational approaches to teaching and learning (Miron et al., 2021).

Schoenherr (2015) summarizes earlier research that addresses **social-cognitive mechanisms** that can account for research misconduct, especially authorship, besides publication pressure, competition, and psychopathy (Schoenherr, 2015). Analyses of cases of misconduct have suggested *social conventions and conformity, the reciprocity norms of exchange systems, as well as role schemata and status* can explain misconduct. Measures proposed are awareness of standards, that co-authors discuss expectations and roles throughout the research process. Finally, to disincentivize dishonest behaviour stemming from a ‘publish or perish’ academic culture, we must consider adopting criterion for hiring, promotion, and funding decisions based on the quality of a restricted number of publications rather than the total number of publications produced by an individual (Schoenherr, 2015).

One of the most recent theoretical developments in this field is the contribution from Waltzer and Dahl (2023) who investigated students’ accounts of their own cheating examining a new theoretical approach to the perception, evaluations, and motivation that influence students’ decisions to cheat. Findings from testing this model suggest that perceptions, evaluations, and competing motivations influence students’ decision to cheat (Waltzer & Dahl, 2023).

While most of these studies have used student-populations in their research, Zhang, Guo & Xu (2022) explored medical researchers’ involvement in scientific misconducts using a moral psychology perspective. They used the theory about *moral licensing* which means that people who have performed unethical behaviour in the past are more prone to engage in this kind of behaviour again in the future. They found that the process of *moral licensing* plays a moderating positive role in the relationship between researchers’ creative performance and scientific misconduct (Zhang et al., 2022).

1.3.2.4. Gaps and limitations

One weakness of TPB is its lack of stress on the importance of context, i.e., situationism, in predicting RM. A few studies were explicit and emphasized the relevance of moral and ethical climate in educating students and other research professionals to reduce incidence of RI breaches (Miron et al., 2021; Uzun & Kilis, 2022). Most of the literature, except two studies (Miron et al., 2021; Schoenherr, 2015), were on student populations and little has been done on PhD students or researchers (Zhang et al., 2018). A limitation concerning most of the studies is that the data were collected using self-reporting. Research designs that involve self-reporting can be affected by a variety of biases. The informants may want to present themselves in a positive manner (socially desirable bias) or give answers they presume are correct to the questions (demand characteristics bias).

1.3.2.5. Recommendations

In practical terms, this review recommends the following: **use of teaching** on the moral and emotional aspects of RM and QRP at earlier ages (Cronan et al., 2018), **educating students about the moral psychology** of misconduct (Gelfand, 2016) and **acculturation of ethical standards** through teaching, model learning and reflection, reducing stress and improving self-control and mental health (Tindall & Curtis, 2020). Setting strong antiplagiarism norms, such as using honour codes, and seeking to enhance students’ self-control, may reduce engagement in plagiarism (Curtis et al., 2018). In addition, educators should clearly communicate what constitutes cheating and the concept of integrity in their classes and examine the reasons students think someone cheats. Furthermore, educators can assist students navigate these difficult situations by providing resources for making decisions under pressure (Waltzer & Dahl, 2023). Based on current study results, past behaviour has been the most influential factor on students’ plagiarism behaviour. Since students may engage in plagiarism in their early years at school, it is essential to minimize the effect of past plagiarism behaviour starting from their

fundamental years as students at college or at the university. One way of doing this is to make instruction in information literacy skills compulsory for students as part of their programme of study. Such explicit information literacy instruction may assist students to form ethical attitudes that actively discourage them from committing plagiarism. Especially, since students' access to digital resources cannot be restricted, students should be taught how to make informed use of digital information and sources ethically and critically (Al-Nuaimi & Uzun, 2023).

Researchers' **creative performance** has been shown to influence scientific misconduct behaviour. In relation to research environments, research managers should pay more attention to researchers' creative performance and guide them accordingly. Especially, when researchers with low moral identity have high creative performance, managers should intervene in a timely manner, strengthen communication with them, and reduce the possibility that these researchers engage in scientific misconduct behaviour (Zhang et al., 2022).

At the organisational level, tutorials might not be enough, and multimodal efforts, where direct involvement of teachers in training and adapted courses to the needs of different study groups, can have stronger impact in building moral and ethical cultures (Miron et al., 2021). Further, academic institutions should provide education workshops and training to discuss ethical conduct of scientific research, including teaching how to use anti-plagiarism tools. In addition, is it recommended to address competence in English language in countries where English is not the first language, as this is expected to reduce the incidence of plagiarism (Arabyat et al., 2022). Also, studies have found a relationship between plagiarism behaviour, negative emotions and self-control. Interventions specific to individual-level treatment and organisational level changes could be considered to reduce negative emotionality within educational and research settings. In particular, higher education providers should implement programs addressing the reduction of mental health challenges associated with negative effects, such as stress, anxiety, and depression. This could, for example, be through giving students access to counselling, stress management workshops, and educating students on coping skills aimed to reduce negative emotionality and subsequently reduce plagiarism behaviour (Tindall et al., 2021).

As most of the studies found in this field have investigated students' different levels of engagement in RM and QRP, moral psychology needs to target the population of more experienced researchers and include other relevant contextual factors derived from the evidence on causes of RM and QRPs.

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3.2.7. Additional References

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1.3.3. Opportunities and challenges in the public and private sectors (including SMEs)

1.3.3.1. Introduction

This section examines the literature on the differing implications for maintaining RE and RI standards in the private sector compared with the public sector. This includes the challenges of managing and regulating RM and QRPs in the private sector. Consideration of the role of REI in private sector research settings is significant in relation to the literature review because the majority of the discussion of research governance in this literature review focuses primarily on research practices and governance in public sector or third-sector research institutions. However, private sector research provides a significant contribution to innovation, particularly in technology and the health sciences, which have both significant short-term and long-term socio-economic implications. This includes a capacity for serious socio-economic and personal harms from products and services derived from inaccurate or maliciously false, or unethically obtained, research outcomes. A glaring and prominent recent example of this can be found in the collapse of Theranos, the US-based company whose founders defrauded investors with a claim to have invented a rapid and comprehensive blood-testing technology that only used one drop of a patient's blood, and whose claims were supported by deliberately falsified research data (Carreyrou, 2018).

1.3.3.2. Methodological approach

Since only two articles are included in the sample for this section (n=2), there is limited representation in this literature review of the potential methodological approaches available to investigate and evaluate the challenges and opportunities relating to RE and RI in the private sector (including Small to Medium Enterprises [SMEs]) relative to the public sector. This small sample size is partly due to the fact that grey literature was deliberately excluded from this review, in order to ensure rigour and parity by only including findings from peer-reviewed publications. Therefore, what is presented here should not be considered the only or best ways to research this topic, and indeed could be used to identify gaps and opportunities to apply other methodological approaches for researching REI in the private versus public sector.

Both articles in the sample use qualitative approaches to gather and analyse primary data (Glenna & Bruce, 2021; Vie, 2022). However, they differ significantly in the nature and epistemological approaches used. Glenna and Bruce (2021) used documentary analysis of legal filings to construct an in-depth case study of corporate research malfeasance. In contrast, Vie (2022) gathered data from in-depth focus groups and semi-structured interviews with social scientists in commissioned research organisations in Norway.

1.3.3.3. State-of-the-Art Knowledge

Both articles evaluate different aspects of REI as they relate to private sector research organisations. Glenna and Bruce (2021) examine the **specific incentives for RM** in private sector settings, focussing on a single case of RM committed by a major multinational corporation. Vie (2022) focusses on the **role of academic funding pressures** in incentivizing researchers to seek out and participate in privately commissioned research, rather than publicly-funded research.

1.3.3.4. Challenges

Glenna and Bruce (2021) identify as an acute challenge understanding the different goals and incentives in private versus public sector organisations, and the implications this has for scientific

practice and regulation. They suggest that unlike public scientists who face sanctions, private scientists may in fact benefit from RM. Likewise, **profit motives** sometimes incentivise private science to produce ignorance, rather than strive to create knowledge. As the divergent goals and motivations in private research can encourage RM, and private companies often face less scrutiny than public institutions, instances of RM and the potential for a wider culture of tolerance for RM and QRPs can lead to a spill-over effect of mistrust in public science too.

Vie (2022) considers the relevance of adverse implications caused by research funding pressures to concerns around REI and evaluates how pursuit of privately commissioned research funding relates to this challenge. Whilst Vie acknowledges the potential benefits of privately commissioned research, he argues that private clients can exert an undue influence on the research process. This could further exacerbate an environment in which competition for funding can affect academic quality standards and be detrimental to careful and rigorous research practices.

1.3.3.5. Gaps and Limitations

Neither of the articles analysed/paid attention to identifying or evaluating REI challenges and opportunities that relate specifically to SMEs, which is a desired knowledge area identified in the scoping of this literature review.

1.3.3.6. Opportunities

Glenna and Bruce (2021) identify an opportunity to strengthen government agencies' regulatory mechanisms to define and mitigate RM, and their powers to enforce sanctions on private sector organisations who engage in RM. In comparison, Vie (2022) emphasizes self-regulation, reflexivity and cooperation rather than the necessity of external regulation to ensure 'good behaviour' in research practice and dissemination. Vie positively identifies commissioned research as a viable pathway for researchers to escape increased funding pressures. He also points to reflective learning from previous experience in managing REI issues, and sharing this learning within the research community, as means to mitigate the negative implications of competition for REI.

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1.3.4. Personal and institutional responsibilities for the promotion of REI

1.3.4.1. Introduction

This section evaluates the literature on the linkages and divisions between personal and institutional responsibilities for the promotion of REI. This relates to questions of the roles of individual versus structural agency in ensuring the promotion and adherence to REI standards and where responsibility lies in both how RM and QRPs are perpetrated, exposed, and acted upon. Problematizing RM and RQPs in this way relates to the premise of the BEYOND project as a whole, which is predicated on Redman's (2013) exhortation to move beyond the 'bad-apple approach' in managing RM. This entails evaluating individual researchers' misconduct in relation to the psychosocial and environmental context in which it occurs, including institutional cultures and work-related pressures in academic and clinical research.

1.3.4.2. Methodological Approaches

The topic of personal and institutional responsibilities is comparatively well-represented in the literature (n=26) relative to some other topics in this systematic review. The review of this topic also demonstrates that a diverse range of methodologies are applied to evaluate this topic. This includes both qualitative (n=18), quantitative (n=4) and mixed (n=4) analysis, and the analysis of both primary (n=19) and secondary (n=7) data.

The most prevalent approach overall was primary documentary analysis mostly in the form of analysing policies and codes of conducts governing REI based on qualitative methods (Gokcay & Arda, 2017; S. A. Page & Stalker, 2019; Valkenburg et al., 2020; Ward & Strong, 2016; Yi et al., 2019), or using mixed methods (Hastings et al., 2022). Two articles were in-depth case studies of RM (Golden et al., 2023; Kahr & Hollingsworth, 2019) and another study (Jacobs, 2021) providing a historical genealogy of the development of ethical reviews in the Netherlands. Other studies conducted surveys of researchers and research ethics practitioners, which were evaluated based on qualitative (Titus, 2014; Titus & Ballou, 2014), quantitative (Huybers et al., 2020) and mixed data analysis (Labib et al., 2021; Vie, 2020). Other qualitative approaches used include several studies using interviews and/or focus groups with researchers and REI practitioners (Deniau, 2023; Evans et al., 2022; Urbanovič & Tauginienė, 2013), and the use of a participatory design workshop to develop institutional guidelines for supporting REI leadership (Pizzolato et al., 2022).

One study applied quantitative methods to evaluate publication records for the prevalence of self-correction in open access journals (Gasparyan et al., 2014), whilst Horvat et al. (2016) analysed the statistical relationship between journal impact factors in a specific field and the inclusion of REI in those journals' instructions to authors submitting papers. DuBois et al. (2013) conducted a statistical analysis of RM case study records to identify and comparatively evaluate the most prevalent reasons for why RM occurs.

Four of the articles provided secondary reviews of the literature to assess concepts of culture and practice in REI discourse (Valkenburg et al., 2021), positive and negative factors impacting the promotion and implementation of REI (Roje et al., 2022), to evaluate the quality of interventions aimed at preventing REI (Marusic et al., 2016), and to gather researchers' experiences of teaching about REI to students (Shephard et al., 2015). Bouter and Hendrix (2017) reviewed the literature in a non-systematic way to evaluate the implications of whistleblowing on both whistle-blowers and the scientists they accuse.

1.3.4.3. State-of-the-Art Knowledge

A number of articles reviewed explicitly evaluate the institutional and individual incentives that contribute to and against RM. Pressures for grants, publications and tenure incentivise researchers to commit RM (DuBois et al., 2013), and institutions will work to minimize or cover-up RM due to economic considerations of potentially losing funding opportunities or incurring reputational damage (Golden et al., 2023). These concerns correlate with Jacobs' (2021) conclusion that financial sanctions related to funding for misconduct are an effective tactic to incentivise RE compliance.

Specific issues pertaining to the promotion of REI and the management of RM at the institutional level include **institutional and financial conflicts of interest (FCoIs/CoIs)** (Kahr & Hollingsworth, 2019; Ward & Strong, 2016), and the effective management of whistle-blowers' complaints and their well-being by organisations (Bouter & Hendrix, 2017; Titus, 2014; Vie, 2020). Deniau (2023) highlights the professional roles of practitioners, such as institutional research integrity officers (RIOs), in having a positive impact in promoting RI within an organisation. Other authors highlight the benefits of educational programmes to promote REI, but point out that such programmes are often piecemeal, and that a lack of consistency in both pedagogy and the quality of reporting and evaluation hinder the impact of these efforts (Evans et al., 2022; Marusic et al., 2016; Roje et al., 2022; Shephard et al., 2015).

Significant findings from the articles that evaluated institutional and governmental REI policies and guidelines suggest that **existing REI policies and frameworks are insufficiently precise**, and fail to adequately consider that many REI issues or situations lack a clear set of rules that can be applied universally, and often require deliberation and judgement (Shephard et al., 2015). Cross-national comparative studies of policy guidance highlight a lack of consistency between different countries in the extent and structure of institutional RI governance and oversight (Evans et al., 2022), including auditing regimes, and inconsistencies resulting from the discretionary powers of institutions within a given country (S. A. Page & Stalker, 2019; Yi et al., 2019). Across disciplinary institutions, Hastings et al. (2022) found that 78% of European learned societies did not provide RI guidance to their members. Likewise, Horvat et al. (2016) point to inconsistencies in journals' publication instructions for authors (IFAs), and a tendency to place far greater emphasis in IFAs on RE and manuscript preparation than on RI and editorial policies including authors' rights of appeal and the journal's approach to managing scientific misconduct.

Several articles attended to the **roles of norms and research cultures** in promoting REI. Urbanović and Tauginienė (2013) define the culture of institutional responsibility as a formation of the societal values brought to an institution by individuals, and posit that institutional values derive from the individuals within a research community. This can be dependent on national and regional geographical factors (Yi et al., 2019), and some locations place a greater onus of responsibility on individual researchers to be aware of what acceptable research practices are, and to self-regulate their conduct (Gokcay & Arda, 2017).

Huybers et al. (2020) evaluates the implications of the Singapore Statement on Research Integrity as an attempt to create global RI norms. In doing so, they identify that different priorities in managing RI tend to correlate to researchers' academic backgrounds, and that the effectiveness of RI enablers can vary depending on diverse factors such as hierarchical position in academia, tenure, and country of employment. Valkenburg et al. (2020, 2021) suggest that conceptual fields of culture and practice in RI can bridge the gap between individuals and institutions, but to prevent ambiguity it is necessary to clarify the specific contexts of practice and content of research cultures, rather than rely on practice and culture as abstract notions. Gasparyan et al. (2014) argue that there has been an increasing trend in post-publication corrections, indicating an increased engagement from readers in spotting

publication errors and unethical practices in publications, and advocating for their rectification. They suggest that different countries' diverse research environments and publishing activity influence the extent of erroneous, duplicate, and unethical publishing.

1.3.4.4. Challenges

The most significant challenge identified in this review is a lack of clarity and consistency in REI policy, guidance, and education at different levels. Multiple authors argued that a lack of clarity exists in institutional policies and guidance to make norms and practices explicit (Titus & Ballou, 2014; Valkenburg et al., 2021), and that there is a lack of consistency between individual institutions and within cross-institutional networks of researchers such as funding bodies, journals (Horvat et al., 2016) and learned societies (Hastings et al., 2022). This includes better defining the roles and remit of RIOs (Deniau, 2023) within an institution. Another area for improving clarification in the research governance arena is to articulate the distribution of roles and responsibilities between research performing organisations (RPOs) and research funding organisations (RFOs), and making these stakeholders mutually accountable to each other (Labib et al., 2021). At the international level, more work must be done to negotiate and establish international agreements in REI standards, such as building upon the groundwork established by the Singapore Statement on Research Integrity (Gasparyan et al., 2014; Huybers et al., 2020).

Another pressing set of challenges relates to institutional pressures, and the implications these have for trust and transparency (DuBois et al., 2013; Golden et al., 2023; Jacobs, 2021). An acute factor contributing to institutional pressure is the need for institutions to find revenue from research funding in a socio-political context characterized by the neoliberalisation of the higher education sector and the increasing commercialisation of scientific research (Urbanovič & Tauginienė, 2013). This leads to an increased potential for financial and professional conflicts of interest (CoIs) by institutional stakeholders (Kahr & Hollingsworth, 2019; Ward & Strong, 2016), which risks eroding trust in RPOs from both the public and within scientific communities. This challenge can be mitigated by implementing robust policy interventions to manage CoIs and to ensure the transparent governance of research (S. A. Page & Stalker, 2019). Another challenge pertaining to institutional (mis)trust is the role of whistle-blowers in handling and preventing REI and how whistle-blower concerns are managed by institutions. Golden et al. (2023) argue that institutional self-preservation and damage limitation can motivate institutions to coverup incidents of RM. This can undermine confidence that an institution will act upon whistle-blower complaints fairly and justly, and that faculty members who whistle blow will be adequately protected from retaliation or damage to their reputations or careers (Titus, 2014; Vie, 2020). However, Bouter and Hendrix (2017) argue conversely that whistleblowing can be weaponized for malicious reasons, and highlight that incorrect or deliberately false whistleblowing claims can be damaging to the research careers of both the accused scientist and the whistle-blower. To prevent such harm, Bouter and Hendrix recommend that a clearer distinction should be made between good- and bad-faith whistleblowing and that anonymous whistleblowing should be discouraged, an approach that may be considered controversial and difficult to implement.

1.3.4.5. Gaps and Limitations

Several themes emerged that show gaps in the knowledge of how individual and institutional factors co-create REI. One is a lack of transparent reporting on cases of RM (Marusic et al., 2016; Vie, 2020). This is in part due to a dearth of established reporting mechanisms for discovering and monitoring RM incidents, which in turn hinders both the prevention of RM and research on patterns and causes of RM and QRPs (Bouter & Hendrix, 2017; DuBois et al., 2013). Compounding this is a lack of research and

evaluation of attitudes to REI (Huybers et al., 2020), including across disciplines (Hastings et al., 2022; Horvat et al., 2016), and across distinct research career stages, from the PhD level (Titus & Ballou, 2014) to professional career researchers (Marusic et al., 2016).

There is also a variability and a lack of shared accepted definitions for key concepts in REI including these very terms and what counts as RM or a QRP (Titus, 2014). Furthermore, there is a need for more clearly defined and standardized practice and methodologies for evaluation of REI education (Roje et al., 2022), as current educational interventions are complex, inadequately described, hard to reproduce and are highly dependent on contextual factors (Marusic et al., 2016). Compounding this is a need to generate more contextually-grounded guidance for researchers on REI, as opposed to generalized and abstract guidance (Valkenburg et al., 2021).

1.3.4.6. Opportunities

Opportunities to improve REI interventions identified in this review fall into three broad categories: **education, capacity-building, and policy improvement and integration**. Several authors recommend redesigning REI education to make it less based on compliance with abstract principles, and more based on epistemologies that privilege reflexivity, contextualisation and sense-making through pedagogical techniques such as case study evaluation and role-play (DuBois et al., 2013; Evans et al., 2022; Huybers et al., 2020; Roje et al., 2022; Shephard et al., 2015). Another aspect of education addressed in the literature is to whom REI educational interventions are targeted. One area of opportunity is to target REI education, not just towards students but also towards career researchers, teaching faculty and senior researchers in particular to encourage a more top-down and systemic change to attitudes to REI in research cultures (Evans et al., 2022; Titus & Ballou, 2014).

Alongside education, there is a need to develop capacity-building to promote REI. This includes training and supporting leadership in REI best practice from senior researchers and mentors (Pizzolato et al., 2022; Shephard et al., 2015; Titus & Ballou, 2014). Another area of opportunity for targeted capacity-building is in the professional roles of REI practitioners including institutional RIOs (Deniau, 2023) and journal editors (Gasparyan et al., 2014) to enable more robust monitoring and decision-making.

Finally, this review's findings suggest that improving and integrating policies at RPO, RFO, national and regional levels can also be effective approaches to encouraging greater awareness and adherence to high standards of REI in research practice. One way of doing this is to clarify existing policies and work towards shared policy standards across institutions (Horvat et al., 2016; Shephard et al., 2015). Another is to improve reporting mechanisms for REI (S. A. Page & Stalker, 2019; Ward & Strong, 2016), including improving and clarifying institutional whistle-blower policies (Bouter & Hendrix, 2017; Kahr & Hollingsworth, 2019; Ward & Strong, 2016). A regulation-led approach to enhancing policy is to strengthen and enforce sanction mechanisms for RM (Golden et al., 2023; Jacobs, 2021), including denying access to funding for researchers who commit RM. To achieve this, as well as other policy outcomes, it is necessary to better integrate policy approaches across RPOs, RFOs and central governance institutions such as national governments and the European Council (Evans et al., 2022), alongside policy strategies to build trust in institutions and researchers' expertise (Titus, 2014). One example of this is RFOs linking research funding for RPOs to the provision of an approved programme of REI education (Gokcay & Arda, 2017). An alternative approach suggested by some authors, however, is to engage stakeholders in co-designing policy (Labib et al., 2021) to create a relevant and consensus-based REI policy regime that accounts for the needs of the researchers and other groups affected by REI concerns.

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1.3.5. Questions related to the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers

1.3.5.1. Introduction

This section examines the literature on the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers who have committed RM or QRPs. This area of the literature review has an acute relevance to the overall aims of the BEYOND project. This is because BEYOND challenges the ‘bad apple’ notion of research misconduct, whereby RM or QRPs are committed by individual researchers deviating from the norms established by the academic research community who must be subsequently punished and ostracized for their transgressions to prevent the spread of malign research practices and reporting (Redman, 2013). However, BEYOND intends to critique this notion by illustrating how individual and ethical socio-economic factors, ethics and moral psychology are factors that both influence decision-making around REI and can be mobilized to promote better REI policies, education, and practices, as well as mitigate the proliferation of RM and QRPs. Part of this remit includes considering more carefully the reasons why RM occurs and offering pathways to reduce harms from RM and QRPs, including finding new and more integrative ways to rehabilitate and reintegrate researchers who have committed such actions.

1.3.5.2. Methodological Approaches

Since only two articles are included in the sample for this section (n=2), there is limited representation in this literature review of the potential methodological approaches available to investigate and evaluate questions related to the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers who have engaged in RM or QRPs.

Both studies represented in this sample use quantitative methodologies to measure the post-misconduct research activities of researchers believed to have committed RM. Galbraith (Galbraith, 2017) conducted a case study review from the records of US Office of Research Integrity (ORI) to identify a pool of researchers who were found to commit RM and subsequently undertook mandated corrective actions. The author then searched public research databases and online sources for evidence of these individuals’ research activities following corrective action and calculated their continued involvement in research according to suggestive indicators.

Mistry et. al. (Mistry et al., 2019) took a somewhat similar but more specific methodological approach. The authors correlated that researchers with multiple publication retractions are very likely to have committed RM or QRPs, and identified 100 authors with multiple retractions from the *Retraction Watch* database (Kincaid, 2023). The study authors then conducted literature searches of the retracted authors’ subsequent work to comparatively measure their pre-retraction and post-retraction publication rates to evaluate the retracted authors’ continued involvement in research after committing RM and/or QRPs.

1.3.5.3. State-of-the-Art Knowledge

In terms of state-of-the-art knowledge, both papers evaluate the extent of research activities carried out after a researcher was found to have committed RM. It should be noted though that Mistry et. al. (2019) paid close attention to researchers who had participated in some form of remediation for RM or QRPs. However, the two articles come to somewhat contradictory conclusions in their analysis of the results they obtained. Galbraith (2017) argues that research misconduct is not a career-ending event since indicators of post-misconduct research were found for nearly half of all researchers who were found guilty of misconduct by the ORI, and overall these researchers continued to bring in substantial

amounts of research funding. He also found that the likelihood of engaging in post-misconduct research increases for more senior academics who are already in a senior position prior to the misconduct than for early career researchers.

In contrast, Mistry et. al. (2019) found that the publication rates of authors with multiple retractions, most of whom were associated with RM, declined rapidly after their first retraction although a small minority continued to publish regularly.

1.3.5.4. Challenges

Challenges identified by Galbraith (2019) emphasize variability in the quality and reproducibility of interventions designed to rehabilitate and reintegrate researchers who have committed misconduct. He also points to a lack of transparency in RM reporting and monitoring, which echoes the findings of multiple authors surveyed elsewhere in this literature review (e.g. De Jong, 2013; DuBois, 2013; Bouter & Hendrix, 2017; Bazoukis, 2020). However, Mistry et. al. (2017) identify a starker challenge that researchers who are found to have, or are perceived to have, committed RM, tend to leave research careers after these incidents and it is difficult to retain them.

1.3.5.5. Gaps and Limitations

Mistry et. al. (2017) identify, as a gap, an overall **lack of attempt being made to rehabilitate researchers** who have committed RM. They also note a lack of distinction in their study of the types of misconduct committed and how different categories of RM affect outcomes. Furthermore, their study identified a gap in assessing the quality or sustainability of the post-misconduct careers of those scientists that did remain in research careers post-misconduct. This contrasts with Galbraith's (2017) findings discussed earlier in this section.

Galbraith (2019) suggests that in-depth qualitative interviews with researchers who have been found to commit RM would be valuable to obtain a more detailed and nuanced understanding of the impacts of RM on researchers' careers. Galbraith also points to a knowledge gap in how research collaborators of a senior researcher who has committed RM, as well as PhD students and post-doctoral researchers under their supervision, are affected by their actions. This includes whether there is stigma attached to those researchers by association, despite their not having committed RM or QRPs themselves.

1.3.5.6. Opportunities and recommendations

Galbraith (2019) argues for **the development of strategies to assist in the reintegration and rehabilitation of researchers** who have committed RM to prevent re-offending and mitigate the consequences of their previous unethical actions for the research community. In particular, he identifies the potential to improve the pedagogy of responsible conduct of research (RCR) training to increase its scope and efficacy. This includes moving beyond fear-based or self-interest-based approaches to a values-based approach that emphasizes “the inherently collaborative and social nature of the research enterprise in RCR training programs, framing misconduct as a direct violation of ethical values that make research possible, such as honesty, transparency, and healthy skepticism” (Galbraith 2019, p. 31).

Mistry et. al (2017) also advance that there is space to create opportunities to rehabilitate and reintegrate researchers who have committed RM through corrective educational programmes so that they are able to continue research work, and their publications are not tainted by concerns regarding the integrity of the authors' research. This is particularly acute and necessary in cases of “serial

fraudsters” who have committed multiple instances of data fabrication, along with an evaluation of the effectiveness of such programmes (Mistry et al., 2019, p. 287).

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1.3.6. Researchers' mental health and well-being in relation to research misconduct (including those employed in uncertain work conditions)

1.3.6.1. Introduction

Investigating the relationship between researchers' mental health & well-being and RM might be important. It might provide information about the possibility of engaging in RM and QRPs due to the high levels of stress in academia. However, it seems that research on the topic of researchers' mental health & well-being is still in the early stages with limited literature published so far (Nicholls et al., 2022). However, a study by Levecque et al. (2017) made clear that the mental health of early-career scientists most likely is negatively affected by workload, conflicting demands between work and family obligations, and lack of decision-making opportunities, which can be linked to working in academia. The aim of this part of the literature review was to explore literature for explanatory factors which can be associated with researchers' mental health and wellbeing and the occurrence of RM and QRPs (see Figure 1.3.2).

Figure 1.3.2. Relationship between researchers' stress levels, mental health problems and RM and QRPs

1.3.6.2. The state-of-the-art

In a qualitative interview study, Vidak et al. (2023) explored how employees and students perceived **organisational climate** and its consequences in the university setting. They focused on ethical climate, which can be linked with several work-related outcomes. In their study, participants were asked if they heard about, or had experience with any type of RM. One participant reported authorship issues, while other participants stressed the prevalence of plagiarism. The results stressed the importance of organisational climate in perpetuating RM and QRPs. Interventions which foster organisational climate could reduce the incidence of RM and QRPs. The relationship between researchers' mental health, well-being and RM was not explored in this study.

Interviewees in Aubert Bonn & Pinxtens' study (2021) described that the pressure to perform, and especially to deliver, and the academic culture of publish or perish as significant issues when asked about which problems affect the culture of science and threaten integrity. Expectations that researchers should devote themselves to science were said to impact the well-being and satisfaction of researchers. Adequate support for researchers, including through an attentive consideration of their well-being and struggles, should be an immediate priority within research institutions (Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2021).

Nicholls et al. (2022) conducted a systematic review and qualitative meta-synthesis to understand how researchers experience working in academia and the effects these experiences have on their mental health and well-being. In their study, the relationship with RM and QRPs was not investigated. Nevertheless, it is an interesting article because it identified seven key themes about researchers' experiences of working in academia and the effect these experiences have on their mental health and well-being. The seven key themes mentioned are insecurity and career prospects; a demanding career path; work-life balance and the academic lifestyle: an incompatibility; the influence of relationships and role models; the impact of working in academia on health; coping and support; positions of privilege (Nicholls et al., 2022). They concluded that "the high expectations set by the academic system, continued job insecurity and incidents of bias and discrimination have left researchers experiencing, or at risk of experiencing, physical and mental health difficulties" (Nicholls et al., 2022, p.25).

In a cross-sectional study using a web-based anonymized questionnaire, Gopalakrishna et al. (2022) focused on RM and QRPs and postulated some possible explanatory factors for RM and QRPs. Their results showed that post-doctoral researchers and assistant professors rated publication pressure, funding pressure and competitiveness higher than other academic factors, but ranked peer norms and organisational justice as lower-level factors. Arts and humanities scholars reported the highest work and publication pressures, the most competition and the lowest in mentoring, peer norms and organisational justice compared to other disciplinary fields. They also suggested that PhD candidates and junior researchers engaged more often in QRPs than other academic ranks, as did males, and those doing empirical research as opposed to those doing non-empirical research. Work pressure and competitiveness were only marginally correlated with a higher likelihood of committing QRPs, whilst mentoring was only weakly associated with a reduction in likelihood of committing QRPs.

Conesa Carpintero & González Ramos (2018) conducted an interview study containing 36 interviews from five different research and academic institutions in Spain and a literature review addressing: (a) the influence of acceleration and audit culture on the well-being and practices of researchers; (b) the impact of **uncertainty and precarious working conditions** on researchers; and (c) **gender inequality** in academia with a specific focus on time regimes. Their aim was to explore the **psychosocial risks** experienced by women and men academics emerging from accelerated time regimes and precariousness from a gender perspective. For this part of our literature review, the impact of uncertainty and precarious working conditions is of relevance. Their results showed that work organisation and expectations in academia follow a time pattern that entails total availability related to high demands and research productivity. Academics interviewed devote more hours to work than they established in their labour contracts. They have to work in a "high-pressure environment, abuse in power relations and lack tools and support (...), eventually led to feelings of isolation and anxiety that produced a lack of selfcare and emotional dependence on giving results to their boss (...)" (Conesa Carpintero & González Ramos, 2018, p. 6). Conesa Carpintero & González Ramos (2018) emphasize a care ethics perspective that acknowledges how both family and care time are traditionally undervalued, as is unpaid work time.

1.3.6.3. What are challenges / trends / opportunities?

This literature review showed several challenges and opportunities for further research. Still, a lot is unknown about the relationship between high-stress levels in academia, mental health problems and the frequency of RM and QRPs; limited literature is published so far.

Where data from Gopalakrishna et al. (2022) showed that work pressure and competitiveness were only marginally associated with higher QRP, data from Vidak et al. (2023) and Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, (2021) showed that fostering greater integrity and responsibility in an RPO's organisational climate could reduce the incidence of RM and QRPs. A clear trend is that “the high expectations set by the academic system, the continued job insecurity and incidents of bias and discrimination have left researchers experiencing, or at risk of experiencing, physical and mental health difficulties” (Nicholls et al., 2022, p.25).

1.3.6.4. What potential research gaps are there?

First, to our knowledge and based on this research, no research has been done on the impact of stress in the work environment causing mental health problems or impact on researchers' well-being, on the occurrence of RM or QRP. Is it possible that stress, manifesting itself in mental health problems, leads to/aggravates RM and QRPs? Second, in the reviewed literature the most important thoughts given for further research regarding researchers' mental health and well-being are the following:

- more research on the ethics of care perspective, to be applied in the academic context (Conesa Carpintero & González Ramos, 2018);
- developing interventions using virtue-based education to improve institutional climate (Vidak et al., 2023);
- high-quality qualitative research to better understand how systematic change, including tackling inequality, can be brought about more immediately and effectively from a researcher's perspective;
- understanding the experiences and support needs of post-doctoral and more senior researchers.

1.3.6.5. Bibliography

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1.3.7. Gender dimensions and power relations in the context of research misconduct

1.3.7.1. Introduction

The objective of this literature review was to identify the causes and consequences of RM and QRPs in terms of gender dimensions, power relations and conditions of employment. This might provide some overview of insights into this topic, and the possible weak position of certain academics who may therefore be particularly susceptible to allowing RM to occur. Gibson et al. (2014) used the definition of Dahl (1957) concerning power: “the ability to compel others to do what you want them to do” (p. 311) and the distinct types of power that operate in the workplace from French & Raven (1959). French & Raven (1959) identified five bases of power: coercive, reward, legitimate, referent, and expert. They state that “coercive power is the use of force (implied or otherwise) to achieve compliance. Reward power is associated with the ability to give somebody something they want. Legitimate power often comes from a role or position with authority over others. Referent power is often used by role models or people who are respected. Finally, expert power comes from having large amounts of knowledge or expertise” (in: Gibson et al. 2015, p. 312).

It is known that gender differences in academics exist. Conesa Carpintero & González Ramos (2018) conducted an interview study to explore the psychosocial risks experienced by women and men academics emerging from accelerated time regimes and precariousness from a gender perspective. Their findings highlighted discriminatory practices toward women academics, which create psychological harm and feelings of being unwelcome and risking their career progression. They suggest that good working conditions should be guaranteed to prevent power abuses driven by an obsession with productivity. To survive in academia, young researchers should be offered space and security to fulfil responsibilities such as building a family, buying a house, caring for ageing parents, and ensuring honesty and openness. They recommend a more detailed focus on structural and institutional changes in the academic context from an ethics of care perspective (Conesa Carpintero & González Ramos, 2018).

1.3.7.2. What is the state-of-the-art?

Gender

The reviewed literature showed that gender, being male or female (studies on transgender people on this topic were not found), in relation to scientific misconduct has been examined in different ways. Some studies focused on gender differences to predict the occurrence of scientific misconduct (Fanelli et al, 2015), others on gender differences in attitude towards research integrity (Mol & van den Hoven, 2022) and finally, on gender differences in reporting scientific misconduct (Horbach et al., 2022; Mol & van den Hoven, 2022).

Fanelli et al. (2015) used a retrospective study design to verify whether risk factors for scientific misconduct could predict the occurrence of retractions of research papers, which is usually the consequence of research misconduct and is often used to predict risk factors for scientific misconduct. One of the possible risk factors was being male. However, Fanelli et al. (2015) concluded that the hypothesis that males are prone to scientific misconduct was not supported.

Horbach et al. (2020) studied the reporting process of employees of eight European universities based on a multinational survey. They examined actors’ rationales for reporting and not reporting misconduct, how they report it and the perceived consequences of reporting. They concluded that

gender did not seem to be distinctively related to researchers reporting of misconduct or to the outcomes of their reporting.

The aim of Mol & van den Hovens' (2022) study was to generate more encompassing and detailed insight into the role of gender in RI. Their data showed **no significant differences between male and female students in attitude towards RI** and no significant differences between male and female students in suspecting and reporting others. However, they found that male students were significantly more likely to report neglecting to do their part of the work in a group project, and putting their names on the work without checking it, than female students. They suspect that gender differences may vary depending on the **type of misconduct** focused on, rather than females showing higher integrity in general.

Seniority/Power relations

Gibson et al. (2014) conducted an interview study and interviewed a diverse set of academics about hypothetical ethical problems that involve power differences among those involved. Gibson et al. (2014) found that participants were able to recognize that **power differentials** can result in power abuses in ethical situations. Participants expressed internal tension regarding how to handle these problems. From the perspectives of those in positions of less power, three themes emerged from the data. The first common theme was to defer to existing channels to deal with abuse and violations of policy. The underlying thinking across this theme was to remove oneself from the situation as quickly as possible, often passing responsibility to people in positions to deal with the situation. The second theme was to, as a subordinate, submit to authority. This method for dealing with ethical dilemmas involving power differentials is basically related to keeping one's head down if one receives pressure to do something unethical. This was also found by Izadinia (2014) in her interview study in which eight students told that when they received unethical treatment from their supervisors, they usually preferred to tolerate it. In a qualitative interview and focus group study of Aubert Bonn & Pinxten (2021), was also found that PhD students are afraid to disagree with a supervisor's inadequate practices (the example of gift authorship was used) because "they were worried that the supervisor would 'make it hard' on them and might not allow them to graduate"(p.13). This suggests that some individuals are consciously aware of the fact that they will submit to performing unethical behaviours if it protects their self-interests. The third theme from Gibson et al. (2014) was that of resisting power and standing one's ground. A researcher taking this perspective believes that they would actively stand up against another researcher if they recognized that person was abusing their power.

The use of power seems to play a role in the prevalence of RM amongst young researchers. Factors relating to power dynamics that can lead to RM are illustrated in Figure 1.3.3. Fanelli et al. (2015) concluded that scientific misconduct is more likely to occur in the earliest phase of a researcher's career. Horbach et al. (2020) results showed that junior researchers did not report misconduct due to their fear of negative consequences, such as losing future opportunities or hampering their social relations at work, the distrust of the management's willingness to take any corrective action, and the belief that reporting would not lead to any changes, notably due to certain individuals being protected. These responses showed "how seniority, hierarchy and power issues affected respondents' decision not to report an alleged case" (p. 1604) and that seniority may actually be one of the causes of misconduct.

Hall & Martin (2019) developed a taxonomy that differentiates various forms of research behaviour, ranging from appropriate practice to blatant misconduct to provide clearer guidelines for especially young researchers. This might give young researchers clarity regarding the boundary between what is acceptable and what is not, especially when they are confronted with pressures to increase their output.

Figure 1.3.3. Ethical situations in which power abuses lead to a higher prevalence of RM

Conditions of employment

The shifting organisational conditions and complexity within higher education have created new pressures to cut corners, and the occurrence of RM and QRPs may have increased as a result. Factors that can cause RM and QRPs identified in this literature review are:

- increased workload (Chapman & Lindner, 2016; Kennedy et al., 2023);
- a lack of public funding causing erosion in salaries (Chapman & Lindner, 2016);
- the pressure to conduct research (Chapman & Lindner, 2016);
- the pressure to publish in high-impact factor journals (Chapman & Lindner, 2016);
- excessive competition (Chapman & Linder, 2016; Kennedy et al., 2023);
- injustice in working environments (Chapman & Linder, 2016);
- concentration of power with insufficient checks and balances (Chapman & Lindner, 2016; Parlangeli et al., 2020);
- short-term employment contracts (Kennedy et al., 2023; Horbach et al, 2020; Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2021).

3.7.3. What are challenges/trends/opportunities?

This literature review showed that there are probably no significant differences between male and female academics in attitudes towards RI and no significant differences between male and female academics in suspecting and reporting cases (Horbach et al., 2022; Mol & van den Hoven, 2022; Fanelli et al., 2015). However, gender differences might be visible depending on the type of misconduct (Mol & van den Hoven, 2022).

Within higher education, power abuse seems to play a role in the prevalence of RM and QRPs among young researchers. They are afraid to disagree with a supervisor and seem to tolerate unethical behaviours, especially when it protects their self-interests (Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2021; Horbach et al., 2020; Fanelli et al., 2015; Gibson et al., 2014; Izadinia, 2014).

This can also be connected to the finding that temporary employment contracts appear to influence the report of incidences and occurrence of RM and QRPs (Kennedy et al., 2023; Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2021; Horbach et al. 2020). The lack of employment security could risk compromising the honesty and openness of young researchers (Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2021). They might fear losing their employment if they disagree with a supervisor.

Kennedy et al. (2023) suppose that cases of RM and QRPs should indicate that a ‘slow science’ approach may be the keystone to a better research system. Slow science is a focus on quality over quantity and speed in research.

Care and consideration should be given to researchers themselves, especially young researchers. This forgotten need for care easily links back to the lack of support faced by young researchers, the precariousness of research careers, and the lack of support for meeting integrity requirements, while it also explains the dominant intolerance for failure and mistakes (Aubert Bonn & Pinxten, 2021).

1.3.7.4. What potential research gaps are there?

In the reviewed literature the most important thoughts given for further research regarding gender dimensions and power relations in the context of research misconduct were:

- exploration of how new technologies are utilized to engage in, detect or pre-empt misconduct (Hall & Martin, 2019);
- clarification of the sometimes ambiguous boundaries between appropriate and inappropriate research conduct and improve awareness (Hall & Martin, 2019);
- a need for improved reporting procedures. Specifically, junior researchers and people with temporary work appointments should be considered in RM reporting policies. This requires procedures that effectively address issues of power imbalance and the fear of not being taken seriously (Horbach et al., 2020);
- understanding what type of thinking regarding power could be more effective in coming to good ethical decisions, and efforts should be made to more explicitly understand how the different bases of power influence ethical decision-making (Gibson et al., 2024);
- more detailed understanding of the connection between gender and integrity, because gender differences may vary depending on the type of misconduct focused (Mol & van den Hoven, 2022).

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1.3.8. Research on the effectiveness of research ethics and integrity training

1.3.8.1. Introduction

In the recent decades, REI (research ethics and integrity) education has gained increasing attention due to various questionable research practices and the efforts to uphold the quality of research (Kalichman, 2013; Katsarov et al., 2021). There is a plethora of training courses and formats, and research is emerging on the effectiveness of the programmes (Watts et al., 2017; Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018; Katsarov et al., 2021; Antes, 2014). Measuring the effectiveness of REI training is problematic as there seems to be no consensus of what constitutes of ‘effective’ in REI and it is difficult to find a feasible measure for this context (Steele et al., 2016; Turner et al., 2018). It has been pointed out (Watts et al., 2017) that it is difficult to measure the effectiveness of REI training as the aims of interventions as well as measurement means vary, so it is difficult to compare different formats of training. Often the evaluation is based on participant reactions to the training, but also the improvement of knowledge and skills can be measured (as pre- and post-tests) (Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018). Occasionally, changes in attitudes, behaviour and motivation follow the trainings; or reduced cases of misconduct and data about improvements in the research community can be measured (Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018). Generally, the analysis of effectiveness of REI training can predict the impact on the trainees, but there is rarely proof of the changes in the actual behaviour (Watts et al., 2017).

1.3.8.2. Review results

Research methods

In total, 31 papers were included in the analysis. This includes 17 review papers and 14 individual articles describing training formats and measures. Secondary articles (reviews) mostly displayed results of quantitative methods (8) (Marusic, 2016; Mulhearn et al., 2017; Medeiros et al., 2017; Watts et al., 2017a, 2017b; Todd et al., 2017; Turner et al., 2018; Katsarov et al., 2022), but also qualitative methods (7) were utilized (Antes, 2014; Maesschalck et al., 2015; Mumford et al., 2015; Todd et al., 2017; Torrence et al., 2017; Watts et al., 2017c; Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018), mixed methods not so common (2) (Steele et al., 2017; Kresimann et al., 2021).

Primary articles used mostly qualitative research methods (8) (Löfström, 2016; Tammeleht et al., 2019; 2020; 2022a; 2022b; Lowe et al., 2018; McIntosh et al., 2018; Dawson et al., 2019); quantitative (4) (Chertok et al., 2013; MacCormack & Garvan, 2014; Vynicker et al., 2015; Zollitsch et al., 2021) and mixed methods (2) (Wada et al., 2013; Buedo et al., 2023) were also used.

Fields

Four individual articles had a context in the health sciences (Chertok et al., 2013; MacCormack & Garvan, 2014; Vynicker et al., 2015; Buedo et al., 2023), 1 in psychiatry (Wada et al., 2013) and 2 reviews from the business context (Medeiros et al., 2017; Kresimann et al., 2021). All other studies had multidisciplinary contexts: 9 individual articles and 15 reviews.

Theoretical background

Ten articles had no specific theories outlined (Dawson et al., 2019; Katsarov et al., 2022; Watts et al., 2017a; Maesschalck et al., 2015; Marusic et al., 2016; Mulhearn et al., 2017; Mumford et al., 2015; Antes, 2014; Kresimann et al., 2021; Medeiros et al., 2017) as they focused on a tool development or

more general overviews. Others were all based on learning theories (21) as measuring the learning process and training effectiveness falls into the realm of education (e.g., Vygotsky's learning theories, scaffolding, evaluation frameworks, etc.). The findings mostly focused on outlining which training formats were more effective. While active interventions seemed to be more effective, no one format was considered significantly better (Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018).

Research results

The reviewed studies gave an overview of different training formats and evaluation tools that were used for measuring effectiveness of the trainings. Effectiveness was mostly based on meta-analysis and Cohen's *d* (i.e., using the pre-and post-test difference to measure change) (Mulhearn et al., 2017; Medeiros et al., 2017; Watts et al., 2017a, 2017b; Todd et al., 2017; Turner et al., 2018). Quantitative methods also included meta regression analysis (Katsarov et al., 2022) and randomized and non-randomized controlled trials (Marusic et al., 2016). Qualitative studies used various frameworks for evaluation, like Kirkpatrick's 4 levels (Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018), an ethical competence framework (Maesschalck et al., 2015) or a multilevel approach (Mumford et al., 2015).

Primary studies focused on the learning process (Tammeleht et al., 2019, 2020, 2022a, 2022b), knowledge acquisition (Chertock et al., 2013), effectiveness of different methods for teaching REI competencies (MacCormack & Garvan, 2014; Löfström, 2016; Bueda et al., 2023), evaluation measures (Vynicker et al., 2015; Zollitsch et al., 2021; Wada et al., 2013; Dawson et al., 2019) and case studies (Lowe et al., 2018; McIntosh et al., 2018)

1.3.8.3. Summary

The reviewed studies gave an overview of different training formats and evaluation tools that were used for measuring effectiveness of the trainings (Medeiros et al., 2017; Todd et al., 2017a; 2017b; Torrence et al., 2017).

The measurement tools were:

- **Self-assessment** - participant reactions e.g., affective reactions toward training, realism of training, difficulty of materials (Steele et al., 2016 lists 175 trainings, Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018 list 11 trainings out of 21 that utilized self-assessment, content not specified);
- **Pre-post-tests**, with or without control groups – tests usually measure moral reasoning (e.g., with DIT), knowledge, ethical awareness and decision making etc. (Steele et al., 2016) (Watts et al., 2017a – the base for several review papers, lists 124 trainings, Katsarov et al., 2021 outline 30 trainings, Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018 list 5 trainings out of 21);
- **Post-tests**, with or without control groups (Watts et al., 2017a lists 26 trainings, Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018 outline 7 studies out of 21)
- **Cohen's *d*** (difference between pre and post-tests for some studies; for some studies it contained other criteria) - this was calculated by the literature review authors (7 review papers utilized this criterion);
- **Qualitative measurement methods** used for REI training evaluation – grounded theory and general thematic analysis (Watts et al., 2017b); best practices criteria (Watts et al., 2017c); multilevel programme evaluation (Mumford et al., 2015); reflection on curricula (Torrence et al., 2017); ethical competence framework (Maesschalck et al., 2015); Kirkpatrick's framework (Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018); instructional effectiveness (Todd et al., 2017).

While **active interventions**, such as case-based discussion, workshops, group-work, role-plays as opposed to lectures, individual reading tasks seemed to be more effective, no single format was considered significantly better (Stoesz & Yudintseva, 2018).

While reviewed papers outlined that the most used and likely most feasible measures were self-assessment measuring learner reactions, and pre-post-tests measuring knowledge and skills learned, individual papers also outlined other, qualitative possibilities to monitor the learning progress. Some examples are audio-recording of group sessions (Tammeleht et al., 2019, 2020, 2022; Buedo et al., 2023), group (e)portfolios/group reports (Tammeleht et al., 2019, 2022), self-reported measures including satisfaction, engagement and own assessment of reaching the learning goals (Löfström, 2016), and research proposals/seminar reports (Wada et al., 2013). Wada et al., (2013) used the seminar reports compiled a semester after the REI training in the effectiveness measure to longitudinally assess training outcomes. Generally, studies did not address changes in behaviour, however, some studies (Wada et al., 2013) acknowledged that outcomes produced some time after the training may come the closest to a behavioral dimension.

What are challenges / trends / opportunities?

As training formats were different and different measuring tools were used as pre-posttests, the **limitations** were mostly outlined as extensive missing data (Watts et al., 2017a and the reviews utilizing the sample of this study) and heterogeneity of trainings and evaluation tools (Kreismann & Talaulicar, 2021; Maesschalck & De Schrijver, 2015). Sometimes small sample sizes restricted the use of methods for calculating statistical inference (Marusic et al., 2016; Stoesz & Yudintseva, 2018; Katsarov et al., 2021), and small sample sizes were common for qualitative analysis methods (Watts et al., 2017b).

Saturation of measurement tools was reached quickly. After reading a couple of review articles, no new measurement tools were identified (or they were too general). The reason might be that the most prevalent measures are quantitative, and they are easy to apply (only 1 review outlined qualitative methods of 24 trainings – Watts et al., 2017b). Still, as the goals of trainings differ, different tests are used to measure those goals, comparisons become almost impossible.

Based on the review of reviews on training effects, we conclude that **self-assessment** is one of the most prevalent means to measure effectiveness of REI training. Self-assessment (or self-report of reactions to trainings) mostly focused on self-reported confidence in identifying and tackling REI issues better in the future, having learned something new, improved understanding, and having overall positive/negative feelings about the training (e.g., Stoesz & Yudintseva, 2018; Steele et al., 2016). According to Steele et al. (2016), almost 30% of courses use this measure.

The second most frequently used method for assessing training effect was a **moral reasoning test** (various versions of Defining Issues Test - DIT). These were used in 15% of the studies included in one of the reviews (Steele et al., 2016). Ethical decision-making (at 11%), knowledge about regulations (at about 10%) and metacognitive strategies (like perspective taking, sense-making, forecasting) (also at around 10%) followed (Steele et al., 2016). Still, as pointed out by the authors (Steele et al., 2016) there were differences between disciplines – e.g. in business moral reasoning was most popular (at 36%) followed by attitudes (prestige, materialism, social responsibility, etc.) (at 14 %) and selfassessment (reactions) (at 13%), while in science and engineering moral reasoning was used 27% of the time followed by self-assessment (reactions) (at about 20%) and measuring knowledge of regulations (at 16%).

Qualitative measures of effectiveness are scarce and analysis methods were **grounded theory** and general thematic analysis (Watts et al., 2017c), best practices criteria (Watts et al., 2017c); multilevel programme evaluation (Mumford et al., 2015); reflection on curricula (Torrence et al., 2017); ethical competence framework (Maesschalck et al., 2015); Kirkpatrick's framework (Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018); instructional effectiveness (Todd et al., 2017). Also, triangulation and using multiple measurement points was rare (Watts et al., 2017a).

Trends and opportunities encourage combining facilitators and learners' evaluation of the achieved levels provide a more holistic view of what was learned (Tammeleht et al., 2019; 2022). There is a trend to triangulate measurements to gain a holistic view of learning and development of REI (for example utilizing the Structure of the Observed Learning Outcome (SOLO) grid and self-reflection outlined in Tammeleht et al., 2019). Comparing understanding of the learner from different perspectives provides a better picture of the learning outcomes. In addition, various tools could be used to measure individuals and then groups to see potential trends (McCormac & Garvan, 2014; Tammeleht et al., 2020).

What potential research gaps are there?

Several review papers point out (Steele et al., 2016; Mumford et al., 2015; Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018) that evaluation of the effectiveness of REI training is most often based on four variables (based on Kirkpatrick's framework dating back to 1959): reactions (participants' self-assessment), learning (knowledge, content), behaviour (acting in the research community) and results (e.g., institutional outcomes). By the same token, the same reviews admit that while measuring participants' reactions and knowledge/skill is relatively easy to organise, measuring behaviour and results is more difficult and may require different measurement methods. Even if the measure claims to be measuring behaviour (e.g., ethical decision-making tests), it still may not indicate if the person would act ethically in future situations.

Qualitative measures of effectiveness are scarce. While most prevalent measures are quantitative, there is a need to also include and develop qualitative approaches to research REI learning and development. There is also a need to utilize method triangulation and multiple measurement points (like adding a retrospective review as pointed out by Dawson et al., 2019).

While measuring participants' reactions and knowledge/skill is relatively easy to organise, measuring behaviour and results is more difficult. Measures for behavioural change are much scarcer than attitude or perception measures. Outcomes produced some time after the training (like Dawson et al., 2019) may come the closest to measuring a behavioural dimension, i.e., they may serve as displays of ethical planning in the absence of actual observations of how people function in everyday research situations. Utilizing such displays as research data is still scarce.

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1.3.9. Case-based methodologies

1.3.9.1. Introduction

This literature review identifies best practices for *case-based methodologies* in teaching ethics, specifically RE, RI and RCR. These concepts are considered together in this review, with responsible conduct of research serving as an umbrella term covering all three areas. Case-based methodologies use short scenarios or vignettes to simulate real-world situations, encourage perspective-taking, and foster problem-solving skills (Todd et al., 2017). Previous literature reviews and meta-analyses have sporadically addressed case-based methodologies, and this study incorporates them to provide a targeted overview of best practices for teaching RCR. The reviewed studies suggest key practices for effective case-based methodologies in ethics education, field-specific or generic content (not mixed), employing active learning methods in conjunction with cases, and low-to moderate case complexity and realism. This section focuses on features and practices for effective case-based approaches to RCR.

1.3.9.2. What methodological approaches are being used to explore the topic?

Various methodological approaches have been employed to explore the topic of case-based methodologies in teaching RCR. Given the consistent study of this topic over the past few decades, the most relevant approaches in this section are literature reviews (Marusic et al. 2016, Watts, Mulhearn, et al., 2016; Medeiros, Watts et al., 2017; Torrence et al., 2017; De Peuter & Conix, 2023) as well as meta-analyses of primary studies (Todd et al., 2017; Watts, Medeiros, et al., 2016; Katsarov et al., 2022). Focusing on these approaches enables a comprehensive examination and synthesis of existing research in the field.

In addition to meta-analyses and literature reviews, several primary studies are also included in this review (Bagdasarov et al., 2013; Harkrider et al., 2013; Thiel et al., 2013). These primary studies were not included in the literature reviews and meta-analysis surveyed above, but still offered relevant evidence to identify best practices in case-based methodologies. Regarding primary data collection, primary studies typically employed experimental methods followed by statistical analysis such as analysis of variance (ANOVA) and/or other statistical techniques. The standard experimental approach in this area appears to involve systematically varying specific variables within an RCR course, such as case complexity, instructional methods, or scaffolding techniques. Subsequently, researchers examine the effects of these variations on various relevant outcomes, such as ethical knowledge, judgment, and sense-making.

1.3.9.3. What is state of the art knowledge?

Over the past decade, research has consistently shown advancements in the effectiveness of education and training in RCR (Medeiros et al., 2017). A recent literature review by De Peuter and Conix (2023) highlights a shift in RCR education from a focus on knowledge about ethical codes of conduct to the development of skills for ethical problem-solving. Case-based methodologies have emerged as a vital component of this shift, as they have proven to be more effective than traditional approaches in promoting deeper understanding and engagement with ethical issues (Todd et al., 2017). While case-based approaches have demonstrated significant effectiveness in enhancing ethical knowledge and decision-making (De Peuter & Conix, 2023; Watts, Medeiros, et al., 2017; Watts, Mulhearn, et al., 2017), case design and implementation greatly influence their efficacy. This section aims to summarize the key findings about best practices for case-based methodologies.

Case length

De Peuter and Conix (2023) and Watts et al. (2016) both suggest that **longer case descriptions are more effective** than shorter descriptions. In contrast, Mederios et al. (2017) found that case-based activities should be short and frequent.

Case complexity and realism

De Peuter and Conix's (2023) review suggests that cases with **low to moderate complexity** are more effective, allowing learners to better understand and respond to ethical issues. Similarly, Watts, Medeiros, et al. (2016) find that low realism supports effectiveness. Todd et al. (2017) recommend including sufficient information for mental model construction, but also highlight that moderate complexity and low realism are more effective than high complexity or high realism. While Katsarov et al. (2022) did not directly use the term case “realism,” they found that cases with concrete ethical problems are more effective.

Case outcomes

The outcomes of cases also impact **instructional effectiveness**, with cases involving positive outcomes being more effective than those with negative or mixed outcomes (De Peuter and Conix, 2023). Further, Mederios et al. (2017) found that trainees may benefit from forecasting possible outcomes based on the case at hand.

Emotional case content

The role of **emotional elements** in cases is debated. Katsarov et al. (2022) notes evidence that emotional involvement can improve ethical decision-making, while De Peuter and Conix's (2023) review cautions against high emotional content for process-oriented reflection. Both reviews draw from similar literature, indicating a need for further research. Watts, Medeiros, et al. (2016) concluded that high emotional content may reduce effectiveness, while Thiel et al. (2013) found that including emotional content increases knowledge acquisition. Overall, including emotional content, albeit perhaps not “high” emotional content, may be beneficial, but more research is needed in this area.

Including social context in cases

In terms of case context, including **social context** in cases, particularly when described as autonomy-supportive, is beneficial for learning outcomes (Bagdasarov et al., 2013). Social context including descriptions of power dynamics, however, do not appear to influence effectiveness (Thiel et al. 2013). Thiel et al. (2013) suggests that future research should examine other kinds of socio-relational information to determine whether it is relevant or irrelevant to effective case construction.

Case comparisons and number of cases

According to Harkrider et al. (2013), **case comparisons**—presenting two cases with similar underlying principles simultaneously, along with open-ended prompts to compare the cases – seems to improve the effectiveness of training. However, Katsarov et al. (2022) did not find any evidence that the number of cases used in a course influences course effectiveness.

Field specific vs. general content

The question of whether content should be field-specific, multi-disciplinary, or non-field-specific general training has been examined, with mixed findings (De Peuter & Conix, 2023; Medeiros et al., 2017; Torrence et al., 2017). Most studies that addressed the subject found that **content should be field specific or generic**, as mixed approaches are less effective (De Peuter & Conix, 2023; Medeiros et al., 2017; Torrence, Watts, et al. 2017; Watts, Medeiros, et al., 2016). However, Katsarov et al. (2022) did not find evidence that mono/multidisciplinarity had effects on knowledge acquisition.

Active learning methods

Courses that employ case-based approaches in conjunction with a variety of other active learning methods, such as discussion groups, journaling, and lectures, have been found to be more effective than traditional methods (Todd et al., 2017). Highly **interactive delivery methods**, including debates, simulations, role-plays, and small-group discussions, are preferred over less-interactive activities (Watts, Mulhearn, et al., 2016). Similarly, Katsarov et al. 2022 found that experiential and practice-based learning are more effective. De Peuter and Conix 2023 found that multiple different interactive methods (debates, role play, small group discussion etc.) are effective. However, it is important to strike a balance and avoid an excessive number of different methods, as programs employing a small number of delivery activities tend to yield larger effect sizes (Todd et al., 2017; Watts, Medeiros, et al., 2016). Further, Katsarov et al. (2022) found that a practical focus is more important than any specific active learning method (e.g., role play, coaching, interactive novels, etc.).

Group vs individual activities

Medeiros et al. (2017), Katsarov et al. (2022), Todd, et al. (2017) and found that a mix of both individual and group activities is preferable, with Todd et al. (2017) suggesting that it may be advantageous to vary the size of groups in group activity. However, Watts, Medeiros, et al. (2016) and Watts, Mulhearn, et al. (2016) found that individual-based, rather than group-based, activities are more effective.

1.3.9.4. Challenges

The most important challenge in this area is that many of the reviews and studies addressed in this section have **contradictory findings**. For example, ensuring that content is either field-specific or generic, employing active learning methods in conjunction with cases, low-to-moderate case complexity and realism are all unanimously supported by at least two studies, individual versus group-based activities, case length, and case emotional content are all disputed or unclear. Some of this disagreement may be explained by the challenges and limitations discussed below.

Another significant challenge is the weak supporting evidence for education and policy interventions designed to reduce or prevent RM (Marusic et al., 2016). Medeiros et al. (2017) note that there are very few long-term studies of ethics interventions. Long-term follow-up studies are lacking, as most studies only examine RCR courses for a single semester or from a one-day training session, without assessing the long-term impact. There is also a limited understanding of how various features of cases interact with each other, as most studies focus on varying one or two key features without exploring the possible gestalt effects or emergent properties of cases. The current main approach in the literature lacks comprehensive analysis of specific combinations of features that may enhance or diminish effectiveness. Inconsistencies in data reporting further contribute to the challenges in researching the effectiveness of training approaches. Important information, such as course duration, is often missing,

limiting the investigation of various other potentially relevant factors, such as the influence of teacher competence (Katsarov et al., 2022).

1.3.9.5. Gaps and limitations

One major limitation of the literature on case-based methodologies for teaching RCR is the predominant focus on students as the study population, with limited research on post-doctoral or later career stage researchers (Marusic et al., 2016). The applicability of best practices identified for graduate students to other populations remains uncertain due to a lack of evidence. Additionally, there may be relevant differences between different learner groups, with Katsarov et al. (2022) suggesting that high-school students tend to show greater learning effects compared to students of higher education. This may suggest that there are relevant differences between what constitutes most effective ethics education for students at different education levels. Larger studies with diverse populations, including active researchers, are needed to enhance the understanding of case-based methodologies and ensure the generalizability of current research (Katsarov et al. 2022). These limitations are consistent with a more general trend reported by Marusic et al. (2016) that suggests that evidence in RCR training and research misconduct prevention is overall weak.

1.3.9.6. Opportunities and recommendations

Based on this review, opportunities for further research and policy guidance exist in exploring the overlap between case-based approaches and virtue-based approaches to RI. While virtue-based approaches have been proven effective in RE, there is limited explicit examination of how virtues can be emphasized in case studies. Incorporating the extensive work on virtue-based approaches into case-based methodologies represents a significant opportunity for enhancing ethical education and training.

Several key areas warrant further exploration due to existing disagreements or due to current reviews stating the need for further research. For example, further research should focus on the social context included in cases, as there is currently limited understanding of its effects. The role of emotional content in case studies also calls for additional study. At the moment, there is disagreement over whether, and to what extent, including emotional content in cases increases effectiveness. Additionally, further examination of the impacts of high versus low emotional content may be useful. Lastly, the optimal length of case studies is an area with unresolved disagreement. Further investigation would be useful to determine whether shorter or longer cases are more effective for teaching ethics. Altogether, these topics present meaningful opportunities for future research that could significantly impact the effectiveness of case-based methodologies for teaching ethics.

Another key recommendation for future research is to carry out replication studies with diverse learner groups and randomized control trials that compare different teaching approaches are recommended to strengthen the knowledge base (Katsarov et al., 2022). Researchers are encouraged to report information systematically and conduct studies that examine multiple learning outcomes (Katsarov et al., 2022).

Finally, although there is a substantial body of evidence around best practices in this area, there may still be limited dissemination and uptake of such practices. De Peuter and Conix (2023) note that the uptake of best practices in RCR education is very limited. Encouraging uptake of evidence based best practices for using case studies in RCR education and training represents a significant policy opportunity.

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1.4. SYNTHESIS AND CONCLUSIONS

1.4.1. Introduction

This section first provides a quantitative descriptive synthesis of the literature gathered in Section 1.3 and identifies patterns and trends across the reviewed literature. It then offers a qualitative synthesis, which highlights the main common themes and general lessons learned in this scoping review exercise.

Throughout the section, topics from Section 1.3 are referred to by the following numbers:

1. Behavioural and organisational ethics
2. Moral psychology related to the promotion of REI and breaches of these standards
3. Opportunities and challenges in the public and private sectors (including SMEs)
4. Personal and institutional responsibilities for the promotion of REI
5. 5: Questions related to the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers
6. 6: Researchers' mental health and well-being in relation to research misconduct (including those employed in uncertain work conditions)
7. Gender dimensions and power relations in the context of research misconduct
8. Case-based methodologies
9. Measurement of the effects of RCR training

In keeping with the usage throughout this literature review, the following acronyms are used in this section: RE for Research Ethics; RI for Research Integrity; RM for Research Misconduct; RCR for Responsible Conduct of Research (this is an umbrella term, used particularly when referring to training programs).

1.4.2. Descriptive statistics and quantitative trends

A total 149 studies were included in the final review, distributed across the nine topics as follows: N = 37 (topic 1, 25% of total circa), N = 25 (topic 2, 17%), N = 2 (3, 1%), N = 26 (4, 17%), N = 2 (5, 1%), N = 5 (6, 3%), N = 10 (7, 7%), N = 11 (8, 7%), N = 31 (9, 21%).

Each colour represents a topic, as shown in the legend. Top: total trend. Bottom: trend for each topic. Topics are listed by number (1: Behavioural and organisational ethics; 2: Moral psychology related to the promotion of REI and breaches of these standards; 3: Opportunities and challenges in the public and private sectors; 4: Personal and institutional responsibilities for the promotion of REI; 5: Questions related to the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers; 6: Researchers' mental health and well-being in relation to research misconduct; 7: Gender dimensions and power relations in the context of research misconduct; 8: Case-based methodologies; 9: Measurement of the effects of RCR training).

Figure 1.4.1. Number (count) of studies included in the review, by year of publication.

The number of included studies was larger overall in more recent years of the study range (Figure 1.4.1, top), but the trend was mainly driven by topics 1, 2 and 6 (Figure 1.4.1, Bottom).

number of studies included in each topic, by methodology and type

Each colour represents a topic, shown in the legend (1: Behavioural and organisational ethics; 2: Moral psychology related to the promotion of REI and breaches of these standards; 3: Opportunities and challenges in the public and private sectors; 4: Personal and institutional responsibilities for the promotion of REI; 5: Questions related to the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers; 6: Researchers' mental health and well-being in relation to research misconduct; 7: Gender dimensions and power relations in the context of research misconduct; 8: Case-based methodologies; 9: Measurement of the effects of RCR training). Primary refers to a study collecting and analysing new data; secondary refers to a review and synthesis or analysis of previously published primary studies.

Figure 1.4.2. Number (count) of studies included in the review, by methodology and type.

The methodological approaches taken were almost equally divided between quantitative and qualitative methods ($N = 75$ and $N = 57$, respectively) although a minority ($N = 15$) used mixed methods (Figure 1.4.2). A relative majority of this literature consisted of primary studies ($N = 97$), whilst the remaining part included systematic review and metaanalyses (that is, quantitative secondary studies), narrative reviews and essays overviewing a literature (which were classified as qualitative secondary studies) and in a few cases doing both (Figure 1.4.2).

number of studies included in each topic, by discipline

Only disciplines with one or more articles are shown. Each colour represents a topic, as shown in the legend. Top: total numbers. Bottom: numbers for each topic, plotted with the same discipline order shown in the top panel. Topics are indicated by number (1: Behavioural and organisational ethics; 2: Moral psychology related to the promotion of REI and breaches of these standards; 3: Opportunities and challenges in the public and private sectors; 4: Personal and institutional responsibilities for the promotion of REI; 5: Questions related to the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers; 6: Researchers’ mental health and well-being in relation to research misconduct; 7: Gender dimensions and power relations in the context of research misconduct; 8: Case-based methodologies; 9: Measurement of the effects of RCR training).

Figure 1.4.3. Number (count) of studies included in the review, by discipline.

The majority of studies were multidisciplinary in scope, meaning that they either examined the issue in general terms, without focusing on a particular discipline, or that they collected and analysed data on multiple disciplines (Figure 1.4.3, top). Discipline-specific studies were mainly focused on Clinical Medicine or the social and behavioural sciences (in particular, Psychiatry and Psychology), and few other disciplines were represented at all (Figure 1.4.3 top). A non-negligible number of studies in several topics focused on ‘practitioners’, meaning that it targeted experts on RCR or related relevant topics. This pattern characterized all the topics (Figure 1.4.3, bottom).

number of studies included in each topic, by country

Each colour represents a topic, as shown in the legend. Top: total numbers. Bottom: numbers for each topic. Topics are indicated by number (1: Behavioural and organisational ethics; 2: Moral psychology related to the promotion of REI and breaches of these standards; 3: Opportunities and challenges in the public and private sectors; 4: Personal and institutional responsibilities for the promotion of REI; 5: Questions related to the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers; 6: Researchers' mental health and well-being in relation to research misconduct; 7: Gender dimensions and power relations in the context of research misconduct; 8: Case-based methodologies; 9: Measurement of the effects of RCR training).

Figure 1.4.4. Number (count) of studies included in the review, grouped by the study's country of focus, if specified.

Similarly to the discipline data, the majority of studies in all topics was either multinational in scope, or not referring to any particular country (Figure 1.4.4 top). The majority of single country studies were conducted in the United States, across all topics (Figure 1.4.4, bottom), although a few countries seemed especially represented in some topics (e.g. India for topic 1, Australia for 2, Estonia for 8), although the numbers of papers about these countries are a small proportion of the total.

number of studies included in each topic, by theoretical stance

Each bar corresponds to the topic, labelled with the topic number (1: Behavioural and organisational ethics; 2: Moral psychology related to the promotion of REI and breaches of these standards; 3: Opportunities and challenges in the public and private sectors; 4: Personal and institutional responsibilities for the promotion of REI; 5: Questions related to the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers; 6: Researchers' mental health and well-being in relation to research misconduct; 7: Gender dimensions and power relations in the context of research misconduct; 8: Case-based methodologies; 9: Measurement of the effects of RCR training).

Figure 1.4.5. Number (count) of studies included in the review that did or did not specify a theory as a basis for its analysis.

Circa 38% (N = 55) of the studies specified one or more theories upon which it based its analysis or recommendations, with a very large variability across topics (Figure 1.4.5).

1.4.3. Qualitative synthesis

Across the nine topics, and despite a considerable variability in the volume and type of literature examined by each topic, it is possible to glean a few common patterns and trends, which paint a consistent picture of the state of knowledge on RCR, the quality of the evidence and the general challenges that BEYOND (and similar projects) face.

1.4.4. Insights on state-of-the-art knowledge

Across the studied topics, the review highlighted several consistent empirical results, suggesting that some important RCR questions have been settled by theoretical and empirical analyses. These include:

- Higher risk of RM and QRP for early-career researchers. Empirical evidence generally supports theoretical consideration and intuitive speculations that a variety of factors make junior researchers particularly exposed including precarious and uncertain working conditions, competition for limited funding, unequal power relations between junior and senior researchers,

and gender inequalities (see sections 1.3.6.2, 1.3.7.2), although the literature is not fully consistent and is sometimes of low quality, as discussed further below.

- No significant gender differences in the overall risk of engaging in RM. Whilst a higher risk for males is often hypothesized (including for student academic misconduct, section 3.1.3), empirical studies failed to observe significant differences in multiple behavioural dimensions relevant to RM and RI such as personality, self-control, moral (dis)engagement and willingness to risk confrontation by whistle-blowing (see section 1.3.2.3, 1.3.7.2), in line with other literature not explored by this review.
- RCR training is valuable, particularly when it imparts ethical problem-solving skills. There is an ample literature on training that generally suggests a positive impact (e.g., sections 1.3.1.3, 1.3.9.3), although assessments of the effectiveness of specific interventions are mostly inconclusive due to significant methodological limitations (discussed below).

Furthermore, there is a general agreement in the literature that in addition to a focus on the individual researcher, the environment in which researchers operate and other contextual factors including academic hierarchies, research funding structures, education and training, and the monitoring and evaluation of RM are likely to be relevant and require further research and policy attention (see sections 1.3.1.3, 1.3.1.5, 1.3.2.5, 1.3.3.4, 1.3.4.3 for discussion of these aspects).

However, another pattern common to most topics and questions explored by this review is that consensus on any particular issue is low and existing evidence is often contradictory. The inconclusive nature of current evidence was noted by studies across all topics. The inconsistent nature of available evidence is well exemplified by topic 5, which only found two relevant studies that had reached "somewhat contradictory conclusions" about the same question (section 1.3.5.2). It must be emphasized in this context that inconsistent and contradictory findings, whilst possibly the results of poor-quality research, are inevitable in any area of research that is complex and multifaceted. The limited and contradictory nature of existing evidence, in other words, is primarily an indicator that studies and evidence about RM, RE and RI need to take more into account the extreme complexity of the phenomena being examined and need to be better contextualized, including the cultural and organisational dimensions (aspects that will be discussed further below).

In many cases, no evidence exists at all. There is indeed a visibly unequal distribution of studies across the topics, and some topics yielded as little as two relevant studies (Figure 1.4.1). This wide imbalance may be partially explained by how the topics were defined (some topics are much broader in scope than others) and in limitations of the search methodology (which adopted very specific sets of strings to narrow the scope; see Appendix A). Nonetheless, the literature searches implemented in this review are certainly more extensive than what the average researcher or policy maker might use when seeking evidence. Therefore, we can conclude that for some of the topics relevant evidence is not easily found the literature and/or is lacking altogether. This highlights several opportunities to conduct novel and high-quality research in areas of interest to the BEYOND project and for future research funding.

1.4.5. Insights on challenges

The challenges highlighted in the literature across the nine topics again showed several common themes, which include:

- **Optimizing a trade-off between uniformity and diversity.** On the one hand, the literature points to excessively variable standards in definitions, measurements, policies, which are rightly believed to limit progress in preventing RI and addressing RM (e.g., sections 1.3.1.4, 1.3.1.5, 1.3.4.3, 1.3.4.4) across fields and countries. On the other hand, the literature also increasingly

emphasizes the need to take into account the complex and context-sensitive nature of RI and RM, suggesting that both research and policy need to become more context-specific to be informative and effective (e.g., sections 1.3.2.4, 1.3.4.5, 1.3.6.2, 1.3.7.2, 1.3.9.6).

- **Improving standards of quality and integrity within research on RI itself.** As noted above, it is common for studies in this review to point out the poor quality of the evidence and analyses produced in their area of interest. This is particularly evident in those areas that are also where most research is found (e.g., sections 1.3.1.3, 1.3.8.4, 1.3.9.3). Moreover, a growing number of papers highlight how studies on RI often do not meet the standards that they are often promoting, for example in terms of completeness of methodological description, data sharing, and equipoise in evaluating evidence (e.g., 1.3.4.5, 1.3.5.3, 1.3.9.5).
- **Better managing of conflicts of interest and RI by stakeholder institutions.** A considerable proportion of the existing literature has highlighted the important role that institutions play in creating a research environment supportive of RI (e.g., 1.3.1.3, 1.3.4.3, 1.3.6.2, 1.3.7.2). However, a relatively novel emphasis is now placed on how institutions might betray their own stated mission of conducting, funding, or publishing research. For example, institutions might mismanage conflicts of interests in handling cases of RM (e.g., 1.3.1.4, 1.3.4.3), and might exceed their remit or be subject to undue influence by commercial interests sponsoring projects and institutions (e.g. 1.3.1.4, 1.3.4.4).

1.4.6. Insights on gaps and limitations

The most common and important gaps highlighted across topics include:

- Lack of **sufficient evidence** to justify conclusions and interventions. In particular:
- Several areas of investigation lack high quality primary quantitative studies, often because research methods are insufficiently standardized and transparent to permit replications and meta-analytical summaries (e.g., 1.3.4.5, 1.3.5.3, 1.3.8.4, 1.3.9.5).
- Qualitative research was also seen as lacking in both frequency and quality. The analysis of several topics highlighted, implicitly or explicitly, the need for in-depth interviews, case studies and impact evaluation studies, which are especially important to pursue the goal of contextualizing our understanding of RI and related problems (e.g., 1.3.1.5, 1.3.4.5, 1.3.5.4, 1.3.6.4, 1.3.7.4, 1.3.8.4, 1.3.9.6).
- Lack of **adequate methods** to incorporate complexity and context into research evidence. Across topics, there was a noticeable contrast between, on the one hand, the suggestion that complexity and context are important factors in research (see above) and, on the other hand, the observed lack of defined methodologies to make that integration possible. The most straightforward way to integrate context and complexity in research consists in integrating qualitative and quantitative data, but only a minority of studies do so (Figure 1.4.2).
- Theory also appears to be lacking. More accurately, theoretically-informed research abounds in some topics and is absent from others (Figure 1.4.5). But even in the topics where theories are present, they consist in frameworks and paradigms developed for other disciplines (e.g., theories from Moral Psychology for topic 2 and Social Psychology for topic 8). Whilst our results may be somewhat confounded by what exactly is meant by "theory", they point to a clear and **general lack of specific theoretical foundations for research** in RI, RE and RM.

Another significant gap highlighted in several topics is the narrow focus of existing evidence. For example:

- Most empirical studies have had students and junior researchers as their primary targets (e.g. 1.3.1.3, 1.3.2.4, 1.3.4.5, 1.3.6.4, 1.3.9.5). Whilst there are several good reasons why these groups

are of special interest (see above), other categories of researchers appear to have been neglected.

- Privately-funded research may tend to be overlooked, at least in the areas of focus of this review (e.g. 1.3.3.1). At the policy and regulatory level, this gap is institutionalized since the remit of most national and institutional offices of RI (where these are present) typically exclude non-publicly funded and non-academic research. However, there is no reason why research on RI should be confined to public and ordinarily peer-reviewed research, when other types of research may be typically at greater risk from biases and undue influences and prone to RM (1.3.1.3, 1.3.4.3).
- Non-academic research more generally seems to constitute a blind spot. For example, research sponsored or conducted by NGOs has been largely neglected in the literature, despite being at risk from a variety of conflicting interest and little accountability (1.3.1.5).
- The current literature has a marked multidisciplinary and multi-national focus (Figures 1.4.3, Figure 1.4.4). In some cases, such studies may be comparative, but in general the broad focus of these studies reflects the universalizing intentions of much research to date. Whilst this is not a limitation but rather a feature of the universal tendencies that have dominated the field to date, it stands in contrast to the current need of more contextualization (see above). Conducting more localized, in-depth analyses of cases and problems may be the next step in the process of maturation of the literature.
- Several new areas where the understanding of RI is incomplete or lacking. For example, mental health conditions (1.3.6.2) and power imbalances (1.3.7.4) are likely to represent an important contextual element that can both help explain and, when intervened upon, mitigate the risk of RM.

1.4.7. Opportunities and recommendations

In conclusion, the literature examined in this review suggests a few overall priorities and recommendations for future research, which are well-aligned with BEYOND's mission. Three significant recommendations that can be derived from this study are to:

- **Improve the quality and rigour of evidence.** For example, studies need to ensure a thorough description of methods, a transparent discussion of limitations, and the use of high-quality and standardized measurements.
- **Incorporate context and complexity in research on RI, RE and RM.** Studies should be designed to take into account, if not directly assess if and how contextual factors that are hypothesized to be relevant affect RI and RM. Where suitable theories and methodologies are lacking, they need to be developed.
- **Strike an optimal balance between uniformity and diversity.** On the one hand, both research and policies seem to lack sufficient homogeneity to achieve maximum efficiency. On the other hand, standards and regulations need to be tailored to context-specific realities. There is a healthy dialectic between universalizing and contextualizing objectives that should be fostered, recognized, and factored into decision making.

Part 2 – Insights from the review of cases on research ethics and integrity, research misconduct and questionable research practices

2.1. Introduction

2.1.1. Purpose

This report presents the findings of a review of recent cases of real-life experiences of research misconduct (RM), carried out as part of BEYOND Project (<https://beyondbadapples.eu>), to specify and evaluate the multiple individual and organisational factors that lead researchers to commit research misconduct. In doing so, the report focuses specifically on three thematic areas identified in T1.2 of the BEYOND Grant Agreement (GA), in which the report's research team were able to identify relevant cases: reporting and whistle-blowing, gender aspects (including discrimination, sexual harassment, and other forms of gender-based violence) and researcher working conditions.

In addition to investigating the themes described above, the report also evaluates significant novel and emerging factors affecting REI identified in this case study review. Better understanding these will help researchers, educators, and REI experts and practitioners to identify current challenges and needs in the REI field, and develop proactive approaches to improve research culture, reduce the occurrence of RM and mitigate its harmful impacts.

2.1.2. Overview of Methodology

The review upon which this report is based consists of two methodological components. The first is a brief comparative analysis of higher-level contextual factors influencing the REI environments in the BEYOND project partner countries (Cyprus, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, UK), including both relevant statistical data and benchmark data for comparing the legal and regulatory contexts in these countries. Additional analytical detail is also provided to compare the research environment in the four countries that are subsequently investigated in the in-depth qualitative evaluation component. The purpose of this component is to provide a foundational understanding of the often-significant similarities and differences between the research environments in BEYOND partner countries, which are likely to influence the project's findings and analytic conclusions, and provide a comparative basis for understanding and contextualizing the qualitative discussion of case studies in the report.

The second methodological component of the study is an in-depth qualitative exercise which gathered and thematically analysed 23 case studies from the last five years across four partner countries within the BEYOND consortium – Estonia (3 cases), Latvia (6 cases), the Netherlands (8 cases) and the UK (6 cases). Case studies were gathered from press and online media sources in both English and local languages that could be corroborated by additional independent sources, including investigatory reports, institutional statements, the Retraction Watch blog and database (<https://retractionwatch.com>), and professional online profiles (e.g. LinkedIn, University researcher profiles). This approach for case study data collection allowed for the extraction of 'thick' qualitative data with a high degree of narrative depth and factual detail about the unique, specific and intersecting factors that comprised each case. This approach also provided a practical solution to overcome a lack of databases or centralized reporting mechanisms for RM in Europe at both the national level and a wider regional

level.¹ Thematically, 13 cases related to reporting and whistle-blowing, 5 cases involved gender aspects (including discrimination, sexual harassment, and other forms of gender-based violence), 5 cases involved researcher working conditions, and 17 cases were linked to novel and emerging factors. However, most cases were linked to multiple thematic categories, particularly with relation to novel and emergent findings.

2.1.3. Structure

The report is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a detailed description of the report's methodology, including inclusion criteria for the collated case studies. Section 3 provides a comparative analysis of the research and REI environment in the BEYOND partner countries, with an emphasis on Estonia, Latvia, the Netherlands and the UK, since these are the focus of the in-depth qualitative analysis. The main empirical findings of the case study review are then presented in Section 4. These findings are organized according to theme in the following order: reporting and whistleblowing mechanisms, gender (including discrimination, sexual harassment and other forms of gender-based violence), researcher working conditions, novel and significant findings. This is followed by a concluding discussion in Section 5, which presents an analysis of our main findings, and brief evaluation of gaps in the literature that came to light in this review and recommendations for emerging areas that merit greater scholarly and practitioner attention within the REI field.

¹ Whilst the authors did use the Retraction Watch (<https://retractionwatch.com>) database and blog to corroborate reported cases, the research found that using the database to obtain cases was of limited value for several reasons. The main reason for this is Retraction Watch's remit is limited to only retractions from papers published in scholarly journals. Whilst there is a correlation between many retractions and RM, retractions occur for a variety of reasons and are not always due to RM. Another reason is that there are 107 distinct categories for reasons for retractions in the database, and the reasons for a retraction in a particular entry were almost always multiple. Therefore, it was difficult to distinguish or evaluate these factors without a more detailed qualitative understanding of the reasons for a specific retraction.

2.2. Methodology

The methodology for the in-depth qualitative analysis carried out in this review entailed gathering descriptions of documented instances of misconduct from specific countries of interest and conducting a comparative qualitative analysis of these cases according to significant thematic areas highlighted in the GA, with an emphasis on identifying particular patterns, trends and extracting salient features from the cases.

2.2.1. Inclusion Criteria and Identification and Analysis Procedure for Cases

A. Basic inclusion/exclusion criteria for selecting cases for this study were the following:

- Cases were reported in the last five years (2019 – Sept. 2023).
- Cases must involve evidence or accusations of RM or Questionable Research Practices (QRPs).

B. Geographical selection criteria. Firstly, **four** case study countries were selected based on the following criteria in ranked order:

- a. Linguistic expertise of researchers: Estonia (Kadri Simm and Heldi Lang), Latvia (Signe Mezinska and Eliza Lasmane), UK (Ian Slesinger) and Netherlands (Susanne van den Hooff)
- b. Data availability – we relied on materials published either in the media or in the dedicated institutions (e.g. Information Commissioner’s Office in the UK, research integrity advisory board LOWI in Netherlands).
- c. Data Triangulation and Validation – More than one source should be available for each case to triangulate and validate the information.

C. Case Study Identification and Analysis process:

- a. Initial identification – Relevant case studies were identified through searches of key terms including ‘academic ethics,’ ‘research ethics’ and ‘research misconduct’ (translated to local languages where appropriate) in both search engine news searches and by using search features of major national newspapers in local languages.
- b. Triangulation and Validation – Links to other stories or documents in online news articles were then followed and collated, and additional web searches were carried out to obtain additional evidence for triangulation. These documents included institutional or Research Integrity Office (RIO) reports on investigations, public statements from institutions, Freedom of Information request results, publication retraction notices, archived social media post, and relevant blog posts and op-ed pieces.
- c. Collation and analysis framework – Evidence from these cases was then collated and analysed on a spreadsheet containing the following data categories:
 - i. Title for reference
 - ii. Brief summary of case
 - iii. date (including occurrence of [alleged] RM and date of reporting)
 - iv. Type of RM/QRP alleged/committed
 - v. misconduct context (publication, grant, research lab etc.)
 - vi. How/where discovered
 - vii. Institution(s)/organisations
 - viii. discipline or commercial field
 - ix. . Researcher level (Student, ECR, Professor etc.)
 - x. Outcome/ Consequences (include retractions from Retraction Watch if available)
 - xi. Source(s) found
 - xii. Sources (including links)
 - xiii. GA themes applicable (see below)
 - xiv. Significant aspects/findings

- xv. New or emerging factors
- xvi. additional comments

- D. Included studies were categorized according to relevance to BEYOND project GA Call Themes:
- a. Adequacy of reporting and whistleblowing mechanisms.
 - b. Gender-related issues, including discrimination, sexual harassment, and other forms of gender-based violence.
 - c. Mental health and well-being.
 - d. Working conditions, considering factors such as career stage, precarious employment, and student experiences.
 - e. Rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers involved in RM.
 - f. New and emerging factors (other)

N.B. Studies could be assigned to multiple categories.

2.2.2. Comparative Data Analysis

For the comparative analysis of countries, we adapted several indicators from Perković Paloš et al. (2023) to benchmark the research environment in the BEYOND partner countries. We then updated the statistical data with more recent figures from the European Union (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>) and the World Bank (<https://data.worldbank.org/>). We then used the list of members by country from the European Network of Research Integrity Offices (ENRIO) website (<http://www.enrio.eu/members/>) to identify national REI bodies. We then conducted an online search and used contributors' expertise to verify the data regarding number of universities per country, RM adjudication bodies, national codes of conducts and whistle-blower protection laws.

2.2.3. Limitations and Justification

The results of the case-based study are not generalizable. We relied on a convenience sample, although our clear inclusion/exclusion criteria provided a shared frame for data collection. However, availability and quality of the data varied between countries and cases and media resources are potentially biased. Therefore, the publication of RM and QRP cases is likely to be affected by selective reporting (e.g. more sensational or those involving senior research figures are more likely to be published) which is commonly influenced by an individual newspaper's bias towards a particular political perspective. Requiring multiple sources for a case, and triangulating analysis between them, was applied as a mitigation strategy to counteract the influence of media bias in the review. The study focused on four select countries, of varying sizes of population (from Estonia's 1.3M to UK's 67M) but lacked representation from southern Europe. Also, as is often the case with REI issues, data from private sector research is not publicly available due to the closed nature of private sector organisations, their limited requirements for transparency, and the protection of intellectual property they are afforded. Finally, the case studies, especially if presented in the media, are potentially simplified for communication to non-specialist audiences.

2.3. Comparative analysis of BEYOND countries

This section contextualizes the research environment in the countries involved in the BEYOND project, and particularly the four countries featured in the in-depth qualitative review, to form a comparative basis for understanding the divergent factors that contribute to how RMs and QRPs occur and are managed between these countries. To do so, the following factors will be evaluated (adapted from Perković Paloš et al., 2023), as shown in Figure 2.3.1 on the following page:

- Number of full-time researchers – both total and per 1M inhabitants
- Number of universities
- Research expenditure – both total and as percentage of Gross Domestic Product (GDP)
- The number of national bodies promoting REI
- Whether a country has national bodies that handle cases of research misconduct
- Whether a national code of conduct for REI exists
- Whether a country has whistle-blower protection laws

The relationship between these factors shapes the research environment in several ways, and can either incentivise RM, or reduce its likelihood. For example, the overall amount of available funding in a country or region, and how that funding is distributed between institutions and research disciplines, influences the nature and intensity of competition between researchers (Harvey, 2020). Conversely, having large amounts of research funds available combined with weak governance and auditing structures by research funding organisations and research performing organisations (RPOs) can increase the risk of RM, both in terms of encouraging harmful research practices by researchers to obtain funding, and enabling financial crimes by researchers (e.g. Bonner, 2023). Whilst comprehensive quantitative data does not currently exist to correlate cases of RMs to these factors, it is possible to gain a comparative sense of the financial and governance factors that influence REI between countries.

2.3.1. BEYOND Partner Countries Overview

In terms of research funding, Germany has the highest amount amongst the BEYOND countries both in real terms (€121.1bn) and as a percentage of GDP (3.13%). Even though Finland's ranking is 6 out of 9 in real terms for research funding amount, it is the 2nd highest in terms of percentage GDP. The Netherlands and France also rank in the upper half in terms of both real term funding amounts and funding as a percentage of GDP. Norway is the median country in terms of both measures of funding. In comparison, the UK contributes approximately €44.4bn in research funding (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/>), which ranks 3rd highest in real terms, but ranks 6 out of 9 in terms of percentage GDP, despite having a relatively large research sector ranking 3 out of 9 in number of full-time

Country	Number of FT Researchers – total/per 1m inhabitants (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/)	Number of Universities	GDP per Capita (PPP adjusted, World Bank data 2022)	Total research expenditure 2022 (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/)	Research expenditure as % GDP 2022 (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/)	The number of national bodies promoting REI (http://www.enrrio.eu/members/)	Bodies that handle research misconduct	National Code of conduct for REI
Cyprus	1,562/1,735 (2021)	9	€ 45,946	€212.5m	0.83%	None	None	No
Estonia*	5370 (2021)/4,037	7	€ 42,971	€641.7m	1.75%	1	Research institutions	Yes
Finland	43,554 (2021)/7,876	14	€ 54,316	€7,936.1m	2.99%	1	Finnish National Board on Research Integrity (TENK)	No
France	333,800 (2021)/4,931	116	€ 51,063	€55,498.9m	2.22%	4	Research institutions	Yes
Germany	461,645/5,549 (2021)	108	€ 58,110	€121,164.5m	3.13%	5	German Research Ombudsman (Ombudsman für die Wissenschaft)	Yes
Latvia*	4,537 (2021)/2,401	6	€ 36,768	€290.5m	0.74%	None	Research institutions and courts	Yes
Netherlands*	106,099 (2021)/6,063	18	€ 64,025	€22,010.4m	2.27%	2	Research Institutions (advised by the Netherlands Board on Research Integrity [LOWI])	Yes
Norway	38,971 (2021)/7,230	10	€ 105,730	€8,792.6m	1.94%	1	The National Commission for the Investigation of Research Misconduct (GRU)	No
UK*	317,472 (approx.)/4,766 (2019)	122 (2024)	€ 50,245	€44,364.3m (2019)	1.76%	1	Research institutions	No

Figure 2.3.1. Comparison of Measures influencing Research Ethics and Integrity in Beyond Member Countries (* in-depth qualitative review countries; indicators adapted from Perković Paloš et al., 2023 and updated with most recent data)

researchers and 1 out of 9 in terms of number of universities. Estonia ranks 7 out of 9 in terms of both research funding in real terms and as a percentage in GDP, whilst Latvia and Cyprus rank lowest in terms of research funding by both metrics. In geographical terms this generally correlates with Northern and Western Europe being the most powerful in terms of research funding, whilst Southern Europe and Eastern Europe are the weakest.

There is significant variability between European countries in terms of national governance structures for promoting, monitoring and adjudicating REI. Germany, it can be argued, has the strongest centralized REI governance structures as it is the only country in the comparison table to have both a national code of conduct for REI – the German Research Foundation’s (DFG) “Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice” (DFG, 2022) – and a national body for investigating and handling RM – the DFG’s German Research Ombudsman. However, Estonia, France, Latvia and the Netherlands also have national codes of conduct for REI, although these countries do not have centralized bodies that directly handle research misconduct. However, the Netherlands Board on Research Integrity (LOWI; <https://lowi.nl>) will act as a secondary advisory body to institutional investigatory committees in cases where an involved party is dissatisfied with the outcome (ENRIO, 2019), and in Latvia the courts will adjudicate RM cases in some instances. Finland and Norway both have national bodies that handle cases of research misconduct – the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity (TENK; <https://tenk.fi/en>) and the National Commission for the Investigation of Research Misconduct (GRU; <https://www.forskningsetikk.no/en>) respectively – but no national code of conduct. The UK has no national code of conduct nor central body that adjudicates RM, which is handled at the institutional level. However, it does have the UK Research Integrity Office (UKRIO), which has no formal legal powers and acts in an advisory capacity to “direct researchers, organisations and the public to regulatory bodies when issues fall within their jurisdiction” (UKRIO, 2023). Cyprus also has no national code of conduct for REI nor central adjudication body, and it is unclear what are the extent and robustness of institutional mechanisms for adjudicating RM there.

All the BEYOND partner countries have at least some mechanisms for whistle-blower protection in place, with the only exception being Estonia. This is conducive to incentivizing the reporting of REI, at least in legal terms, although institutional and economic factors could counterbalance this benefit in some countries, organisations and individual cases. It should be noted that there are no clear regional patterns in the prevalence and robustness of REI governance that can be correlated to geographical differences.

2.3.2. Contrasting the In-depth Case Study Countries

Attention will now turn to providing a more focused comparison of Estonia, Latvia, the UK and the Netherlands, using the same data as the previous discussion (Figure 2.3.1). These are the four countries that will feature in the in-depth thematic examination of significant and emerging factors contributing to RM in the section that follows.

Within Europe’s geography the UK and the Netherlands are both mid-sized North-western European countries, whilst the Latvia and Estonia are neighbouring small states on the Baltic coast on the Eastern edge of the European Union bordering Russia. The UK has a significantly higher population than all the other three countries, whilst both Estonia and Latvia have relatively small populations of less than 2m people (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/>). In economic terms the Netherlands is the wealthiest country with a GDP per capita of 28% larger than that of the UK, as well as a significantly lower rate of economic inequality than the UK (<https://data.worldbank.org/>). Whilst both Estonia and Latvia have a significantly lower GDP than the UK, there is still a significant economic disparity between the two Baltic states with Estonia having a 17% higher GDP per capita, and a significantly lower rate of economic inequality than Latvia (<https://data.worldbank.org/>).

In real terms the UK has the largest number of researchers out of the four countries followed by the Netherlands, Estonia and Latvia. However, the Netherlands in fact has more researchers per capita than the UK, even though the UK has over six times the number of universities as the Netherlands. It is also noteworthy that the UK has weaker governance structures than the Netherlands despite the significantly larger size of the UK's research sector, as evidenced by the UK having fewer national bodies promoting REI, the lack of a national code of conduct, and relatively weaker integration of adjudication processes with national bodies. Whilst Estonia and Latvia both have significantly smaller research sectors compared to the UK and the Netherlands, as is to be expected due to their smaller demographics, in comparative terms Estonia has a 68% higher number of researchers per capita than Latvia, even though both countries are quite similar in terms of the number of universities they contain. There are both similarities and meaningful differences between Estonia and Latvia's REI governance structures. Both countries have a national code of conduct for REI, as well as institutional procedures for investigating and handling research misconduct. However, Estonia has one distinct national body that promotes REI (Eesti Teadusagentuur, 2022), whilst Latvia has none. Conversely, Latvia has a whistle-blower protection law in place, while Estonia has none, although there is currently a legislative process underway to create such a law there.

In terms of research funding, the UK has by far the highest amount of research funding in real terms out of the four in-depth case study countries, at over double that of the Netherlands, and approximately 150 times that of Latvia. However, when looked at as a percentage of GDP, the Netherlands spends 0.5% more than the UK on research, which is roughly on par with Estonia. Latvia lags far behind the other countries in terms of research funding, spending on research as a percentage of GDP 1.53% less than the Netherlands, and 1.01% less than Estonia. This correlates with Latvia's weak economic position relative to the other in-depth case study countries.

In conclusion, the differences in population, economic status, and research infrastructure highlight the complexity of addressing REI issues comparatively. Increased resources allocated to research might translate into enhanced resources for the improvement and enforcement of REI norms when combined with effective governance and oversight. Despite the UK's larger research sector, it exhibits weaker national-level governance structures compared to the Netherlands. Estonia and Latvia, while having smaller research sectors, showcase both similarities and differences in their research ethics and integrity (REI) governance structures. This comparison sets the stage for a more in-depth thematic examination of the significant and emerging factors contributing to REI issues in the subsequent sections.

2.4. Thematic qualitative analysis of case studies

2.4.1. Reporting and whistleblowing mechanisms

One of the most significant issues to emerge from this analysis is that there is often a **long timescale between when a researcher or researchers begin engaging in RM**, or when an instance of RM occurs, and when it is reported or emerges in public fora such as the press or online social media. 11 out of the 2 cases recorded in this study included this aspect as a notable feature (6 from the Netherlands, 3 from Latvia, 2 from the UK). In one serious case, a Dutch political anthropologist who retired from the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU) in 2002, was found by a university committee in 2013 to have never actually published 61 of the papers listed on his CV. Furthermore, it only came to light in 2019 that his 1973 PhD thesis contained a significant number of fabricated facts (Margry, 2020). In 2023, the VU research committee concluded that the professor was guilty of serious scientific misconduct, cheating and self-plagiarism in his publications. Whilst this case provides an extreme example of delays between RM occurring and being discovered and acted upon, it highlights the potential consequences of failing to promptly discover and address RM since the researcher's credibility remained unblemished for his entire academic career lasting several decades, allowing for additional scholarship to build upon the inaccuracies and fraudulent data presented in his work that actually did exist and was subsequently retracted (Bax, 2000).

In another case from the Netherlands, a cognitive psychology researcher was found in 2022 to have committed fraud in at least 15 publications by the University of Leiden's Scientific Integrity Committee. This follows accusations of fraud and clinical research ethics violations dating to 2019 relating to illegally collecting blood samples from research participants. This case highlights the **potential harms that can occur to human research participants when RM in clinical research settings goes undiscovered**, or there is a delay in reporting or a protracted investigation period over multiple years. In addition to these matters, the researcher in question was suspected of tampering with grant applications and removing other authors' names from reports (NL Times, 2022). This highlights the contextual link between RM and competition over limited funding. Weak or delayed reporting and enforcement mechanisms can potentially incentivise researchers to commit RM. Research has shown that the perception of being 'caught' misbehaving or engaging in questionable behaviour reduces the likelihood of such misbehaviour (Adams & Pimple, 2005; Gopalakrishna et al., 2022).

Another factor correlated with delays in reporting is a **RPO mitigating or covering up whistle-blower allegations** of RM to protect the institution from reputational damage. Whilst this was only evidenced in one case in this review, the ramifications of doing so for REI and public trust in science are significant. In a long-running UK case, University College London (UCL) found that researchers from a lab at UCL run by a prominent professor of genetics, who subsequently became vice-chancellor of another university, had published fraudulent papers with manipulated and falsified data over a number of years. UCL determined in investigations conducted in 2015 and 2018 that the professor running the lab was responsible for committing RM due to running his lab in a reckless manner and adding himself as a co-author to fraudulent publications, although they acknowledge the misconduct on his part was not necessarily deliberate (Aldhous, 2019). However, subsequent UK Freedom of Information Act requests and media investigations from 2020 also uncovered an e-mail between administrators sent in 2007 that showed UCL had hushed up whistle-blower complaints and avoided investigating the professor's lab in order to protect against reputational damage to the university (Aldhous, 2020).

Other cases in this review also demonstrated powerful **research institutions failing to support whistle-blowers**, and in some cases creating a hostile environment against whistle-blowers. In one case in Estonia, the rector of Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech) deliberately ignored and

downplayed a PhD student whistle-blower's reporting on serious financial irregularities in how grant money for European Commission (EC) funded projects was being allocated within the university (ERR News, 2019). In another case in Latvia, a female professor reported in court that she had suffered from academic bullying, which she claimed was possibly retaliation for whistle-blowing in several cases. These included questioning the effects of a registered medicine without sufficient proof and highlighting alleged historical ties between a colleague and the Soviet security services. The court ruled in her favour that unequal treatment in the workplace did occur, but the ruling did not have significant consequences (Feldmanis & Zvirbulus, 2019; Zvirbulus, 2022). However, negative or dismissive behaviour by institutional authorities towards whistle-blowers is not a universal phenomenon, and **RPOs can demonstrate best practice in handling whistle-blower revelations**. In the University of Leiden psychology researcher case described above, the RM was brought to light by three whistle-blowers who reported it to the scientific director of their research institute, who then gathered evidence based on their claims and filed a complaint with the university's Committee on Scientific Integrity, which vindicated the whistle-blowers' claims. However, one of the whistle-blower's stated that they were initially reluctant to join as a named party in a formal complaint due to fear of retaliation (Teller, 2020).

In some instances, there is a clear **political or public interest motivation for investigating and reporting RM**. In Latvia, a judge was discovered to have plagiarized 75% of his 2008 PhD thesis from St. Petersburg State University in Russia by a group of Russian scientific integrity activists called Dissernet, who investigate plagiarism in Russian advanced degrees. The story received attention in the Latvian press in 2021, eventually leading the judge to resign from his post (*Par Daugavpils tiesas tiesneša Arvīda Ozerska atbrīvošanu no tiesneša amata*, 2021) although he continues to be employed as a lecturer in law by Daugavpils University according to their website ('Jūs Meklējāt Ozerskis > Daugavpils Universitāte', n.d.). In a second case from Latvia, a practising public prosecutor was found to have committed plagiarism in his undergraduate dissertation, based on several whistle-blower reports, where one of the whistle-blowers was the accused on a court case upheld by him as a prosecutor. This case received media coverage in 2022 alongside the conclusion of a court battle over whether the degree should be annulled, which eventually ruled in the prosecutor's favour (LETA, 2022).

2.4.2. Gender (including discrimination, sexual harassment, and other forms of gender-based violence)

Gender is often an important aspect in RM and QRP case descriptions. There are many ways in which gender can play a significant role – sexual or gender-based discrimination or even violence; unequal power balances that have consequences for real or perceived reporting barriers and underreporting; or matters might be complicated by gender stereotyping and intersectionality issues. Our case studies highlighted the following ways in which gender can play a critical role.

Gender of the RM or QRP participants matters, as in the Latvian case of discrimination, raised by a prominent female pharmacology professor (Zvirbulus, 2022). Equally, bullying behaviour can be associated with and “normalized” through connecting it to traditional gender roles and stereotypes, as in another Latvian case. There, a prominent guest lecturer's contract was not renewed for the next period, partially due to students' whistle-blowing on him as being disrespectful to women. While the university stood its ground, the public discourse around the issue featured a series of publications in his support, which suggested students were being overly sensitive about the sexist jokes he was making and downplayed the seriousness of his behaviour (Beinerte, 2021; Veidemane, 2021). These examples indicate the tensions around evolving gender-roles and how these larger social trends play out in research communities. The latter case illustrates how students and younger scholars are increasingly challenging the continued perpetuation of traditional gender stereotypes by established researchers in RPOs, especially universities.

A research topic or methodology might have a particular gendered aspect. For example, the Estonian infertility study involved illegal and unethical data collection practices, but the very high media coverage of the story and the very swift reaction of the university involved (responsible person was fired from deanship and professorship) can, at least partly, be attributed to the politically sensitive topic of the research (in/fertility in the context of pro-natalist politics). Personal data of young Estonian women was accessed, and they were asked to participate in a survey regarding their decisions about fertility (including questions “Why do you not have children” sent to 18-year-olds), their sexual habits and experiences (including same sex relationships) and their political preferences (Pärli, 2023a). Interestingly, the survey focused broadly on fertility behaviour but targeted only women. Another important aspect of this case pertains to the politicized research funding – the project was led by a politically funded non-profit that had received the funds directly from the Minister, without any regular peer-review and outside the competition usually associated with research funding.

An example of contentious and provocative research methodology that has a gender aspect involves a research publication by a young scholar in the UK. A PhD student at Manchester University published a short ‘Notes’ piece in the peer reviewed journal *Qualitative Research* on conducting auto-ethnographic research on his experiences of masturbating to Shota, a genre of pornographic Japanese Manga depicting young boys in sexual poses and acts. This was related to his PhD work on Shota carried out at Manchester between 2020-2022. Media controversy followed about 4 months after the publication and the attention from social media as well as print media (Cole, 2022; Powell, 2022), including censure from UK MPs (Bolton, 2022), led to the retraction of the article and instigated changes in the editorial processes and oversight in the journal (Howard, 2022). The case raised questions about the method of auto-ethnography and the kind of research ethical oversight that this type of phenomenological research might require. It also highlights challenging ethical and legal issues surrounding ethics of researching representation of illegal and unethical acts, as well as boundaries of what can be legitimately considered research.

In conclusion, our case studies illustrate the ways in which gender plays a role in RM and QRP. Gender affects the experiences, attitudes and actions of participants and influence how societal norms have an impact on professional conduct within academic environments. The gendered aspect extends to research topics and methodologies, as seen in the Estonian infertility study’s politically sensitive subject and the provocative research methodology employed by a UK scholar. These cases highlight the complexities surrounding evolving gender roles, the persistence of traditional stereotypes in academia, and the need for heightened awareness and ethical considerations in research practices with gender dimensions.

2.4.3. Researcher working conditions

RM and QRPs can significantly influence, and be influenced by, the working conditions of researchers. This impact is occasionally directly associated with whistleblowing or accusations of wrongdoing, while in other cases, the changes may not be explicitly connected, at least in a formal sense. Both parties involved—the accuser and the accused—may face repercussions affecting their working conditions. These consequences range from reduced pay and shortened work hours to the more severe outcome of job loss and extending beyond the immediate context of the allegations. Our cases illustrated that people in senior positions can also face significant repercussions (although media reporting of those cases is also more likely, in comparison to student wrongdoings).

At least one case highlights the negative **implications of precarious funding** for preventing RM and promoting good REI practice. The details of the financial misconduct that occurred in the case from TalTech in Estonia discussed in Section 4.1 were that the Nurkse Institute of Public Administration at

the university siphoned European Union project funds into salaries for researchers by falsifying timetables and working hours. The university's rector was made aware this was taking place from the whistle-blower complaint and deliberately ignored it for at least five months. This misconduct led to criminal proceedings being initiated against the university, and the situation received significant press media coverage of approximately 100 articles in a 2.5-year period. Ultimately the criminal charges were dropped, but the university had to pay back the research money to the EC (close to €100,000; Altosaar, 2022). The corrupt decision-making by senior university administrators in this case was likely caused by institutional funding pressures in the Estonian publicly-funded research sector that relies extensively on competitive research funding.

Early-career researcher (ECR) working conditions are another factor contributing to RM. A significant aspect of the relationship between ECR working conditions and the occurrence of RM is the research culture led by senior researchers in a research team or laboratory. This was made evident in at least one UK case. As noted in section 4.1, in the UCL genetics lab case, the senior academic responsible for running the lab where multiple instances of RM were identified was found to have been "reckless in the conduct of his laboratory" by the university's investigatory panel, which also determined that his co-authorship on a number of papers, including those using fabricated data "facilitated misconduct" (Sample, 2019). Furthermore, a mid-career researcher in the lab responsible for falsifying information in publication figures on papers in which the head of the lab was a co-author had attempted to pass the blame for misconduct down the academic hierarchy to junior researchers (Aldhous, 2020).

The above case also highlights a related phenomenon that is becoming increasingly frequent, which is the **responsibility of senior researchers for the misconduct of the junior and mid-ranking researchers they manage**. In another case from the Netherlands, a research team from the Delft University of Technology (TU Delft) published an article in the journal *Nature* claiming to have experimentally observed Majorana particles – a theoretical particle that is not charged nor has any mass – which can be significant in the development of quantum computers. However, the article's conclusions were subsequently demonstrated to be incorrect and irreproducible. The journal officially retracted the article in 2021 on the grounds of errors in the data analysis (Zhang et al., 2021), and another article involving the same authors was retracted between 2020 (Gazibegovic et al., 2022). An investigation by the Netherlands Board on Research Integrity found the researchers to have been "negligent" and to have breached three basic principles of the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (KNAW et al., 2018): 'honesty and scrupulousness', 'transparency', and 'responsibility,' but had not deliberately committed RM. The investigation placed primary responsibility on the first author, who was a doctoral student, but also determined that a senior researcher who was both the corresponding author for the paper, and the first author's PhD supervisor bears "full responsibility." LOWI's findings also determined that TU Delft should state clear rules and record agreements so that research supervisors "can carry out their responsibility adequately and if necessary can be addressed on it" in order to obviate a lack of clarity about the extent to which senior researchers' are ultimately responsible for the conduct of junior researchers under their supervision (Bonger, 2022; LOWI, 2022).

Finally, another case from the Netherlands demonstrates how **ECRs are in a structurally more precarious position** than their more senior colleagues and institutional administrators, making them vulnerable to institutional pressures and abuses of power. Here, in 2019 a PhD student at the University of Maastricht accused a cardiology professor – who was her supervisor at the time – of manipulating images and embellishing several subsidy applications. The student whistle-blew to the Commission for Scientific Integrity about the matter in July 2019, and as a result was subsequently denied access to the laboratory to conduct her research. This resulted in a labour relations dispute between the student

and the university that was adjudicated in the Dutch Courts, which ruled in favour of the university on the grounds that the student was no longer able to carry out their work without a PhD supervisor. However, the PhD student eventually reached an agreement with the university and was able to complete her studies under new supervisors (Maastricht University, 2020).

2.4.4. Other novel and significant findings

Whilst **the politicization of research** is not, in principle, a novel phenomenon, it has certainly become a more commonplace one, particularly in relation to topics that are sensitive or are flashpoints of public controversy. An example of this is how gender-related research concerning clinical practices and REI around the highly sensitive topic of gender dysphoria came under scrutiny in the UK in a politicized way. An investigation by the BBC's *Newsnight* current affairs programme found that a prominent UK gender dysphoria clinic lowered the age at which it would provide children puberty blockers based on information from a study started in 2011 that later came under scrutiny (Cohen & Barnes, 2019). Critics argued that the study has significant flaws both in terms of RI and RE. The lack of a control group in the study meant that it was impossible for researchers to tell whether there was a causal relationship between some participants' reporting thoughts of self-harm and suicide (caused by the hormone-blockers being trialled), despite claims by the researchers that there was no meaningful correlation. Ethical concerns were also raised about participants' capacity to consent (as they were underaged), long-term health risks and degree of informed consent in alternative and later approaches to medical transitioning (Wilkinson & Savulescu, 2019). Later, the UK Health Research Authority cleared the study of wrongdoing (Health Research Authority, 2019). Although the UK High Court ruled in 2020 that under 16s are unlikely to have capacity to give informed consent for puberty blockers (BBC News, 2020; *Bell & Anor v The Tavistock And Portman NHS Foundation Trust*, 2020), a later Court of Appeal decision overturned this in 2021 (*Bell & Anor v The Tavistock And Portman NHS Foundation Trust and others*, 2021; Brooks, 2023). This case highlights the issues that frequently characterize the politicization of research findings, encompassing various aspects such as their clinical applications and outcomes, the ongoing debates surrounding public acceptance of controversial treatments, and the hesitance of certain researchers and clinicians to openly question or express their views, driven by the fear of being accused of transphobia (Brooks, 2023).

Equally intriguing is the Estonian fertility study, which situated a research topic (fertility and birth rates in Estonia) within a highly politicized framework. This context was shaped by pro-natalist debates and policy measures, framed as imperative for the preservation of the Estonian nation and culture. Additionally, the research received targeted funding from a foundation affiliated with a political party, adding another layer of political influence to the study (Pärli, 2023b).

Reporting with political or public interest dimensions is increasingly likely to take place through public discourse on social media platforms such as Twitter (now X). This is demonstrated in a 2023 case from the UK in which Civitas – an influential think tank that has been described in the media as right-wing (Bawden, 2016; Manley, 2019) and has been criticized by public interest researchers for lack of transparency (Mureithi, 2022) – published a report claiming the cost of achieving net zero carbon emissions in the UK would cost £4.5tn (Sabey, 2023). Following criticism on Twitter of the methodology and analysis used to make this claim, Civitas subsequently retracted the report several days later stating that there were factual errors with the report, and it was undergoing a fresh peer review process (Stewart, 2023). These errors were due to the incorrect calculations due to the author's confusion of units used to measure cost of electricity generation versus power capacity and confusing billions with trillions in calculations. However, prior to the retraction the erroneous figure received press coverage in several major UK media outlets including the Sun, Daily Mail and the Times (Carrington, 2023). Surrounding this report is a policy context in which the UK government has delayed the deadline for achieving Net Zero from 2030 to 2050, and the issue of green energy transition

has become an increasingly polarized partisan issue with the PM claiming an ostensible “war on motorists” as a wedge issue ahead of impending UK elections (Sky News, 2023).

The globalization and internationalization of research raise questions about the governance of information related to RM and QRPs. This review uncovered two examples – both from the UK – in which researchers who have been found to commit RM and dismissed obtained employment in another country without being held accountable for their actions or corrective action to prevent the recurrence of REI breaches. In one case a postdoctoral researcher who admitted to manipulating research images in publications, for which the senior researcher running the lab was also held responsible, left UCL in 2013 to the European University Cyprus, and became deputy dean of the School of Medicine there (Rose, 2020). Likewise, another professor – whose position at Imperial College London was terminated for RM following an independent investigation relating to falsified and manipulated data in a paper of which he was a co-author – is now a visiting professor of oncology at Sun-Yat Sen University in Guangzhou, China (Marcus, 2021).

Another noteworthy avenue for discovering and reporting RM is **the work of voluntary investigators**, particularly on the internet platform PubPeer (<https://pubpeer.com>), which allows users to anonymously review and critique publications in the literature across a wide range of fields, including to find discrepancies and flawed research. PubPeer played a significant role in discovering and drawing attention to actions of RM in three of the cases reviewed, two from the UK (Marcus, 2021; Owens, 2015) and one from the Netherlands (Marcus, 2020). This includes the UCL genetics lab case, in which 25 papers from this professor's lab were investigated and suspected RM has been indicated, including image manipulation of figures, including a 2005 paper that came under scrutiny in 2014 (Oransky, 2015). Likewise, another case from the UK professor in oncology who ran a lab at Imperial College London (ICL), was terminated from his position at ICL following an independent investigation that found he had committed RM in relation to falsified and manipulated data in a subsequently retracted 2018 paper from the Nature journal Cell Death and Disease, of which he was a co-author. However, evidence of alleged data manipulation has been presented on PubPeer from 2018 onwards relating to a number of this professor's co-authored publications dating back to 2003 (Marcus, 2021). In 2015, a “data sleuth” posted concerns on PubPeer about image manipulation in a 2007 article written by researchers at the Hubrecht Institute in the Netherlands in the high-impact journal Science whose senior author was a prominent oncology researcher and former Dutch government minister (Marcus, 2020). The article was eventually retracted by Science in 2020 (Sills, 2020).

2.5. Conclusions

2.5.1. Discussion of Significant Findings

This report has illustrated several important issues concerning the practical implications and impacts of RM, and the multiple and complex challenges of managing REI issues in practice. These issues cut across multiple areas including reporting and whistle-blowing, gender and sexuality, researcher working conditions and the movement of researchers between institutions and countries. The report also identified novel findings relating to these areas, and other areas that were not included in the BEYOND GA including the role of technology and social media in shaping the contemporary REI environment, and the increased politicisation of REI concerns as an aspect of the broader contemporary pattern of political polarisation influencing scientific practice.

The case studies analysed relating to **reporting and whistle-blowing** affirm that mechanisms for reporting are often weak and not formal enough to ensure robust action to halt RM, and that in some cases it can be in an institution's interest to not address cases of RM. Likewise, even when legal and protections and norms to protect whistle-blowers exist, they do not necessarily protect whistle-blowers in practice. This can contribute to potential whistle-blowers feeling intimidated or afraid of repercussions, which has a chilling effect on reporting and reducing RM. However, there are also some examples in which institutions demonstrate best practice in supporting whistle-blowers, and investigating their allegations in a serious and considered way (Teller, 2020). These examples should be evaluated for 'lessons learnt' that can be adapted in other institutional contexts, and promoted as a model for other institutions to emulate.

There has been a shift in **gender-related considerations** within RM and QRP. Previously, the predominant focus was on the gender of implicated researchers and often the crux of the matter was linked to (traditional) gender roles and the changing expectations, practices and associations around those roles. We now increasingly witness how research foci, topics and methods with a particular gendered angle become sensitive and consequently develop into REI issues. This applies, perhaps not surprisingly, directly to topics around sexuality (as, within our study exemplified by masturbation as a method case (Cole, 2022) but also to issues with a particular gendered focus, as in the Estonian fertility study case (Pärli, 2023) or the UK gender dysphoria clinical care case (Cohen & Barnes, 2019).

Several broader trends that are emerging in the REI field were identified in this review. There is currently an increasing trend of **senior researchers being held responsible** for the culture and behaviours that occur in the research teams they manage by both institutions and external REI advisory and adjudication bodies. Alongside this, is an impetus towards developing clearer accountability structures to define senior researchers' roles in managing the junior researchers that work with them, and to hold senior researchers' responsible for RM that occurs in the teams they supervise. Issues regarding failures of leadership either in preventing RM, or being oblivious to RM occurring in their team, is likely a product of the combined pressures on senior researchers that underscore an expectation that 'more is always better.' A notable example of this problem that was illustrated in our review is the UK genetics professor case, where a junior researcher evidently lacked supervision and oversight that resulted in fabricated and manipulated data and fraudulent publications for the entire research group. Senior researchers not only grapple with the imperative to conduct high-quality research, but also face multiple competing responsibilities to oversee large teams, consistently secure funding, and assuming various administrative and advisory roles. This culture of expectation places a significant burden on senior researchers, and numerous recent REI scandals have highlighted the difficulties senior researchers face in coping with the growing quantity and seriousness of demands and expectations in

their roles. This highlights the need to reevaluate academic expectations to ensure a sustainable and supportive research environment to enable better REI outcomes.

Another emerging challenge relates to the **timescales of RM reporting and investigation** in a world mediated by digital technology and rapid information flows. REI investigations tend to have particular temporal aspects – they often take very long time as balance is thought between transparency, objectivity, fairness and thoroughness. In the past, often RM cases have been uncovered that trace back several decades. Given the increasingly accessible data analytic possibilities (plagiarism software, large language models etc), it is likely that there will be more instances of past misconduct uncovered and more actors who are able to do that (although uncovering certain types of RM requires very specific scientific skills). This could especially affect more senior and prominent researchers as their increased public profile will encourage attract greater scholarly and public interest, which is more likely to uncover any potential issues regarding the integrity and standards of their research. This temporal aspect is affected by **novel social media and research platforms** that play an increasing role in situations involving RM and QRPs. They provide space for whistleblowing and discussing and sharing about REI issues. The activities there also pile new pressures on researchers and institutions, aided by online media, to accelerate the decisions and make REI investigations more transparent. This creates tensions with the traditional REI processes, the deliberative nature of academia. Confidentiality obligations affect what kind of information can be made available to the public.

The escalating **politicization of research** has become a recurring theme in contemporary REI discourse, a trend that is influenced by the increasing role of social media as a platform for public discourses on REI. The influence of these dynamics on public trust in science is serious, as the lines between objective inquiry and political priorities and allegiance blur. Additionally, the political stakes associated with RM have become more visible, manifesting in the strategic deployment of evidence to either support or counter specific political positions. Debates over scientific evidence during the COVID-19 crisis is an excellent example of this (Druckman, 2022).

2.5.2. Recommendations

This review exercise has highlighted the methodological challenges in obtaining qualitatively detailed data on case studies of RM. To better monitor cases of RM for transparency, as an evidence base for REI research, and to inform policymaking around REI, a good first step would be for European (and global) RIO to develop repositories or databases to gather and analyse case study data on incidents of RM. Alongside this, it would be highly beneficial for RIOs, possibly through an organisation such as ENRIO, to develop **an interoperable rubric for reporting case studies that includes criteria that facilitate qualitative depth**. Such a rubric might include a narrative summary for each case, standardized codes for RM categories, key dates of events and reporting, relevant discipline or commercial area, the context for the misconduct (journal, lab, grant application etc.), how the misconduct was discovered and reported, and any outcomes from the case. Having this rubric that can be shared and implemented with relative ease by individual RIOs will both encourage the adoption of reporting systems, and allow for straightforward comparative analyses to be carried out both along thematic lines and across national and regional groupings. This methodological approach to REI reporting would allow for clearer analytical understanding of the relationship between individual and systemic factors that contribute to RM, and to better formulate holistic mitigation strategies to address these factors.

Globalization of research, in terms of ideas, fora and researchers raises, the question of whether investigations of RMs and QRPs should globalise as well. For example, information regarding RM and QRPs could be governed at an international level (for example, by RFOs or networks of REI actors like national RI offices), and **information-sharing and reporting mechanisms could be**

implemented at the international level to ensure that research misconduct cannot be exported or simply displaced. On the one hand, those who have made serious mistakes need to be held accountable, on the other hand pathways to rehabilitation and reintegration should be made available, transparent and trustworthy. Addressing this challenge is complex since the presence of media and social media platforms places **a duty of care incumbent upon hiring institutions to conduct due diligence** work to prevent researchers with a history of committing RM continuing to do so elsewhere but often even official misconduct reviews are confidential and well hidden within institutional edifices.

The implications for the REI landscape of the increasing emphasis on the responsibility of senior researchers for RM that occurs in the research teams they manage suggests the need for a shift within institutional research cultures towards **inculcating a different culture of responsibility that reduces pressures on senior scientists by enabling them to engage in ‘slower science.’ This would give senior scientists more time to properly mentor junior researchers in the principles and practical aspects of research ethics** to reduce the risk of RM occurring in the teams they manage. This strategy orients towards a blame-free approach that empowers researchers in relation to institutional and regulatory contexts in which they operate (Bouter, 2018). This is important when considering the power relations inherent to the institutional context of research in which junior researchers both learn from senior researchers, and depend on them for job security and professional advancement. In contrast, an approach that places shared responsibility or blame on junior researchers for RM that occurs in their research teams would ultimately be detrimental to mitigating RM. Junior researchers would be reluctant to act if they were held directly responsible for addressing research misconduct that occurs within their team due to well-placed fears of professional repercussions.

Finally, the study has identified gaps in case study data in several thematic areas, which would benefit from further research. These areas were identified as being of interest in the BEYOND project GA, but the research team was unable to find relevant case studies for these themes in our research. However, this should be caveated by the fact that both the sample size of cases and geographical spread of the review were somewhat limited. One area that would merit further case study investigation is the **relationship between researchers’ mental health and wellbeing and RM**, as it is a reasonable hypothesis to draw that there is a meaningful relationship between them (Limas et al., 2022). Another area of interest identified in the BEYOND GA that the research team were unable to uncover any evidence about in the case studies gathered and evaluated is the extent to which formal **rehabilitation and reintegration mechanisms for researchers found to have committed RM** exist within Europe, as well as how they might operate and their efficacy. Addressing and monitoring this through multilateral engagement at the institutional, practitioner and policy levels can help to mitigate the deleterious consequences of RM for those found to have committed it, and to redress some of harm to individuals created by the adverse structural and systemic factors that influence RM.

2.6. References

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APPENDIX A: PRISMA DIAGRAMS AND SEARCH DATA

1.3.1. Behavioural and Organisational Ethics

Search date:	Database:	Search terms	Results	Relevant title / abstract
28 February 2023	University of Edinburgh Library	“Research misconduct” “bad apple”	71	1 (possibly more)
31 March 2023	Google scholar	Behavioural ethics to promote research integrity	14	1
31 March 2023	Google scholar	“organisational ethics” and “research integrity”	19	2
31 March 2023	Google scholar	“institutional ethics” and “research misconduct”	246	46

1.3.2. Moral psychology related to the promotion of REI and breaches of these standards

Search date:	Database:	Search words	Results	Relevant title / abstract
15 February 2023	Google scholar	“Moral psychology” and “research integrity”	328	1 (possibly more)
15 February 2023	Google search	“Moral psychology” and “research misconduct”		1
17 March 2023	Google search	Whistleblowing “academic misconduct”	32	1

Search date:	Database:	Search words:	Results	Relevant title,/abstract
12 April 2023	Web of science	“Moral factors” “moral psychology” “planned behaviour” “research integrity” “research ethics” “research misconduct” “plagiarism” “falsification”	42	26
12 April 2023	PubMed Ovid	“Moral factors” “moral psychology” “planned behaviour” “research integrity” “research ethics” “research misconduct” “plagiarism” “falsification”		

1.3.3. Opportunities and challenges in the public and private sectors (including SMEs)

Search date:	Database:	Search words:	Results:	Relevant title/abstract:
15 February y 2023	Google scholar	“Research misconduct” and “private sector”		1
15 February y 2023	University of Edinburgh library	“Research integrity” “private sector”		1
15 March 2023	Google Scholar	“research misconduct”; “private sector”	963	1 (possibly more)
22 March 2023	Google Scholar	“research integrity”; “private sector”	145	0
22 March 2023	Google search	“Research integrity in the private sector”		1
22 March 2023	PubMed	(Research misconduct) and (Private sector)	9	0
31 March 2023	Google scholar	“Behavioural ethics” and “research integrity”	14	1

1.3.4. Personal and institutional responsibilities for the promotion of REI

Search date:	Database:	Search words:	Results:	Relevant title/abstract:
15 February 2023	Google search	Moral psychology and “research integrity”		1 (possibly more)
28 February 2023	University of Edinburgh Library	“Research misconduct” “responsibility”	1,141	1 (possibly more)
17 March 2023	Google scholar	Whistleblowing “academic misconduct”	32	2
17 March 2023	University of Edinburgh library	“research misconduct” “rehabilitation”	101	1
31 March 2023	Google scholar	“institutional responsibility” “research misconduct”	79	16
31 March 2023	Google scholar	“researcher responsibility” “research integrity”	87	2

1.3.5. Questions related to the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers

Search date:	Database:	Search words	Results	Relevant title / abstract
15 February 2023	University of Edinburgh library	“research misconduct” “rehabilitation”	101	3
28 February 2023	University of Edinburgh Library	“Research misconduct” rehabilitation	157	2
28 February 2023	Google scholar	“Research misconduct” reintegration	4	1
28 February 2023	Google scholar	Whistleblowing “research misconduct”	456	2
15 March 2023	Google scholar	Rehabilitating researchers after misconduct	1,400	13
15 March 2023	PubMed	A typology of scientific misconduct	2	1
17 March 2023	Google scholar	Rehabilitate “research misconduct”	138	2
17 March 2023	Google scholar	“rehabilitate” “plagiarism”	44	1
17 March 2023	Google scholar	“academic misconduct”; “rehabilitation”	25	0

1.3.6. Researchers' mental health and well-being in relation to research misconduct (including those employed in uncertain work conditions)

Search date	Database	Search words	Number of publications; Criteria: last 10 years; peerreviewed; article; duplicate deletion	After screening the title/abstract; double (already in reference shortlist)	After reading full text, first time	After analysing text
27 febr 2023	Google scholar (review articles; last 10 Years)	researchers mental wellbeing; researchers' mental wellbeing effect on questionable research		1		
	Erasmus Univeristy library	kw:(mental health) AND kw:(academia) AND kf:(research misconduct)	2	1		
		kf:(mental health) AND kf:(academia) AND kf:(research misconduct)	12	0		
1 march 2023	Erasmus University Library	fc:(researchers' mental health and well-being) AND ti:(research misconduct) OR ti:(questionable research practice)	8	0		
		ti:(researchers' mental health and well-being)	277; peer reviewed only 3	0		
		ti:(researchers) AND ti:(academia) AND kw:(work conditions) AND kw:(research)	12	1		
	Google scholar	work conditions		0		

		academia researchers' misconduct				
	Erasmus University Library	misconduct) OR kf:(reasons for questionable research practice) AND ti:(academia)	106	0		
9 March 2023	University of Humanistic Studies Library; Web of Science	Ab:Power relations*; Topic: research misconduct*	16	0		
	University of Humanistic Studies Library; Web of Science	AB: researchers well-being; T: research misconduct	3	0		
	Journal: Accountability in Research	mental health researchers	43	2		
	Erasmus University Library	Ti(Power misuse in academia)	1	0		
		ti:(power imbalance) AND ti:(academia)	5	0		
		kw:(questionable research practice) AND ti:(reasons)	16	0		
		kw:(questionable research practice) AND ti:(stress)	40	0		
total			540	5	4	

1.3.7. Gender dimensions and power relations in the context of research misconduct

Search date	Database	Search words	Number of publications; Criteria: last 10 years; peerreviewed; duplicate deletion	After screening title; double (already in reference short list)	In reference list (found in other article)	After reading abstract	After reading full text
30 Jan 2023	Erasmus University Library	(kw: power misuse) AND (ti: academia)	15	2			
6 Febr 2023	Erasmus University Library	(kw: research organisations) AND (kw: gender) AND (kw: research misconduct)	7	1	2		
		(kw: power relations) AND (ti: academia)	148	3			
	Google scholar	“Literature review” “questionable research practice” “PhD students”	24	1			
7 Febr 2023	Erasmus University Library	(ti: research integrity) AND (ti: qualitative)	209	8			
		Female in academic boundaries	164	1			
		Female in academia research misconduct	15	2			

13 Febr 2023	Erasmus University Library	(kw: research misconduct) OR (kw: questionable research practice) AND (kw: work conditions) OR	300	22			
		(kw: power relations) AND (ti: academia)					
15 Febr 2023	Erasmus University Library	(kf: research organisation) AND (kf: power misuse) AND (ti: research misconduct)	No articles. Handbook of research on academic misconduct in Higher Education (2017)				
	Erasmus University Library	kf:(students) AND kf:(research misconduct)	333	11			
16 Febr 2023	Journal of Academic Ethics	'power abuse'	71	6			
	Springer Link	'gender misuse academia'	61 Result(s) used filter: Article, Ethics	2			
23 Febr 2023	Google scholar	influence of power relations in research misconduct					
Total			1.347	59	2	23	10

1.3.8. Research on the effectiveness of research ethics and integrity training

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

Search date:	Database:	Search terms	Results	Relevant title / abstract
March 2023	WoS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • research ethics * (academic) (research) integrity • training * education * course * • (measurement of) training effect * evaluation of training * assessment of learning 	124	15
March 2023	Scopus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • research ethics * (academic) (research) integrity • training * education * course * • (measurement of) training effect * evaluation of training * assessment of learning 	21	2
March 2023	Other (snowballing)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • research ethics * (academic) (research) integrity • training * education * course * • (measurement of) training effect * evaluation of training * assessment of learning 	29	14

1.3.9. Case-based methodologies

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases, registers and other sources

*Consider, if feasible to do so, reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched (rather than the total number across all databases/registers).
 **If automation tools were used, indicate how many records were excluded by a human and how many were excluded by automation tools.

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

Search date:	Database:	Search words:	Results:	Relevant title/abstract:
15 February 2023	Google search	Moral psychology and “research integrity”		1 (possibly more)
March 10th, 13th, 14th 2023	Google Scholar	"case based" AND research misconduct AND “ethics instruction”	511	20 (possibly more)
March 15th 2023	Google Scholar	“research misconduct” AND ethics instruction intitle:"casebased"	10	0
March 15th 2023	Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY(case-based), PUBYEAR AFT 2008, AND research misconduct AND ("ethics training" OR "ethics education" OR "research integrity")	15	3
March 15th 2023	Scopus	"case based" AND research misconduct AND ethics instruction	61	2

March 16th 2023	Embassy of Good Science: Education	N/A	250	2
March 16th 2023	Web of Science	(AB=(case-based)) AND ALL=(research integrity)	61	0
March 17th 2023	Google Scholar	Citation search: Citing Antes et al 2009	236	6
March 19th, 20th 2023	Google Scholar	"research integrity instruction" OR "research integrity training" OR "research integrity education"	581	0 (possibly more)

March 20th 2023	Academic Search Complete	("case-based" OR "case deliberation") AND ("research integrity" OR "research misconduct")	5	0
March 20th 2023	Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY (case AND deliberation AND research AND integrity)	11	1
Search date:	Database:	Search words:	Results:	Relevant title/abstract:
15 February 2023	Google search	Moral psychology and “research integrity”		1 (possibly more)
March 10th, 13th, 14th 2023	Google Scholar	"case based" AND research misconduct AND “ethics instruction”	511	20 (possibly more)
March 15th 2023	Google Scholar	“research misconduct” AND ethics instruction intitle:"casebased"	10	0
March 15th 2023	Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY(case-based), PUBYEAR AFT 2008, AND research misconduct AND ("ethics training" OR "ethics education" OR "research integrity")	15	3
March 15th 2023	Scopus	"case based" AND research misconduct AND ethics instruction	61	2
March 16th 2023	Embassy of Good Science: Education	N/A	250	2
March 16th 2023	Web of Science	(AB=(case-based)) AND ALL=(research integrity)	61	0
March 17th 2023	Google Scholar	Citation search: Citing Antes et al 2009	236	6

March 19th, 20th 2023	Google Scholar	"research integrity instruction" OR "research integrity training" OR "research integrity education"	581	0 (possibly more)
March 20th 2023	Academic Search Complete	("case-based" OR "case deliberation") AND ("research integrity" OR "research misconduct")	5	0
March 20th 2023	Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY (case AND deliberation AND research AND integrity)	11	1

APPENDIX B: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

1.3.1. Behavioural and Organisational Ethics

Total number of articles included (n)
37

Articles by publication year:

Year	Articles Published
2013	1
2014	4
2015	1
2016	2
2017	4
2018	2
2019	6
2020	2
2021	9
2022	3
2023	3

Methodology:

	Total	Survey	Case Study	Interviews/Focus Groups	Lit. Review (academic)	Documentary analysis	Stakeholder Engagement/Participatory Design
Qualitative	22						
<i>Primary</i>	11	0	1	4		5	
<i>Secondary</i>	11	0	3	0	7		
Quantitative	11						
<i>Primary</i>	10	9	0	0	0	1	
<i>Secondary</i>	1	0	0	0	1		
Mixed	4						
<i>Primary</i>	3	3	0	0	0	0	
<i>Secondary</i>	1	0	0	0	1	0	

Disciplinary focus of research:

Disciplinary Category	Number of Articles
<i>Agricultural Sciences*</i>	0
<i>Biology & Biochemistry*</i>	0
<i>Chemistry*</i>	0
<i>Clinical Medicine*</i>	11
<i>Computer Science*</i>	0
<i>Engineering*</i>	0
<i>Environment/Ecology*</i>	0
<i>Geosciences*</i>	0
<i>Immunology*</i>	0
<i>Materials Science*</i>	0
<i>Mathematics*</i>	0
<i>Microbiology*</i>	0
<i>Molecular Biology & Genetics*</i>	0
<i>Neuroscience & Behavior*</i>	0
<i>Pharmacology & Toxicology*</i>	0
<i>Physics*</i>	1
<i>Plant & Animal Science*</i>	0
<i>Psychiatry/Psychology*</i>	1
<i>Space Science*</i>	0
<i>Architecture, Building & Planning†</i>	0
<i>Social Studies†</i>	1
<i>Law†</i>	0
<i>Business & Administrative Studies†</i>	1
<i>Mass Communications & Documentation†</i>	0
<i>Languages†</i>	0
<i>Historical & Philosophical Studies†</i>	0
<i>Creative Arts & Design†</i>	0
<i>Education†</i>	0
<i>Multidisciplinary*</i>	17
<i>Practitioner‡</i>	5

* adapted from Web of Science ESI Classifications

† adapted from HESA JACS 3.0 Classifications

‡ ad-hoc category based on study requirements

Geographical focus:

NA/no country	Multicountry	Japan	Nigeria	Iran	Croatia	Australia	Benin	Brazil	USA	India	Belgium	Thailand
12	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8	5	1	1

Theoretical Approach:

Stated	Not-stated
2	35
specific approach (if stated)	number of articles
<i>Systems approach^a</i>	1
<i>Deviance theory^b</i>	1
<i>Bifurcation theory^b</i>	1

^aCapaldi 2021

^bHesselmann et. al. 2017

1.3.2. Moral psychology related to the promotion of REI and breaches of these standards

Total number of articles included (n)
23

Articles by publication year:

Year	Articles Published
2013	1
2014	0
2015	1
2016	2
2017	1
2018	3
2019	0
2020	3
2021	2
2022	8
2023	2

Methodology:

	Total	Survey	Case Study	Interviews/Focus Groups	Lit. Review (academic)	Documentary analysis	Stakeholder Engagement/Participatory Design
Qualitative	5						
<i>Primary</i>	4	0	0	2	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Quantitative	17						
<i>Primary</i>	17	17	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mixed	1						
<i>Primary</i>	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

* adapted from Web of Science ESI Classifications

† adapted from HESA JACS 3.0 Classifications

‡ ad-hoc category based on study requirements

Disciplinary focus of research:

Disciplinary Category	Number of Articles
<i>Agricultural Sciences*</i>	0
<i>Biology & Biochemistry*</i>	0
<i>Chemistry*</i>	0
<i>Clinical Medicine*/medical sciences</i>	2
<i>Computer Science*</i>	0
<i>Engineering*</i>	1
<i>Environment/Ecology*</i>	0
<i>Geosciences*</i>	0
<i>Immunology*</i>	0
<i>Materials Science*</i>	0
<i>Mathematics*</i>	0
<i>Microbiology*</i>	0
<i>Molecular Biology & Genetics*</i>	0
<i>Neuroscience & Behavior*</i>	0
<i>Pharmacology & Toxicology*</i>	0
<i>Physics*</i>	0
<i>Plant & Animal Science*</i>	0
<i>Psychiatry/Psychology (multidisciplinary)*</i>	3
<i>Space Science*</i>	0
<i>Architecture, Building & Planning†</i>	0
<i>Social Studies†</i>	0
<i>Law†</i>	0
<i>Business & Administrative Studies†</i>	2
<i>Mass Communications & Documentation†</i>	0
<i>Languages†</i>	0
<i>Historical & Philosophical Studies†</i>	0
<i>Creative Arts & Design†</i>	0
<i>Education†</i>	2
<i>Multidisciplinary*</i>	13
<i>Practitioner‡</i>	0

Geographical focus:

NA /no country	Mu lti-cou ntry	Aus tralia	Canada	USA	Singapore	Indonesia	Taiwan	Iran	India	Jordan	Tha iland	Turk ey	China	Pakistan	Oman
0	1	4	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1

Theoretical Approach:

Stated	Not-stated
0	1
specific approach (if stated)	number of articles
<i>Extended Theory of planned behaviour</i>	17
<i>Self-efficacy and self-control</i>	0
<i>Social cognitive theory</i>	1
<i>Moral foundation theory</i>	0
<i>Big five theory & ethical ideology</i>	1
<i>Situated decision-making model</i>	1
<i>Ethical decision making</i>	1
<i>Moral licencing</i>	1

1.3.3. Opportunities and challenges in the public and private sectors (including SMEs)

Total number of articles included (n)
2

Articles by Publication Year

Year	Articles Published
2013	0
2014	0
2015	0
2016	0
2017	0
2018	0
2019	0
2020	0
2021	1
2022	1
2023	0

Methodology:

	Total	Survey	Case Study	Interviews/Focus Groups	Lit. Review (academic)	Documentary analysis	Stakeholder Engagement/Participatory Design	Other
Qualitative	2							
<i>Primary</i>	2	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Quantitative	0							
<i>Primary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mixed	0							
<i>Primary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Disciplinary focus of research:

Disciplinary Category	Number of Articles
<i>Agricultural Sciences*</i>	1
<i>Biology & Biochemistry*</i>	0
<i>Chemistry*</i>	0
<i>Clinical Medicine*</i>	0
<i>Computer Science*</i>	0
<i>Engineering*</i>	0
<i>Environment/Ecology*</i>	0
<i>Geosciences*</i>	0
<i>Immunology*</i>	0
<i>Materials Science*</i>	0
<i>Mathematics*</i>	0
<i>Microbiology*</i>	0
<i>Molecular Biology & Genetics*</i>	0
<i>Neuroscience & Behavior*</i>	0
<i>Pharmacology & Toxicology*</i>	0
<i>Physics*</i>	0
<i>Plant & Animal Science*</i>	0
<i>Psychiatry/Psychology*</i>	0
<i>Space Science*</i>	0
<i>Social Studies†</i>	1
<i>Education†</i>	0
<i>Architecture Building & Planning†</i>	0
<i>Business & Administrative Studies†</i>	0
<i>Creative Arts & Design†</i>	0
<i>Historical & Philosophical Studies†</i>	0
<i>Languages†</i>	0
<i>Law†</i>	0
<i>Mass Communications & Documentation†</i>	0
<i>Multidisciplinary*</i>	0
<i>Practitioner‡</i>	0

* adapted from Web of Science ESI Classifications

† adapted from HESA JACS 3.0 Classifications

‡ ad-hoc category based on study requirements

Geographical focus:

NA/no country	Multi-country	Norway
0	1	1

Theoretical Approach:

Stated	Not-stated
0	2

1.3.4. Personal and institutional responsibilities for the promotion of REI

Total number of articles included (n)
26

Articles by publication year:

Year	Articles Published
2013	2
2014	3
2015	1
2016	3
2017	2
2018	0
2019	3
2020	3
2021	3
2022	4
2023	2

Methodology:

	Total	Survey	Case Study	Interviews/Focus Groups	Lit. Review (academic)	Documentary analysis	Stakeholder Engagement/Participatory Design	Other
Qualitative	18							
<i>Primary</i>	13	2	2	3	0	7	1	1
<i>Secondary</i>	5	0	1	0	3	1	0	0
Quantitative	4							
<i>Primary</i>	3	1	0	0	0	2	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Mixed	4							
<i>Primary</i>	3	2	0	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0

Disciplinary focus of research:

Disciplinary Category	Number of Articles
<i>Agricultural Sciences*</i>	0
<i>Biology & Biochemistry*</i>	0
<i>Chemistry*</i>	1
<i>Clinical Medicine*</i>	7
<i>Computer Science*</i>	0

<i>Engineering*</i>	0
<i>Environment/Ecology*</i>	0
<i>Geosciences*</i>	0
<i>Immunology*</i>	0
<i>Materials Science*</i>	0
<i>Mathematics*</i>	0
<i>Microbiology*</i>	0
<i>Molecular Biology & Genetics*</i>	0
<i>Neuroscience & Behavior*</i>	0
<i>Pharmacology & Toxicology*</i>	0
<i>Physics*</i>	0
<i>Plant & Animal Science*</i>	0
<i>Psychiatry/Psychology*</i>	1
<i>Space Science*</i>	0
<i>Social Studies†</i>	0
<i>Education†</i>	0
<i>Architecture Building & Planning†</i>	0
<i>Business & Administrative Studies†</i>	0
<i>Creative Arts & Design†</i>	0
<i>Historical & Philosophical Studies†</i>	0
<i>Languages†</i>	0
<i>Law†</i>	0
<i>Mass Communications & Documentation†</i>	0
<i>Multidisciplinary*</i>	15
<i>Practitioner‡</i>	2

* adapted from Web of Science ESI Classifications

† adapted from HESA JACS 3.0 Classifications

‡ ad-hoc category based on study requirements

Geographical focus:

NA/no country	Multico untry	USA	France	Turkey	Netherlands	Croatia	Spain	Canada	China
13	2	6	1	1	3	1	1	1	1

Theoretical Approach:

Stated	Not-stated
7	19
specific approach (if stated)	number of articles
<i>Cultural Dimensions Theory</i> ^a	1
<i>Institutional Isomorphism</i> ^b	1
<i>Cognitive Dissonance</i> ^c	1
<i>Institutional Corruption Theory</i> ^c	1
<i>Kantian Ethics</i> ^d	1
<i>Normative Stakeholder Theory</i> ^d	1
<i>Epistemic Culture</i> ^{e.f}	2
<i>Social Practice Theory</i> ^f	1
<i>Empirical Ethics</i> ^g	1
<i>Social Control Theory</i> ^g	1

^a Huybers et. al. 2021 ^b Jacobs 2021 ^c Kahr et. al. 2019 ^d Urbanovič and Tauginienė 2013 ^e Valkenberg et. al. 2020 ^f Valkenberg et. al. 2021
^g Vie 2020

3.5. Questions related to the rehabilitation and reintegration of researchers

Total number of articles included (n)
2

Articles by publication year:

Year	Articles Published
2013	0
2014	0
2015	0
2016	0
2017	1
2018	0
2019	1
2020	0
2021	0
2022	0
2023	0

Methodology:

	Total	Survey	Case Study	Interviews/Focus Groups	Lit. Review (academic)	Documentary analysis	Stakeholder Engagement/Participatory Design
Qualitative	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Primary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Quantitative	2						0
<i>Primary</i>	2	0	0	0	1	1	0
<i>Secondary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mixed	0	0	0	0			0
<i>Primary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Disciplinary focus of research:

Disciplinary Category	Number of Articles
<i>Agricultural Sciences*</i>	0
<i>Biology & Biochemistry*</i>	0
<i>Chemistry*</i>	0
<i>Clinical Medicine*</i>	0
<i>Computer Science*</i>	0
<i>Engineering*</i>	0
<i>Environment/Ecology*</i>	0
<i>Geosciences*</i>	0
<i>Immunology*</i>	0
<i>Materials Science*</i>	0
<i>Mathematics*</i>	0
<i>Microbiology*</i>	0
<i>Molecular Biology & Genetics*</i>	0
<i>Neuroscience & Behavior*</i>	0
<i>Pharmacology & Toxicology*</i>	0
<i>Physics*</i>	0
<i>Plant & Animal Science*</i>	0
<i>Psychiatry/Psychology*</i>	0
<i>Space Science*</i>	0
<i>Social Studies†</i>	0
<i>Education†</i>	0
<i>Architecture Building & Planning†</i>	0
<i>Business & Administrative Studies†</i>	0
<i>Creative Arts & Design†</i>	0
<i>Historical & Philosophical Studies†</i>	0
<i>Languages†</i>	0
<i>Law†</i>	0
<i>Mass Communications & Documentation†</i>	0
<i>Multidisciplinary*</i>	2
<i>Practitioner‡</i>	0

* adapted from Web of Science ESI Classifications

† adapted from HESA JACS 3.0 Classifications

‡ ad-hoc category based on study requirements

Geographical focus:

NA/no country	Multi-country
2	0

Theoretical Approach:

Stated	Not-stated
0	2

3.6. Researchers' mental health and well-being in relation to research misconduct (including those employed in uncertain work conditions)

Total number of articles included (n)
5

Articles by publication year:

Year	Articles Published
2013	0
2014	0
2015	0
2016	0
2017	0
2018	1
2019	0
2020	0
2021	1
2022	2
2023	1

Methodology:

	Total	Survey	Case Study	Interviews/Focus Groups	Lit. Review (academic)	Documentary analysis	Stakeholder Engagement/Participatory Design	Other
Qualitative	0							
<i>Primary</i>	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Quantitative	0							
<i>Primary</i>	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mixed	0							
<i>Primary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Disciplinary focus of research:

Disciplinary Category	Number of Articles
<i>Agricultural Sciences*</i>	0
<i>Biology & Biochemistry*</i>	0
<i>Chemistry*</i>	0
<i>Clinical Medicine*</i>	0
<i>Computer Science*</i>	0
<i>Engineering*</i>	0
<i>Environment/Ecology*</i>	0
<i>Geosciences*</i>	0
<i>Immunology*</i>	0
<i>Materials Science*</i>	0
<i>Mathematics*</i>	0
<i>Microbiology*</i>	0
<i>Molecular Biology & Genetics*</i>	0
<i>Neuroscience & Behavior*</i>	0
<i>Pharmacology & Toxicology*</i>	0
<i>Physics*</i>	0
<i>Plant & Animal Science*</i>	0
<i>Psychiatry/Psychology*</i>	0
<i>Space Science*</i>	0
<i>Architecture, Building & Planning†</i>	0
<i>Social Studies†</i>	0
<i>Law†</i>	0
<i>Business & Administrative Studies†</i>	0
<i>Mass Communications & Documentation†</i>	0
<i>Languages†</i>	0
<i>Historical & Philosophical Studies†</i>	0
<i>Creative Arts & Design†</i>	0
<i>Education†</i>	0
<i>Multidisciplinary*</i>	5
<i>Practitioner‡</i>	0

* adapted from Web of Science ESI Classifications

† adapted from HESA JACS 3.0 Classifications

‡ ad-hoc category based on study requirements

Geographical focus:

NA/no country	Multicountry	Spain	Belgium	Netherlands	Croatia
1	0	1	1	1	1

Theoretical Approach:

Stated	Not-stated
0	3
specific approach (if stated)	number of articles
<i>organisational psychology</i>	1
<i>gendered institution approach</i>	1

3.7. Gender dimensions and power relations in the context of research misconduct

Total number of articles included (n)
10

Articles by publication year:

Year	Articles Published
2013	0
2014	2
2015	1
2016	1
2017	0
2018	0
2019	2
2020	1
2021	1
2022	1
2023	1

Methodology:

	Total	Survey	Case Study	Interviews/Focus Groups	Lit. Review (academic)	Documentary analysis	Stakeholder Engagement/Participatory Design
Qualitative	7						
<i>Primary</i>	6	1	0	4	1	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Quantitative	3						
<i>Primary</i>	2	2	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
Mixed	0						
<i>Primary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Disciplinary focus of research:

Disciplinary Category	Number of Articles
<i>Agricultural Sciences*</i>	0
<i>Biology & Biochemistry*</i>	0
<i>Chemistry*</i>	0
<i>Clinical Medicine*</i>	0
<i>Computer Science*</i>	0
<i>Engineering*</i>	0
<i>Environment/Ecology*</i>	0
<i>Geosciences*</i>	0
<i>Immunology*</i>	0
<i>Materials Science*</i>	0
<i>Mathematics*</i>	0
<i>Microbiology*</i>	0
<i>Molecular Biology & Genetics*</i>	0
<i>Neuroscience & Behavior*</i>	0
<i>Pharmacology & Toxicology*</i>	0
<i>Physics*</i>	0
<i>Plant & Animal Science*</i>	0
<i>Psychiatry/Psychology*</i>	2
<i>Space Science*</i>	0
<i>Architecture, Building & Planning†</i>	0
<i>Social Studies†</i>	0
<i>Law†</i>	0
<i>Business & Administrative Studies†</i>	1
<i>Mass Communications & Documentation†</i>	0
<i>Languages†</i>	1
<i>Historical & Philosophical Studies†</i>	0
<i>Creative Arts & Design†</i>	0
<i>Education†</i>	0
<i>Multidisciplinary*</i>	6
<i>Practitioner‡</i>	0

* adapted from Web of Science ESI Classifications

† adapted from HESA JACS 3.0 Classifications

‡ ad-hoc category based on study requirements

Geographical focus:

NA/no country	Multicountry	Belgium	Netherlands	Italy	USA	Iran	Estonia	Norway	UK	Germany
3	2	2	2	3	1	1	2	2	2	1

Theoretical Approach:

Stated	Not-stated
0	7
specific approach (if stated)	number of articles
<i>theory of social power (French and Raven)</i>	2
<i>entrepreneurial risk return perspective</i>	1

3.8. Research on the effectiveness of research ethics and integrity training

Total number of articles included (n)
31

Articles by publication year:

Year	Articles Published
2013	2
2014	2
2015	3
2016	3
2017	8
2018	4
2019	2
2020	1
2021	2
2022	3
2023	1

Methodology:

Qualitative	15						
<i>Primary</i>	8	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Secondary</i>	7	0	0	0	7	0	
Quantitative	12						
<i>Primary</i>	4	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Secondary</i>	8	0	0	0	8	0	
Mixed	4						
<i>Primary</i>	2	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Secondary</i>	2	0	0	0	2	0	

Disciplinary focus of research:

Disciplinary Category	Number of Articles
<i>Agricultural Sciences*</i>	0
<i>Biology & Biochemistry*</i>	0
<i>Chemistry*</i>	0
<i>Clinical Medicine*</i>	4
<i>Computer Science*</i>	0
<i>Engineering*</i>	0
<i>Environment/Ecology*</i>	0
<i>Geosciences*</i>	0
<i>Immunology*</i>	0
<i>Materials Science*</i>	0
<i>Mathematics*</i>	0
<i>Microbiology*</i>	0
<i>Molecular Biology & Genetics*</i>	0
<i>Neuroscience & Behavior*</i>	0
<i>Pharmacology & Toxicology*</i>	0
<i>Physics*</i>	0
<i>Plant & Animal Science*</i>	0
<i>Psychiatry/Psychology*</i>	1
<i>Space Science*</i>	0
<i>Architecture, Building & Planning†</i>	0
<i>Social Studies†</i>	0
<i>Law†</i>	0
<i>Business & Administrative Studies†</i>	2
<i>Mass Communications & Documentation†</i>	0
<i>Languages†</i>	0
<i>Historical & Philosophical Studies†</i>	0
<i>Creative Arts & Design†</i>	0
<i>Education†</i>	0
<i>Multidisciplinary*</i>	24
<i>Practitioner‡</i>	0

* adapted from Web of Science ESI Classifications

† adapted from HESA JACS 3.0 Classifications

‡ ad-hoc category based on study requirements

Geographical focus:

NA/no country	Multicountry	USA	Estonia	Finland	Belgium	Canada
1	17	6	4	1	1	1

Theoretical Approach:

Stated	Not-stated
0	10
specific approach (if stated)	number of articles
<i>theory 1 - learning theories</i>	21

3.9. Case-based methodologies

Total number of articles included (n)
11

Articles by publication year:

Year	Articles Published
2013	3
2014	0
2015	0
2016	3
2017	3
2018	0
2019	0
2020	0
2021	0
2022	1
2023	1

Methodology:

Column1	Total	Case Survey Study		Interviews/Focus Groups	Lit. Review (academic)	Documentary analysis	Stakeholder Engagement/Participatory Design
Qualitative	4						
<i>Primary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	4	0	0	0	4	0	0
Quantitative	7						
<i>Primary</i>	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	4	0	0	0	4	0	0
Mixed	0						
<i>Primary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Secondary</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Disciplinary focus of research:

Disciplinary Category	Number of Articles
<i>Agricultural Sciences*</i>	0
<i>Biology & Biochemistry*</i>	0
<i>Chemistry*</i>	0
<i>Clinical Medicine*</i>	0
<i>Computer Science*</i>	0
<i>Engineering*</i>	0
<i>Environment/Ecology*</i>	0
<i>Geosciences*</i>	0
<i>Immunology*</i>	0
<i>Materials Science*</i>	0
<i>Mathematics*</i>	0
<i>Microbiology*</i>	0
<i>Molecular Biology & Genetics*</i>	0
<i>Neuroscience & Behavior*</i>	0
<i>Pharmacology & Toxicology*</i>	0
<i>Physics*</i>	0
<i>Plant & Animal Science*</i>	0
<i>Psychiatry/Psychology*</i>	0
<i>Space Science*</i>	0
<i>Architecture, Building & Planning†</i>	0
<i>Social Studies†</i>	0
<i>Law†</i>	0
<i>Business & Administrative Studies†</i>	0
<i>Mass Communications & Documentation†</i>	0
<i>Languages†</i>	0
<i>Historical & Philosophical Studies†</i>	0
<i>Creative Arts & Design†</i>	0
<i>Education†</i>	9
<i>Multidisciplinary*</i>	2
<i>Practitioner‡</i>	0

* adapted from Web of Science ESI Classifications

† adapted from HESA JACS 3.0 Classifications

‡ ad-hoc category based on study requirements

Geographical focus:

NA/no country	Multi-country	USA
8	0	3

Theoretical Approach:

Stated	Not-stated
0	11

APPENDIX C: ANALYSIS OF CASE STUDIES BY COUNTRY

Please see the Excel dataset uploaded to the Zenodo platform for the data collated in BEYOND T1.2 Review of Real-life Cases of Research Misconduct, which contains the evidence analysed for the findings in Part 2 of this deliverable: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12081543>

APPENDIX D: LIST OF RELEVANT EU-FUNDED PROJECTS

Added by	Project title	Years	Programme	GA number	Website	Key deliverables and outputs
TRI	SOPs4RI (Standard Operating Procedures for Research Integrity)	2019-2022	Horizon 2020	824481	https://sops4ri.eu	see D3.2: Scoping reviews including multi-level model of research cultures and research conduct.
TRI	ENVRIplus (Environmental Research Infrastructures Providing Shared Solutions for Science and Society)	2015-2019	Horizon 2020	654182	https://envri.eu/home-envri-fair/	see D13.3: Ethical Guidelines for Research Infrastructures
TRI	ENVRI-FAIR (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability [FAIRness] in environmental research infrastructures)	2019-2023	Horizon 2020	824068	https://envri.eu/home-envri-fair/	see D6.1 Inventory & gap analysis of FAIR training materials
UT	PRINTEGER (Promoting Integrity as an Integral Dimension of Excellence in Research)	2015-2018	Horizon 2020	665926	https://printeger.eu	see D3.9: Managing research integrity: An assessment of best practices from the organisational literature

Added by	Project title	Years	Programme	GA number	Website	Key deliverables and outputs
TRI	TRUST (Creating and enhancing TRUSTworthy, responsible and equitable partnerships in international research)	2015-2018	Horizon 2020	664771	https://trust-project.eu/project.eu	see under WP1: Report on Generic Risks of Exporting Non-Ethical Practices, Matrix mapping case studies onto risks [Exploitation Risks and Research Ethics Guidelines], Special Symposium in the “Cambridge Quarterly of Healthcare Ethics; see under WP5: Policy briefs for ethics committees.
TRI	PRO-RES (PROMoting integrity in the use of RESearch results)	2018-2021	Horizon 2020	788352	https://prores-project.eu/	of honest, by the book, deployment); see D5.1: Report on the interview outcomes with experts from science, policy making and from Research Ethics Committees; see D5.2: Report on future ethical requirements; see D6.1: Unethical use of research results.

Added by	Project title	Years	Programme	GA number	Website	Key deliverables and outputs
TRI	PRO-Ethics (Participatory Real Life Experiments in Research and Innovation Funding Organisations on Ethics)	2020-2023	Horizon 2020	872441	https://pro-ethics.eu/	see: Ethics Framework 0.1 and Guidelines; Policy Brief 1: Putting Citizens at the Centre of Research and Innovation; Summary and Evaluation Reports on Pilot I Results; Results of Workshop 1 with Ethics Committees and Research Integrity Bodies; Paper Manuscript on Participatory Practices and Ethics Issues in Innovation; PRO-Ethics Project Handbook.

Added by	Project title	Years	Programme	GA number	Website	Key deliverables and outputs
TRI	ROSiE (Responsible Open Science in Europe)	2021-2024	Horizon 2020	101006430	https://rosie-project.eu/	see D1.1: Report on the relationship (tensions, challenges, overlaps) between RI, the wider RE perspective and OS; D1.2: Suggested framework for addressing the (epistemic-ethical) challenges; D5.1: Report on existing policies and guidelines.
TRI	VIRT2UE (Virtue based ethics and Integrity of Research: Train-theTrainer program for Upholding the principles and practices of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity)	2018-2021	Horizon 2020	787580	Website no longer available	Information not available

Added by	Project title	Years	Programme	GA number	Website	Key deliverables and outputs
TRI	INTEGRITY (empowering students through evidence based, scaffolded learning of Responsible Conduct in Research)	2019-2022	Horizon 2020	824586	https://h2020integrity.eu	Glossary for Research and Academic Ethics and Integrity; various Tool Kits for pupils, students, and research practitioners.
TRI	ENERI (European Network of Research Ethics and Research Integrity)	2016-2019	Horizon 2020	710184	https://eneri.eu	see: ENERI Handbook on RI (Recommendations for the Investigation of Research Misconduct); D2.2: RIO Boot Camp Prototype; D2.4: REC Bootcamp Prototype; D1.3: Report of midterm Consensus Conferences; D3.1: Appendix: Manual; D6.1: Pilot set of Indicators and Criteria for Certification; D6.2: Evaluation Report on Pilot Set of Indicators.

Added by	Project title	Years	Programme	GA number	Website	Key deliverables and outputs
TRI	Path2Integrity (Rotatory roleplaying and role models to enhance the research integrity culture)	2019-2022	Horizon 2020	824488	https://www.path2integrity.eu	see: D3.1: Path2Integrity roadmap; D3.2: Path2Integrity Handbooks of Instructions: The P2ILC Programme; D4.2: Path2Integrity Training Curricula;
TRI	HYBRIDA (Embedding a comprehensive ethical dimension to organoid based research and resulting technologies)	2021-2024	Horizon 2020	101006012	https://hybrid-a-project.eu	Information not available
TRI	SIENNA (Stakeholder informed ethics for new technologies with high socioeconomic and human rights impact)	2017-2021	Horizon 2020	741716	https://www.sienna-project.eu	see D2.3: Survey of REC approaches and codes for genomics; D4.3: Survey of REC approaches and codes for Artificial Intelligence & Robotics; D5.1: Report documenting elements to open and complement operational guidelines for research ethics committees.

Added by	Project title	Years	Programme	GA number	Website	Key deliverables and outputs
TRI	PREPARED	2022-2025	Horizon 2020	10048353	https://prepared-project.eu	Information not available
TRI	EnTIRE (Mapping Normative Frameworks for EThics and Integrity of Research)	2017-2021	Horizon 2020	741782	Website no longer available	Information not available
TRI	TechEthos (Ethics for Technologies with High Socio-economic impact)	2021-2023	Horizon 2020	101006249	https://www.techethos.eu	see: D2.1 Methodology for ethical analysis, scan results of existing ethical
TRI	SHERPA (Shaping the ethical dimensions of smart information systems (SIS) – a European perspective)	2019-2023	Horizon 2020	786641	https://www.project-sherpa.eu/	see: D1.4 Report on Ethical Tensions and Social Impacts; D3.2 Guidelines for the development and the use of SIS.

Added by	Project title	Years	Programme	GA number	Website	Key deliverables and outputs
TRI	PANELFIT (Participatory Approaches to a New Ethical and Legal Framework for ICT)	2018-2022	Horizon 2020	788039	https://www.panelfit.eu	see: D5.5 The Citizens' Info Pack and Guide for Vulnerable People.
TRI	ETHNA (Ethics Governance System for RRI in Higher Education, Funding and Research Centres)	2020-2023	Horizon 2020	872360	https://ethnasystem.eu	see: D2.1 Report on the state of the art and best practices; D2.2 SWOT analyses of current and future HEFRC RRI initiatives; D2.3 Review article on the scientific literature; D2.4 Scientific article on implementation of RRI; D3.1 Mapping stakeholders and scoping involvement – a guide for HEFRCs; D3.2 Gauging the potential societal contributions of research and innovation – a guide for HEFRCs; D3.3 Stakeholder involvement in ethical governance of R&I – a guide for

Added by	Project title	Years	Programme	GA number	Website	Key deliverables and outputs
						HEFRCs; D4.3 Blueprint for institutional change to implement an effective RRI governance; D6.2 Final version of the ETHNA System; D6.4 Manual of trainers on the ETHNA System; D7.7 Policy brief / recommendation paper.
TRI	DEFORM (Define the global and financial impact of research misconduct)	2016-2018	Horizon 2020	710246	Website no longer available	Information not available